

Digital Technology: A Tool of Customer Satisfaction in B2C Supply Chain of Courier Services in Pakistan

“Responsiveness, Accuracy, and Efficiency as Mediators”

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is entirely my own and has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, for a Doctor of Business Administration (DBA), Doctor of Professional Studies (DProf), Doctor of Engineering (EngD), Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), or any other comparable academic award at this or any other institution. This thesis represents original research carried out under the supervision and guidance of the relevant academic authorities, and no portion of it has been previously used to satisfy the requirements for any other degree or qualification.

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ABSTRACT

Background: This thesis examines how digital technologies effect customer satisfaction within the Pakistani business-to-consumer (B2C) supply chain of courier services. Along with explosive growth in e-commerce have come new challenges confronting courier companies; yet widespread customer dissatisfaction persists across responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Although digital technologies possess ultimate transformative ability within international supply chains, empirical research continues to be minimal about how they impact service quality and customer satisfaction in emerging markets.

Objective: To investigate how digital technologies influence customer satisfaction in Pakistan's B2C courier industry and to test the mediating effects of service quality dimensions—responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency.

Methods: Quantitative research design was employed such that a structured questionnaire was administered to users of courier services functioning in Lahore, Pakistan. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) and SPSS 26 in order to evaluate proposed relations and mediation effects.

Results: It was found that both responsiveness and accuracy significantly lead to higher levels of customer satisfaction having direct and indirect effects while efficiency does not have any significant effect. This finding implies that customers attach a higher preference to reliable information updates and correct deliveries compared to transportation speed. Such a finding identifies how responsiveness and accuracy are key service features in securing customer trust and satisfaction in digitalized courier services.

Conclusion: This research makes a supply chain and service quality literature contribution by providing empirical findings within a developing nation context. It then supplies actionable advice to courier services firms, with a message of importance that investments in technologies improving real-time responsiveness and accuracy in deliveries will be more likely to yield satisfaction improvement rather than efficiency programs. It ends the research with managerial insights, identifies limitations, and suggests agendas for further research in digital technologies within wider service industries.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Digital Technologies, Service Quality, Responsiveness, Accuracy, Efficiency, Courier Industry, Lahore, Pakistan.

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CHAPTER 1. Background of the Research

Customer satisfaction is fundamental in marketing and company strategies (Rane et al., 2023). In the current business environment, customer satisfaction is crucial in a highly global, extremely competitive economy, especially in providing services such as the courier industry (Akil & Urgan, 2022). Customer satisfaction refers to customers' attitudes toward a product or service (Andri et al., 2022). Customer satisfaction is the degree to which a customer's expectations are fulfilled (Cronin and Brady, 2005). It is likely an evaluative judgement that compares perceived performance with a preexisting expectation (Fornell, 1992). Customer satisfaction is, therefore, directly proportional to increased profitability, loyalty, and word-of-mouth communication (Hoyer & MacInnis, 2001). A service industry's capacity to comprehend and sustain customer satisfaction is essential to its success since it directly impacts customer retention, positive word of mouth, increased sales, and profitability (Dominici and Guzzo, 2010).

Customer satisfaction is a crucial aspect of business success, especially in service-oriented industries like courier companies (Dominici & Guzzo, 2010; Hoyer & MacInnis, 2001). In these contexts, prompt shipment delivery and reliable communication are essential factors that impact customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention (Rane et al., 2023). The evolution of digital technologies has raised customers' expectations significantly, especially for real-time tracking and automated interaction with service organizations. In Pakistan, the rapid expansion of e-commerce has led to an increasing demand for courier services; however, companies continue to struggle with operational inefficiencies, errors, and delayed response times (Javed, 2020; Khan, 2022; Zia et al., 2024). The uneven deployment of digital technologies worsens the situation, with negative implications for customer satisfaction, and hinders the industry's development (Irshad et al., 2022). The research objective is to examine the contribution of digital technologies to responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in the Pakistani courier sector with the overall aim of improving customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is important in achieving success in the competitive business world, particularly in service businesses such as courier companies. In these enterprises, elements such as timely and on-time deliveries, as well as decent and understandable communication, are imperative in significantly impacting customer retention and building customer loyalty (Dominici & Guzzo, 2010; Hoyer & MacInnis, 2001). The continuous progress in digital technologies has

significantly elevated customer expectations, especially with regard to the need for real-time tracking capabilities and automated customer interactions (Rane et al., 2023). In Pakistan, while there has been a tremendous increase in e-commerce development that has led to an increased demand for courier services, many companies operating in this sector are beset by significant challenges, including inefficiencies in their operations, lack of accuracy in their services, and delayed response to customer enquiries (Javed, 2020; Khan, 2022; Zia et al., 2024). The uneven and disparate adoption of digital technologies among these companies further reinforces these inherent problems, adversely impacting overall customer satisfaction, ultimately limiting the industry's growth potential as a whole (Irshad et al., 2022).

The research investigates the imperative function of digital technologies in augmenting responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in Pakistan's courier industry, with the goal of significantly improving customer satisfaction. The three dimensions—responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency—were selected for analysis intentionally because they hold a direct correlation with key performance areas in the courier industry, which, in turn, significantly impact customers' perceptions regarding service quality and their overall satisfaction with the services being provided. Responsiveness is the effectiveness and timeliness with which a company can respond to and address customer enquiries and problems that are likely to arise, while accuracy is about reliability and precision in making proper deliveries on time. Efficiency, however, addresses the effective use of resources and the timeliness of the services provided. All these factors—responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency—become key determinants of business success and achieving high customer satisfaction levels, specifically for the case of courier services (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Kolasińska-Morawska et al., 2022; Qing et al., 2023).

This particular research study did not address or include other SERVQUAL dimensions, such as tangibility and empathy, in its analysis. This was because these dimensions are thought to be less relevant to the courier sector's main operational issues. The dimension of tangibility particularly addresses factors such as physical facilities and the general appearance of services, which have an insignificant impact on the main operational problems that courier services encounter on a daily basis. Empathy, as providing personalised customer care and attention, while undoubtedly important and worthwhile, do not fundamentally or adequately deal with the more basic, more systemic operating inefficiencies along with accuracy-related problems that are of primary concern within the context of this particular study (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

1.1. Context of the Research

The courier industry in Pakistan has grown rapidly as the country's youthful, internet savvy population embraces online shopping. With over 250 million people—60 % of whom are under thirty—Pakistan is the fifth most populous country in the world (Reuters, 2022; World Population Review, 2024). E-commerce revenues have surged, placing Pakistan among the top forty e-commerce markets and generating about US\$ 6 billion in 2021 (Nachar, 2019; Dawood, 2019; Barrech et al., 2023). This boom has led to a strong demand for reliable last mile delivery services. Forecasts value the courier market at around US\$ 2.82 billion in 2024, rising to US\$ 3.64 billion by 2030, with a CAGR of roughly 4.35 % (Mordor Intelligence, 2024). Major players such as Pakistan Post, TCS, Leopards Courier Services (LCS), DHL Pakistan and M&P Courier dominate a sector that contributes approximately 6% of total employment and more than 22 % of the services sector's GDP (Business Recorder, 2019). New logistics start-ups are also entering the market, backed by substantial venture capital, signalling both opportunities for expansion and increased competition (Logistics Tech Startups in Pakistan, 2022).

Market forces involve a mix of both opportunities and threats. Today, customers are putting a premium on the immediacy of tracking, expedite shipping, and efficient communication (Narayanan & Antoniou, 2022; Mohammad et al., 2023). Major courier companies thus invested in mobile applications, GPS route optimization based on routes, and automated sorting mechanisms. However, not all organizations made such equivalent investments; small businesses use conventional approaches since technology is prohibitively expensive, infrastructure is insufficient or inadequate, and there is a lack of training for workers satisfaction (Glenn et al., 2021; Corejova et al., 2022; Su et al., 2022; Rapi, 2022; Remondino & Zanin, 2022; Gupta et al., 2023; Janinhoff et al., 2024; Kraugusteeliana & Violin, 2024). Infrastructural shortcomings, unstable fuel prices, and inconsistent addressing systems make the challenge of on-time delivery even greater. Industry regulatory standards are still in a state of confusion. However, increased access to the internet, a growing middle-class population, and government efforts towards developing logistics infrastructure are encouraging signs for industry expansion (Shamsi & Syed, 2015; Khan, 2022; Zia et al., 2024). As such, in this regard, research explores how digital technologies can improve responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency—who are major service quality components—all in an effort to meet the growing customer expectations and support sustainable development in the courier sector in Pakistan.

1.2. Problem Statement

The exponential increase in e-commerce in Pakistan has resulted in an extraordinary escalation in demand for quality and trustworthy courier services (Naseem et al., 2021; Barrech et al., 2023; Mordor Intelligence, 2024). However, despite this heightened demand, the courier sector in Pakistan still suffers from numerous issues based on operational inefficiencies, delayed response times, and a high incidence of discrepancies in delivery (Shabbir, 2024). Operational inefficiencies are manifested in many ways, including poor logistics management, inefficient route planning, and ineffective utilization of existing resources (Tang et al., 2022; Jaen, 2024). Such inefficiencies are likely to result in late deliveries, higher operating expenses, and reduced reliability of services (Javed, 2020; Khan, 2022; Zia et al., 2024).

Persistent service-quality problems in Pakistan's courier industry are well documented. Consumer courts have repeatedly penalised Pakistan Post for proven delivery negligence—for example, one case imposed a fine of over Rs 1.3 million for failure to deliver time-critical documents, and another sanctioned staff after a parcel arrived as “garbage” instead of the booked goods (Dawn, 2024). The Universal Postal Union has also highlighted the need for special handling of “undelivered inbound parcels,” underscoring systemic last-mile challenges (UPU, 2022). At the industry level, the World Bank Logistics Performance Index gives Pakistan an overall score of 2.42/5 (2018), with low ratings for infrastructure, competence, and timeliness—dimensions closely tied to slow response and delivery reliability (World Bank, 2018; World Bank, 2023).

Empirical studies carried out in Pakistan validate these structural problems: a countrywide survey of 659 e-logistics users confirmed that transit time and frequency of distribution are key variables affecting customer satisfaction and thus validate that irregular delivery performance and delay remain significant issues (Memon et al., 2023). In addition, an analysis of hub optimization carried out in Lahore suggested that moving one main distribution center could shorten the mean delivery distance by up to around 16%, thus exposing weaknesses within the current configuration of the network responsible for long journeys and late delivery (Faisal & Khalid, 2024). Altogether, these results provide hard, country-level evidence of inefficiency, slow reaction times, and delivery mistakes within the courier and e-logistics markets throughout Pakistan.

Additionally, slow response times considerably reduce customer satisfaction (Tang et al., 2022; Prapinit et al., 2024). Customers are increasingly demanding timely and efficient communication, especially in cases of delay or complications in their deliveries (Shamsi & Syed, 2015; Memon et al., 2023). Pakistan courier services consistently experience delays in responding to customer queries and resolving delivery problems, which lead to customer frustration and dissatisfaction (Qureshi, 2025). Research has shown that effectiveness and timeliness in responding to customer service problems have a significant impact on both overall customer satisfaction and the perceived quality of the service delivered (Zia et al., 2024; Situmorang et al., 2025).

Inaccurate deliveries are responsible for increased rates of customer dissatisfaction (Dundar & Ozturk, 2020). Typical problems faced by the Pakistani courier industry are incorrect addresses, misplaced deliveries, product damage, and delayed or failed deliveries (Qureshi, 2025). Inaccuracies not only disappoint customer expectations but also significantly impact customer satisfaction and the likelihood of future transactions. High return levels, resulting from inaccuracies, further increase operational costs and negatively impact overall efficiency (Shabbir, 2024). Evidence of continued problems includes attempted delivery frauds, inadequate communication with customers about delivery status, and manual handling and paperwork process errors (Azam, 2024).

The inconsistent application of digital technology “Digital technologies are electronic tools and devices—such as tablets, computers, mobile phones and multimedia systems—that store, generate or process information. They allow users to access and manage resources (e.g., social media platforms, online games, streaming services) and underpin modern activities like online learning (Sienna, 2025).” within the courier sector enhances these difficulties (McGuirk, 2021). Although there are significant technological advancements that promise to enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, most courier businesses in Pakistan have not yet adopted these tools (Shabbir, 2024). The partial use of some of the digital technologies, including real-time tracking systems, automated customer interaction platforms, and predictive data analytics, is responsible for the chronic problems in service delivery (Qureshi, 2025). The inconsistency that was witnessed can be due to a range of factors, including inadequate technology infrastructure, inadequate awareness or training for the employees, resistance to organizational change, and high cost of implementation as perceived (Irshad et al., 2022).

Despite the evident benefits of digital technologies as seen globally, there remains a significant

gap in empirical research on their usage and effectiveness being implemented in Pakistan's courier industry (Alam et al., 2025; Dubey et al., 2023). Studies conducted internationally highlight the significant impact that digital technologies can have on increasing the efficiency of operations, improving the accuracy of services, and enabling quicker responses to customer enquiries and issues (Lee & Baker, 2017; Zhong et al., 2022). Despite that, similar research studies in Pakistan are limited, hence the important knowledge gap on the localized applicability and suitability of such technologies. This gap poses an obstacle for industry players who require evidence-based recommendations on how to ensure effective deployment of digital solutions within the local context and operational environment typical of Pakistan.

This research aims to fill the gap in knowledge by quantifying how digital technologies can bring responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency to the Pakistani courier sector. By focusing on these particular aspects of service quality, the research aims to discover how the adoption of technology can resolve the current operational issues and increase customer satisfaction. Lastly, the research aims to create a validated model that guides courier companies on how to leverage digital technologies strategically to neutralize operational inefficiencies and respond to evolving customer needs effectively.

1.2.1. Gaps in Theory and Practice

Many contexts, including the banking sector (Sureshchandar et al., 2002; Mosahab et al., 2010), fast food (Farooqui & Alwi, 2019), and telecommunication (Al Awadhi et al., 2021), have discussed customer satisfaction. However, few studies have addressed how digital technologies can enhance customer satisfaction within the courier industry, particularly in emerging markets like Pakistan. Research has demonstrated that digital technologies can enhance service quality and customer satisfaction (Lee & Baker, 2017; Demirel, 2022; Abdel-Hamid et al., 2022; Zhong et al., 2022). However, the impact of digital technologies on critical factors such as responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in the courier industry remains largely unexplored. The few available studies focus on general service quality metrics and need to investigate the specific dynamics of the effect of digital technologies within the courier industry (Ejdys & Gulc, 2020).

In addition, Pakistan's socio-economic context presents both obstacles and opportunities when it comes to the adoption of digital technologies in the courier industry. However, the literature has not yet addressed this regional aspect. Most of the existing studies have focused on more

developed countries or other industries providing services, hence creating a significant understanding gap about how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction in the courier sector of Pakistan (Irshad et al., 2022; Alasadee & Alfatlawi, 2023).

I made a selective search of scholarly and professional materials such as "digital technology," "courier," "Pakistan," "customer satisfaction," and "service quality" for 2010–2024. Although there were some which dwelt upon digital transformation in supply chains or overall logistical effectiveness, there were no results which had any empirical evidencing connecting digital technologies with service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction in Pakistan's B2C courier sector. Other research, like Saxena (2017) and Loh et al., (2023), only uses conceptual frameworks and quantitative data from other fields, so they can't really show how complicated this relationship is in the courier business. As an illustration, a recent research paper on Pakistani courier supply chains explored Digital Transformation barriers and outlined technologies such as AI, IoT and blockchain which had the potential for optimizing operations (Zeeshan et al., 2025). However, it did not study customer satisfaction or service quality outcomes. Other research only focused on risks affecting logistics performance (Akram & Siddiqui, 2019) or explored service quality dimensions in countries like Malaysia and Kuwait; Pakistan was not a subject in such works (Rui et al., 2022). I found no empirical research which directly explores the effect of digital technologies on customer satisfaction through responsiveness, accuracy, or efficiency in the courier industry in Pakistan. The absence of such evidence proves the identified gap, thus enabling to state with conviction that an effective search yielded no relevant empirical works in this regard.

The research seeks to establish the effect of digital technologies on responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction within the Pakistani courier industry. To achieve this, the study examines how responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency influence the connections between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. This research places emphasis on developing practices that lead to efficient and effective service delivery in the courier market.

1.3. Research Aim

This research aims to investigate how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry, considering the mediation effects of three service quality components: responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency.

1.4. Research Objectives

The present investigation endeavours to fulfil the subsequent research objectives based on the arguments highlighted in the problem statement:

1. To examine the impact of digital technologies on responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction in the courier industry of Pakistan.
2. To examine the impact of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency on customer satisfaction.
3. To investigate the mediating effect of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.
4. To suggest a quantitatively tested model showing how digital technologies can be used to improve responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency to achieve customer satisfaction in the courier sector.

1.5. Research Questions

The previously discussed problem statement prompted the formulation of the following research questions.

1. To what extent do digital technologies influence responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry?
2. To what extent do responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency affect customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry?
3. How do responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency mediate the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction?
4. What quantitatively validated framework can be proposed to illustrate how digital technologies enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, thereby improving customer satisfaction?

1.6. Significance of the Research

This is an important study, as it will explain how digital technologies can be used to improve

service quality and customer satisfaction in the courier industry settings, especially in the wake of growing demand promoted by e-commerce. Basically, since customers are increasingly in need of rapid, reliable, and accurate deliveries, courier companies have to tap into technologies that enhance their responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. In markets where logistics challenges are common, embracing digital technologies remains critical for competitiveness. The specific ways that digital technologies impact service quality and mediate customer satisfaction remain largely unexplored. Therefore, this study aims to fill that knowledge gap by providing novel empirical evidence on the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction, as well as highlighting the mediating role of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in the Pakistani context, specifically in the courier industry.

1.7. Scope of the Research

The scope of the study is to research the impact of digital technologies on customer satisfaction within the courier business in Pakistan, narrowed down to only responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. The research shows how the technologies are going to affect customer satisfaction. The following elements define the scope of the investigation:

Geographic Aspect: This research explicitly focuses on the concepts mentioned above about Pakistani courier companies. In Pakistan, TCS, LCS, and M&P Courier & Logistics dominate a significant share of the courier industry. Therefore, the study restricts its scope to walk-in customers within Pakistan's courier industry. The major cities of Pakistan host their booking offices. Therefore, the research focuses solely on Lahore. This city is one of the major courier service markets because of its large population and considerable e-commerce business volume.

Industrial Aspect: With the growing e-commerce business in Pakistan, the research focuses on the courier and logistics industry, which plays a crucial role in the supply chain and distribution of goods. It examines the opportunities for courier companies to use digital technologies to improve the quality of their service and customer satisfaction.

Theoretical Framework: The SERVQUAL model appeared to be the most appropriate concept for this study's nature. Research has emphasised that responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency are components that should be present for the best customer satisfaction in the courier industry.

Technological Aspect: It explicitly investigates the influence of digital technologies on improving

service quality and customer satisfaction.

Research Methodology: This study is quantitative, where the implementation of a self-administered questionnaire-based survey and statistical data are involved in the collection and analysis through SPSS 26 and SMARTPLS 3.0. This research focuses on measuring the impact of digital technologies on the selected responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction.

1.8. Definitions of the Constructs

An operational definition embedded in research simply refers to the explicit criteria and procedures that outline how a particular concept is measured or observed in the study so that its methods are constantly applied to different investigations. This study outlines the operational definitions of several research variables.

1.8.1. Customer Satisfaction

Fornell (1992) states customer satisfaction is “an overall post-purchase evaluation.” Notably, the definition emphasises customers' impressions that differ from the expectations they set prior to purchasing. Current research uses this conception of customer satisfaction to guide its operationalisation.

1.8.2. Service Quality

Parasuraman et al., (1988) defined service quality as "the delivery of excellent or superior service relative to customer expectations." Service quality consists of two key components. A service is an activity or benefit that a provider wants to offer a customer. On the other hand, quality is one of the most critical components of an organisational strategy framework that enhances performance and operational efficiency. You can utilise the following strategies to ensure high-quality service delivery:

Responsiveness: the willingness and ability of the service provider to respond to enquiries, provide information, and do so promptly (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Accuracy: Accuracy is the measure of correctness and precision in service provision. According to Van Dyke et al. (1997), accuracy refers to the degree of consistency in providing services that align with the customer's needs and established criteria while maintaining a fair balance between

reducing errors and ensuring reliable results.

Efficiency: Efficiency is the best way to use resources, time, and effort based on better facilities for service provision. The assessment of this aspect hinges on how procedural guidelines can minimise waste and enhance quality and timeliness in service delivery (Zeithaml et al., 2002).

1.8.3. Digital Technologies

Digital technologies are “ICT-based tools, platforms, and systems that generate, process, and exchange data to enable connectivity, automation, and innovation (World Bank, 2023; UNCTAD, 2023; ITU, 2024)” For the purpose of this research, digital technologies are understood as solutions, systems, and tools based on information and communication technologies (ICT), including real-time tracking systems, automated customer care systems, mobile applications, GPS, IoT (Internet of Things), and data analytics, which are applied to enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in courier services.

1.9. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis consists of five chapters, all of which focus on different aspects of this study method and increase understanding regarding the effect of digital technologies on customer satisfaction within Pakistan's courier industry. The researcher has organised the chapters as follows:

The following chapter is an abridged literature review that critically analyses contemporary research on customer satisfaction, service quality, and digital technologies with an emphasis on the SERVQUAL model. We critically review the literature to identify areas that necessitate further investigation. As a result, this research seeks to fill these gaps by integrating digital technologies into traditional service quality models, thus setting the theoretical background for the research.

The methodology chapter directly follows the literature review and provides a detailed description of the research design and the methodologies adopted in this study. The chapter elucidates the decision to conduct the study using a quantitative approach, detailing all the data collection steps, including the design, respondent selection, sampling strategy, and the tools used to measure the most significant variables. This chapter also addresses the analytical approaches applied to test the study's hypotheses and validate its findings.

The following chapter focuses on the data analysis to present the results. This chapter examines

how digital technologies influence SERVQUAL's various components and, consequently, customer satisfaction. Statistical analysis tests the relationships between variables and evaluates the mediating effects of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Tables and figures present the results very explicitly and concisely.

This final chapter presents an in-depth discussion of the research findings in light of current literature and identifies the study's overall purpose. This chapter closely examines the major implications for the Pakistani courier industry, primarily emphasising the potential use of DT to enhance service quality and customer satisfaction. Limitations of the research are further discussed in this chapter, together with possible lines of future studies. Finally, this chapter concludes by highlighting the main findings and their contributions from both a theoretical and practical perspective, while actionable recommendations on how industry participants can effectively use digital technologies in enhancing customer satisfaction are discussed. This chapter concludes with a proposed framework and gives an idea of the study's possible contribution to the academic community and its effect on Pakistan's courier industry.

1.10. Summary of Chapter 1

Chapter 1 presents the study's background, states the problem, and identifies the significance of the research investigation. The first section of the research provides a brief overview of customer satisfaction, a crucial aspect of the service industry and, more significantly, the courier industry in Pakistan, which is experiencing significant growth following the introduction of electronic commerce. The chapter highlights various industry problems, including inefficiency and unreliability in service quality. All this becomes more aggravated when dealing with a non-digital integration base.

This chapter outlines the problem statement of the study, focussing on establishing the need to research how digital technologies might enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency to improve customer satisfaction in the courier business in Pakistan. It also seeks to fill the literature gap regarding the effect of digital technologies on service quality in developing countries. The main goals of this study are to find out how responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency play a part in figuring out how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction. As part of the goals, digital technologies will be looked at in terms of how they affect things like responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, as well as how they affect customer satisfaction, and suggestions will be made for

how to make the service delivery process more effective.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter presents a comprehensive review of extant literature pertaining to customer satisfaction, service quality dimensions, and digital technologies, with the aim of positioning their application in the courier industry context. The chapter begins by discussing earlier notions of customer satisfaction, including definitions, theories, and their critical significance in service firms. This part establishes the link between customer satisfaction and long-term business prosperity through descriptions of ways in which satisfied customers are crucial for firms.

Following this, the review focuses on the SERVQUAL model, a renowned model used to measure service quality. The discussion extensively examines its key dimensions, specifically responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, pointing out their immediate relevance to the operational dynamics of courier services. The rationale for the selection of these dimensions is explained, emphasizing their role in shaping customer perceptions and general satisfaction in the courier sector.

This chapter segment discusses how digital technologies impact service quality and customer satisfaction. It covers technologies including real-time monitoring, automated customer services, mobile apps, GPS route planning, IoT, and big data analytics, with their focus on responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. The discussion focuses on global digital technology success and best practices for Pakistan's courier industry.

Literature review discusses the SERVQUAL model that illustrates how customer satisfaction is affected by digital technology adoption and how expectations of service quality are formed. The chapter identifies key gaps in the literature, with particular emphasis on a lack of empirical studies on digital technology in the courier industry of Pakistan. The chapter highlights the distinctions between developed markets and emerging economies such as Pakistan and their impact on technology adoption and operations. The chapter identifies gaps that warrant further research and calls for comprehensive studies on the mentioned subjects in Pakistan.

2.1. Customer Satisfaction

A company's success hinges on its ability to satisfy its customers, which leads to customer retention and the likelihood of their repurchasing. When satisfied with the services, a customer will return for purchases and, according to Hague and Hague (2016), act as a brand ambassador

by spreading the positive experience. Rebekah and Sharyn (2004) suggest that satisfied customers significantly enhance the reach of businesses by facilitating access to high-quality goods and services through their networks.

Customer satisfaction is widely recognised as a critical factor for business success, but it is also a complex, multi-dimensional construct with various definitions and interpretations. Despite extensive research since 1965, a universal definition of customer satisfaction remains undeveloped (Giese & Cote, 2000). Few researchers consider customer satisfaction a process and emphasise its path and the interactions that lead to it (Hunt, 1977; Oliver, 1981; Fornell et al., 1992). Others define it as a response to this process, focussing on the emotional reaction or outcome (Howard and Sheth, 1969; Tse; Wilton, 1988; Halstead et al., 1994; Oliver, 1997). This distinction is crucial as it underscores distinct facets of customer satisfaction, such as the comprehensive experience or the ultimate assessment following service consumption. However, there is some debate regarding the primary treatment of customer satisfaction as an emotional or cognitive response (Westbrook and Reilly, 1983; Cadotte et al., 1987; Tse and Wilton, 1988; Bolton and Drew, 1991).

In this context, we perceive customer satisfaction as the overall assessment of a customer's experience with each service they receive, with a particular focus on the responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency facilitated by digital technologies. Even though customer satisfaction is a multi-dimensional construct, the focus of the present research is on its role as an outcome, influenced by these particular responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency factors, and thus fitting the perspective of "an overall post-purchase evaluation" by Fornell et al., (1992).

Other disagreements arise over the terms used to refer to this construct. Researchers use the terms "consumer satisfaction, customer satisfaction, or simply satisfaction" interchangeably (Kourilsky and Murray, 1981; Churchill and Surprenant, 1982; Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Spreng et al., 1996; Smith et al., 1999; Mittal et al., 1999). Fornell (1992) defined "customer satisfaction" as the buyer's overall reaction in the study's context.

This approach maintains academic depth without overloading the reader with potentially tangential theoretical debates. It focuses on how customer satisfaction is relevant to this research model, as well as the context of digital technologies and service quality in Pakistan's courier industry

Table 2. 1 Customer Satisfaction Definitions

Definition	Author	Year
"The buyer's cognitive state of being adequately or inadequately rewarded for the sacrifices he has undergone."	Howard and Sheth	1969
"The evaluation rendered that the experience was at least as good as it was supposed to be."	Hunt	1977
"Global evaluative judgment about product usage/consumption."	Westbrook	1980
"An evaluation of the surprise inherent in a product acquisition and/or consumption experience. In essence, the summary psychological state resulting when the emotion surrounding disconfirmed expectations is coupled with the consumer's prior feelings about the consumption experience."	Oliver	1981
"Conceptually, an outcome of purchase and use resulting from the buyer's comparison of the rewards and costs of the purchase relative to anticipated consequences."	Churchill and Surprenant	1982
"the evaluative response to the current consumption event...the consumer's response in a particular consumption experience to the evaluation of the perceived discrepancy between prior expectations (or some other norm of performance) and the actual performance of the product perceived after its acquisition."	Day	1984
"Conceptualized as a feeling developed from an evaluation of the use experience."	Cadotte et al.	1987
"The consumer's response to the evaluation of the perceived discrepancy between prior expectations (or some norm of performance) and the actual performance of the product as perceived after its consumption"	Tse and Wilton	1988
"Examined whether satisfaction was an emotion. Satisfaction is a summary attribute phenomenon coexisting with other consumption emotions."	Oliver	1992
"An overall postpurchase evaluation."	Fornell	1992
"A transaction-specific affective response resulting from the customer's comparison of product performance to some prepurchase standard."	Halstead et al.,	1994
"the consumer's fulfillment response. It is a judgment that a product or service feature, or the product or service itself,	Oliver	1997

provided (or is providing) a pleasurable level of consumption-related fulfillment, including levels of under- or over-fulfillment.”		
“perception of happiness or frustration which occurs as a result of the comparison between the performance of a product/service and expectations.”	Kotler & Keller	2016
“the psychological state experienced by consumers when their expectations prior to the consumption of a product/service meets or exceeds the actual consumption experience.”	Patricks et al.,	2020
“pleasure a consumer derives from a product/service performance visà-vis his/her expectation.”	Liang & Zhang	2020

Table 2.1 shows a variety of definitions and conceptualizations of customer satisfaction as reflected in seminal literature. It illustrates a common agreement among researchers that customer satisfaction is an evaluative judgment that arises through the comparison of customer expectations and perceived service performance. There are, however, differences in scope and complexity of these definitions, from simplistic perspectives emphasizing mere expectation fulfillment to more elaborate perspectives involving emotional as well as cognitive judgments. This variation highlights the multidimensional, rich nature of customer satisfaction that demands context-specific definitions, especially for those service businesses like courier services. One major gap revealed through this table is the absence of the explicit consideration of the effects of digital technology in such traditional definitions, indicating the necessity of modern-day studies incorporating digital interaction explicitly within satisfaction models.

2.2. Prior Research on Customer Satisfaction

Saxena (2017) believes that a company must satisfy its customers. Customers are the company's most important asset. Farooqui and Alwi (2019) assessed customer satisfaction using various factors, including service quality, pricing, ambiance, and food quality. Zeithaml et al., (2009) highlighted that customer satisfaction encompasses more than service quality, which focuses on specific aspects of service delivery. Lee and Baker (2017) supported the above argument and highlighted that service companies have made considerable efforts to understand, use, and manage technologies to increase customer satisfaction. Table 2.2 provides a summary of the prior research on customer satisfaction.

Table 2. 2 Prior Research on Customer Satisfaction

Author & Year	Method	Outcome
Yi (1989)	Review of Literature	He provides a comprehensive review of the definition, antecedents, determinants, and consequences of customer satisfaction. Emphasis on testable models and future research directions.
Oliva et al. (1992)	Survey (General Electric Supply)	They proposed methods for analyzing relationships among transaction costs, satisfaction, and loyalty using nonlinear techniques.
Willard (2000)	Case Study (California Community Colleges)	The study recommended macro/micro customer satisfaction models for the improvement of educational quality.
Giese and Cote (2000)	Review of Literature, Interviews	They found variation in satisfaction definitions, which points to the importance of standard definitions.
Sureshchandar et al. (2002)	Survey (Banking Industry of India)	Assessed service quality scales (SERVPERF) validity and diagnostic ability in the Indian context.
Jain and Gupta (2004)	Survey (Indian fast-food customers)	Assessed service quality scales (SERVPERF) validity and

		diagnostic ability in the Indian context.
Mosahab et al. (2010)	Survey (Sefah Bank Iran)	Satisfaction mediates between service quality and loyalty.
Hanif et al. (2010)	Survey (Telecom Sector Pakistan)	Price fairness and customer service are significant for customer satisfaction; price fairness had a stronger impact.
Biesok and Wyrod-Wrobel (2011)	Review of Literature	The study identified 21 indicators of customer satisfaction and highlighted the challenges associated with their measurement.
Lin et al. (2011)	Survey on online customers (Taiwan's University Undergraduate Students)	Delivery and product quality are the most critical factors for customer satisfaction.
Hilaludin and Cheng (2014)	Survey (Malaysia online shoppers)	E-service and information quality impact satisfaction.
Saxena (2017)	Review of Literature	Proposed Expectation-Value Addition-Satisfaction Matrix; emphasized value creation through innovation.
Lee and Baker (2017)	Case Study (Tourism/Hospitality)	The study examined the use of technology in the hospitality industry, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities it presents
Farooqui and Alwi (2019)	Survey (Pakistan fast food)	The study revealed that ambiance, price, and food

		quality have a positive impact on customer satisfaction.
Olumayowa (2019)	Survey (Banking Nigeria)	The speed and adaptability of digital banking improve satisfaction.
Rahman Zanzeh (2020)	Systematic Literature Review	Institutional and quality dimensions affect patient satisfaction
Ejdys & Gulc (2020)	Survey	The study confirmed that technological innovation and human interaction significantly enhance trust, which in turn activates perceived service quality and customer intention to reuse the service. Strengthening technological solutions in courier services raises trust, perceived quality, and ultimately customer loyalty.
Al Awadhi et al. (2021)	Survey (UAE telecom)	The study found a strong link between expectations, experiences, and satisfaction in digital solutions.
Zouari and Abdelhedi (2021)	Survey (Tunisian Islamic banks)	Digitalization is significant for service quality and satisfaction.
Sesar et al. (2021)	Review of Literature	Limited research on digitalization's link to satisfaction and loyalty during COVID-19.
Kidwai and Maqbool (2022)	Case Study (Courier Services)	Digital technologies significantly enhance efficiency, reliability, and customer satisfaction in

		courier services, particularly in light of the growing demands of e-commerce. The coordination of multimodal transport enabled by digital tools is vital to ensure a competitive advantage. This research points out employee satisfaction as an equally important element in delivering high-quality services in the courier sector.
Mohyudin (2022)	Survey (Pakistan Textile Industry)	The incorporation of advanced technologies enhances operational efficiency and product quality and allows customization of experiences to meet the specific needs of each customer. Digital tools are essential to enhance customer satisfaction and remain competitive in a global market that is growing more dynamic, the research states.
Irshad et al. (2022)	Case Study (Food Panda)	Service quality and social media marketing boost satisfaction; price has no moderating effect.
Abdel-Hamid et al., (2022)	Survey (Hotel Industry, Egypt)	The study found that while some hotels have embraced modern technology, the majority of hotels lack more advanced innovations like robots and self-service kiosks that can propel operations and service. It concludes that complete integration of digital technology will greatly improve guest experience, operational efficiency, and overall customer satisfaction, and it calls for greater focus on digital transformation in the

		hospitality sector.
Demirel (2022)	Online Survey (Turkey)	Digital service quality and dimensions, such as trust and enthusiasm, positively affect satisfaction.
Eckert et al. (2022)	Review (Insurance industry)	Digital transformation has a positive impact on various components of satisfaction, highlighting the importance of empirical studies.
Martínez de Miguel et al. (2022)	Survey (Automobile customers)	Dynamic capabilities via digital transformation enhance satisfaction.
Alasadee and Alfatlawi (2023)	Survey (Iraq Islamic Bank)	Digital technologies significantly impact satisfaction.
Loh et al., (2023)	Survey (Online responses from shipping customers of Singapore)	Digital platforms' user-friendliness boosts satisfaction.
Sobaih & AlSaif (2023)	Survey (Saudi Arabia-Logistics Industry)	The research identified that the various service quality dimensions positively impact customer satisfaction, and the most important one is reliability. It also revealed the existence of cultural differences, where the Saudi customers were more satisfied than their non-Saudi counterparts—maybe because of language or cultural familiarity. The research emphasizes the importance of concentrating on these service quality dimensions to better increase customer satisfaction.

Shah et al., (2023)	Case Study (SME-Pakistan)	The study established that digital innovation significantly mediates the impact of digital capabilities, organisational orientation, and digital transformation on SMEs' performance. It highlighted the adoption of digital technologies, the reskilling of employees, and the building of a digital mindset to enhance competitiveness and facilitate the digital economy. Continual innovation was regarded as central to improved financial and operational performance during a turbulent business landscape.
Hussain et al., (2023)	Case Study (Roshan Digital Account—Pakistan)	The study found that the security of the system, quality of service, and convenience are key elements in enhancing customer satisfaction for online banking. Each of these is a crucial role-player in building proper customer relationships and enhancing satisfaction levels.
Luan-Thanh (2024)	Survey (Ho Chi Minh)	Reliability, responsiveness, content, accessibility, and expectations influence M-commerce satisfaction.
Lohano et al., (2024)	Survey (Private Banking Sector – Hyderabad, Pakistan)	The study confirmed that technology is transforming the conventional banking models, in which an enhanced customer experience is at the core of delivering healthy financial results. The integration of digital banking tools leads to increased customer satisfaction and facilitates improved financial

		performance for banks.
Ashfaq et al., (2024)	Survey (China)	The study found that firms that adopt digitalisation and services achieve superior outcomes in terms of financial performance, operational efficiency, and customer satisfaction. It concludes that novel service offerings and digital innovations are key to sustaining competitiveness and ensuring long-term financial growth.

Yi (1989) critically reviews the literature in these three areas: what customer satisfaction is, how it is defined and measured, its antecedents and determinants, and its consequences. Customers generally describe customer satisfaction as their response to the perceived discrepancy between their expectations and the perceived performance of a product or service. The disconfirmation and pre-experience comparison standards are used to measure customer satisfaction. Previous studies have focused on data description and hypothesis testing. Efforts to create testable customer satisfaction models have also accelerated. Some possible research directions include creating a complete model of customer satisfaction that encompasses at least the most important variables, setting benchmarks, looking into how expectations are formed, looking into how customer satisfaction affects attitude changes, comparing the importance of different complaint behaviours, looking into the factors that affect the nature of complaints, and exploring how word-of-mouth affects those who receive it. Yi (1989) suggested that investigating these can provide a more complete picture of customer satisfaction.

Oliva et al., (1992) conducted a survey at General Electric Supply. They recommended a method for analysing sophisticated behaviour to design service plans more precisely by recognising the interrelationships among customer transaction costs, satisfaction, and loyalty. They also suggested that researchers adopt nonlinear tools, such as catastrophe theory, to better understand the dynamics underlying them.

Willard's (2000) case study of California Community Colleges proposes conceptualising customer satisfaction in macro- and micro-models. The study postulates that community institutions must measure and assess student satisfaction based on an accurate, global view. We utilise the models to enhance student satisfaction and deliver quality education. Logically, macro-models include micro-models, so there must be a conceptual spillover. However, other analysts may use a different approach when conceptualising these frameworks.

In this regard, Giese and Cote (2000) reviewed existing studies and found extreme heterogeneity in the definition of satisfaction. Consistency in the definition, a fundamental prerequisite for these kinds of investigations, still

restricts the impact of the customer satisfaction study.

Sureshchandar et al., (2002) surveyed the Indian banking industry to examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. The research identified that academics have recently focused significantly on this relationship. However, the exact nature of this relationship remains unclear. Many scholars have used single-item scales to operationalise customer satisfaction, whereas others have used multiple-item scales. Their research takes a different approach, viewing customer satisfaction as a multidimensional construct. However, it advocates operationalising customer satisfaction using the same factors as service quality. Researchers have used this method to study the relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality. While the variables are independent, their strong relationship indicates that an increase in one will likely lead to an increase in the other. This study recommended investigating the correlations between service quality and customer satisfaction in other service business industries.

Jain and Gupta (2004) surveyed Delhi-based fast-food customers to evaluate their ability to diagnose problems using the two service quality scales. Their empirical tests on service quality scales show that the SERVPERF scale outperforms others in terms of validity, reliability, and methodology. However, a full explanation of this study remains elusive, and the diagnostic efficiency of the scales clearly lacks empirical support.

For instance, Mosahab et al. (2010) surveyed Sefah Bank Tehran customers to establish the relationship between loyalty, customer satisfaction, and service quality. The findings of this study indicate that customer satisfaction mediates between service quality and service loyalty.

Hanif et al., (2010) surveyed telecom providers in Pakistan to determine the factors influencing customer satisfaction with a specific brand. The researchers used price and customer service as criteria to predict customer satisfaction. The findings demonstrated that, while both variables significantly contributed to explaining customer satisfaction, price fairness had a more significant effect on customer satisfaction than customer service.

Biesok and Wyrod-Wrobel (2011) reviewed the existing literature and identified 21 customer satisfaction metrics based on previous research. They also suggested that measuring customer satisfaction can require time and effort, even with the wide range of options.

Lin et al., (2011) performed an online survey of undergraduate students at Taiwan's universities to determine the factors influencing online customer satisfaction in Taiwan. The study highlighted qualities such as information, system, service, product, delivery, and perceived pricing as predictors of customer satisfaction. The results confirmed that information, system, service, product, delivery, and perceived pricing have a positive relationship with online customer satisfaction. Moreover, delivery quality was the most critical factor, followed by product quality. According to the data gathered for this study, e-commerce businesses should focus more on product

sourcing and work with the delivery provider to ensure better delivery quality, which includes accurate orders, on-time deliveries, and secure packaging. Previous studies have demonstrated that culture significantly influences customers' behaviours. Subsequent investigations should replicate this analysis and evaluate this theoretical framework across different nations or societies.

Hilaludin and Cheng (2014): This study mainly aimed to identify factors influencing customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction also influences the e-loyalty of youth towards online shopping. Results showed that only the quality of e-services and information influenced customer satisfaction.

Saxena (2017) reviewed existing research and conceptualised the matrix. The study focused on three customer satisfaction strategies: loyalty, the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction, and price tolerance. The author talks about the potential benefits of innovation and how it can boost customer satisfaction. To summarise, the author believes that a company must satisfy its customers. Customers are the company's most important asset. Measuring customer satisfaction statistically is crucial for organisations to effectively manage their performances. Profit is vital, but growth and profit depend entirely on satisfied customers for a long time. The company ought to concentrate on using innovations to create more value.

According to the Lee & Baker (2017) case study, service companies have made considerable efforts to understand, use, and manage technologies to increase customer satisfaction in the hospitality and tourism industries. However, industry and academia still need to address problems and possibilities to advance the hospitality and tourism fields' knowledge of the consequences of using technology to serve customers.

Farooqui and Alwi (2019) surveyed fast food in Pakistan. This study highlighted the trend of fast-food customer satisfaction based on variables such as service quality, price, ambiance, and food quality. Ambiance, price, and food quality positively affect customer satisfaction.

Olumayowa (2019) investigated the impact of digital banking's speed and adaptability on customer satisfaction in Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory. Customers' behaviours continuously change; therefore, there is an increasing urge for innovative digital technologies and new ways of using financial services. Banks must adopt novel digitalisation without further delays in light of competition in a digital economy. "Digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and provide new revenue and value-producing opportunities. It is the process of moving to a digital business (Dang & Kaur, 2016)". To maintain a strategic edge in the digital landscape, the bank must be able to create new digital channels and products, upgrade its technological infrastructure, and make significant organisational adjustments. Their primary goal is to gratify their customers by enhancing transaction speeds and streamlining the adaptability process. Any organisation that begins this process will be in a better position to meet the evolving needs of its customers.

In this respect, Rahman Zanzeh (2020) conducted a systematic literature review to assess the effects of person-centered healthcare quality determinants on patient satisfaction and responsiveness. The results showed that institutional characteristics like administration, doctor-patient contact, staff attitudes, and hospital environments such as privacy, convenience, and cleanliness influenced the patient's satisfaction level. Additionally, the quality factor increased patient satisfaction. The study discovered that quality factors like responsiveness, reliability, assurance, tangibles, and empathy boost patient satisfaction. There were drawbacks to using only secondary data, such as the inability to thoroughly examine the dimensions of quality service in the healthcare industry. Only a few of the assessed studies reviewed all aspects of quality service. The study suggests that future studies should collect and analyse primary data using quantitative or qualitative research methods. These methodologies enable researchers to investigate all aspects of healthcare service quality.

Ejdys & Gulc (2020) deeply analysed the dimensions of ease of use, perceived usefulness, and level of trust, all of which play a critical role in shaping customers' perceptions of the quality of courier services. Technological advancement and personal interaction are strongly linked to trust. Trust then becomes a key driver of the perceived quality of the service provided, as well as the intention of customers to use the service again shortly. Business Implications: The study shows that improving the technological solution at courier services can result in much higher levels of trust among customers, an increase in the overall quality of the service, and, ultimately, a rise in customer loyalty toward the brand.

Al Awadhi et al., (2021) surveyed UAE-based telecom customers. This study examines the various relationships between perceived expectations and customer satisfaction associated with digital solutions in the UAE telecommunications industry. Its findings have proved that when the people of the UAE are using or accessing any digital solution regarding the telecommunications industry, they have a significant association between their expectations, experiences, and satisfaction levels. The research identified another area for improvement in the digital age: increasing efficacy and efficiency. Furthermore, they recommended that businesses use digital platforms more frequently to reach ROI goals and improve efficiency.

Zouari and Abdelhedi (2021) surveyed Tunisian Islamic Banking customers to investigate how digitalisation affects customer satisfaction as a service quality dimension. This investigation used the extended SERVQUAL model. Factor analysis identified five dimensions of service quality: confidence, compliance, digitalisation, tangibles, and human skills. The study finds a positive and strong correlation between service quality and customer satisfaction, except for tangibles. Above all, the study suggested that digitalisation is a crucial factor in determining service quality and general customer satisfaction among today's digital consumers. Islamic banks must focus their service quality on potential customers who will increasingly rely on digital means in the future. Furthermore, it is critical to conduct more research on the impact of digitalisation on service quality and customer satisfaction, particularly in the context of Islamic banks versus conventional ones.

Sesar et al., (2021) reviewed the literature to examine how digitalisation affects customer loyalty and satisfaction during the coronavirus outbreak and summarised the literature on research in these domains. The study's findings recommend conducting additional research on the impacts of digitalisation on customer loyalty and satisfaction. Each research paper insisted that digitisation influences business processes and, above all, the way organisations work. This alters companies' performance and emphasises the need to improve their current capabilities to drive digital transformation. Further studies are necessary, considering the correlation between digitalisation and customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Kidwai and Maqbool (2022) discuss how digital technologies contribute to the development of courier services. In this context, innovations such as RFID tracking, automated systems, and paperless billing contribute to improving efficiency and customer satisfaction. E-commerce has increased the demand for speed, reliability, and service efficiency. In this regard, multimodal transportation supported by digital tools is the key factor for competitiveness. This paper also insists that employee satisfaction is the basis for receiving qualitative services from courier companies.

According to Mohyudin (2022), adopting digital technologies, data analytics, and other digital platforms has a pivotal effect on improving customer satisfaction in Pakistan's textile industry. Due to the incorporation of advanced technologies into business processes, companies in the textile industry can show much better efficiency and produce quality merchandise. Additionally, they can provide experiences that correspond to customers' individual needs and preferences. This study concludes that, from a strategic perspective, the utilisation of digital tools is advantageous and a crucial element in enhancing customer satisfaction levels and maintaining business competitiveness in the dynamic and ever-changing global market.

Irshad et al., (2022) used the Food Panda brand image to study the impacts of service quality and social media marketing on customer satisfaction. They also tested whether the price could moderate the relationship between customer satisfaction and brand image. The findings indicate that the service quality and social media marketing variables have higher impacts on customer satisfaction, while the price has no moderate influence. More studies can use food apps as an independent variable in establishing their effects on customer satisfaction and brand image.

In their research study, Abdel-Hamid et al., (2022) critically look at how sophisticated digital technologies, such as AI chatbots, experiences in virtual reality, and novel mobile apps, help elevate customer satisfaction levels among hotel guests in Egypt. The results of this broad study indicate that while several hotels have embraced some of these modern technologies, there is still a significant gap because many have yet to implement higher-end technologies like automated robots and self-service kiosks that will improve operations and guest service further. The study concludes that fully adopting digital technologies into hotel operations would significantly improve the guest experience, smooth processes more seamlessly, and increase overall satisfaction. This report calls for more

authorities to focus on the digital transformation process in the hotel sector.

Demirel (2022) conducted his research in Kocaeli, Turkey, via an online survey to understand how digital services can facilitate customer relationship management (CRM) by adopting customer-orientated management systems. This paper also examined the relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality through its research. These findings confirm that the most critical aspects influencing digital service quality support customer satisfaction. We found positive associations between the independent variables and trust, enthusiasm, sensitivity, and customer satisfaction. The research revealed that digital technologies enable businesses to provide better customer service. This study significantly extends the use of structural equation modelling to examine service quality and technological advancements in customer satisfaction. Effective digitalisation provides the company with definite, beneficial, and long-term advantages. Every digital advancement that enhances the customer experience will create new opportunities for the company. In other words, service quality facets have a very high level of correlation with each other, and the essential independent variables causing customer delight are trust and enthusiasm. While success is important, service quality may not be enough on its own.

In adopting a holistic perspective in managing customers' satisfaction and digitalisation, Eckert et al., (2022) considered the insurance industry. The results indicate a positive impact on a customer's perception of service quality and perceived value in relation to customer satisfaction within the insurance industry. There is limited academic research on customer satisfaction in insurance firms. Its primary focus is on the potential created by digitalisation. This study offers a comprehensive overview of how digital apps can enhance customer satisfaction. We should conduct more empirical studies to determine whether frequent use of digital applications by insurance businesses increases customer satisfaction.

Martínez de Miguel et al., (2022) surveyed customers in the automotive business to establish the impact of digital transformation on customer satisfaction. Many firms have realised that changing business models and structures to improve customer satisfaction is necessary because of the various ways technology has affected organisations. Few studies have looked at customer satisfaction in the context of digital transformation, and even fewer have looked at customers' satisfaction with dynamic capacities in the automobile industry. Additionally, five suggested metrics for assessing customer satisfaction in the context of digital transformation were deemed appropriate. Researchers have established a quantitative relationship between dynamic capabilities and their impact on customer satisfaction.

Alasadee and Alfatlawi 2023 studied the impact of digital technologies on customer satisfaction at Amin Al-Iraq Islamic Bank, Iraq. This study proved that digital technologies have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. They gave some recommendations to increase the customer satisfaction ratio and attract new customers. Banks must promote their products and services through social media and digital advertisement. To enhance their reliability and financial performance, they must prioritise modern information technology.

Loh et al., (2023) evaluated the influence of digitalisation on customer satisfaction among Singapore-based shipping customers. The introduction of digital platforms has dramatically changed the business models of shipping companies, which are moving away from conventional operating procedures and towards customer-focused digital solutions. These solutions allow shipping companies to offer their customers increased efficiency and convenience through real-time tracking and shipment control. The findings also indicate that the customer's ease of use on the digital platform is crucial, as it can significantly improve and influence much greater customer acceptance and engagement. Additionally, user-friendliness has the potential to increase customer satisfaction. We can make the platforms' interface more user-friendly by keeping it straightforward and intuitive, making it simple to use, incorporating a feedback system, enabling customisable features, guaranteeing accessibility and responsiveness, etc.

Sobaih & AlSaif (2023) investigated the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction within Saudi Arabia's logistics industry. Using the SERVQUAL model, which is well known and used in the service industry, the authors found that reliability, empathy, tangibility, and responsiveness are some of the most important factors that make customers happy. Customers found these to have a profoundly positive effect on their overall satisfaction, with reliability being the most significant factor. Further, it emphasises a cultural difference between Saudi and non-Saudi customers—the former is more satisfied. Language mastery or cultural knowledge may explain this. As a result, the study emphasises and stresses that detailed attention to these various dimensions of service quality is critical for effective improvements and customer satisfaction.

Shah et al., (2023) have conducted an in-depth analysis of how various factors, such as digital capabilities, organisational orientation, and digital transformation, decisively influence the performance of SMEs in Pakistan. Their analysis identified digital innovation as a significant mediating factor influencing these relationships. The authors stressed how important it is for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) to quickly adopt new digital technologies, retrain their employees, and create a digital mindset within their businesses to become more competitive in the market and help the digital economy grow. The authors further state that continuous innovation has become crucial for determining financial and operational performance in a rapidly evolving environment.

According to Hussain et al., (2023), digital banking innovation is vital for enhancing and developing customer satisfaction levels, especially as far as studying Roshan Digital Account, a case study for Pakistan, is concerned. Subsequently, the researchers conducted a detailed study on the impact and influence of four fundamental variables, specifically the quality of the service provided. The study focused on the soundness of the system's security, the user's acceptance of technology, and the overall convenience factor that customers consider when establishing customer relationships and satisfaction. This extensive study shows that factors such as service quality, system security, and convenience make vital contributions toward higher levels of customer satisfaction

in digital banking.

However, we found that customer satisfaction levels with technology acceptance were relatively high. Predictably, this is due to the intrinsic complexity surrounding the nature of digital banking technologies and the low general levels of financial literacy that most users possess. The survey highlights the importance of reliable service quality, adequate security, and ease of access as crucial factors that contribute to overall customer satisfaction. The paper also suggests areas of development, including recommendations for customer support services, ensuring greater security features, and developing more user-friendly technologies to enhance user adoption. Finally, the paper concludes with thoughtful suggestions to guide future research efforts and recommendations for improvements in the industry that provides digital banking services.

Luan-Thanh 2024 surveyed "Factors Affecting the Adoption of Mobile Commerce in Ho Chi Minh City in Terms of Customer Satisfaction and Service Quality." The factors that affect service quality and customers' purchases using M-commerce services are reliability, responsiveness, content, accessibility, expectations, and satisfaction.

Lohano et al., (2024) present the results of a detailed survey of the private banking sector in Hyderabad, Pakistan, where they carefully scrutinised and analysed various aspects of the influence of digital banking services on financial performance. Customer experience is a critical aspect of the investigation. The elaborated study explored how increasingly important digital platforms would transform banking services toward improving overall customer satisfaction, which is conducive to banks driving positive financial outcomes. The research highlights how digital technologies are changing the traditional pattern of banking. Research investigated the transformation in the context of several dimensions of digital banking, such as online transactions, mobile banking applications, and new customer service tools that enhance user experiences.

These findings demonstrate that digital banking services improve the overall customer experience, as they are more convenient, quicker, and precisely tailored to individual needs. Another positive outcome of these changes is the enhancement of financial performance in banks because they manage to be successful under challenging conditions. However, the study highlights several barriers to the adoption of digital solutions, including the varying maturity levels of banks and their customers, which could potentially diminish the efficacy of these innovations. It concludes with recommendations for further inclusion of digital solutions to improve customer satisfaction and financial outcomes, as well as pointing out that innovation in digital banking technologies is ongoing.

Ashfaq et al., (2024) investigate how businesses can achieve financial performance optimally by considering the strategies of digitalisation and servitisation. Digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to streamline activities, whereas servitisation is the shift from a product-based orientation to a service orientation. The empirical analysis of the research study reveals that companies combining both strategies demonstrate superior financial results, operational efficiency, and customer satisfaction. In the end, the paper comes to the conclusion that digital

innovations and the provision of innovation services are still essential for businesses to stay ahead in the market. These measures will also help organisations maintain sustainable financial growth.

As a result, businesses have discovered that a satisfied customer base can result in customer retention, loyalty, brand image, a competitive advantage, business growth, profitability, and global expansion. Customer satisfaction was initially examined to investigate the consequences of the phenomenon in businesses. Previous studies have illuminated various factors that impact customer satisfaction, such as customer expectations, perceived value, emotional considerations, price, after-sales service, and service quality. Service quality was a factor mainly studied in terms of customer satisfaction. Sureshchandar et al., (2002) suggest that the precise nature of this relationship is still unknown. The results suggest that, although the two variables are independent, they are closely related, meaning that a rise in one would likely lead to a rise in the other. The study recommended an investigation of the associations between service quality and customer satisfaction in sectors other than banking services.

Even though service quality significantly influences customer satisfaction, recent studies have identified that information technology, digital technologies, and innovation are other factors affecting it. Lin et al., (2011) found a positive relationship between online customer satisfaction and information, system, service, product, delivery, and perceived pricing. Hilaludin and Cheng (2014) determined that the quality of e-services and information would influence customer satisfaction. Saxena (2017) recommended that companies focus more on innovation to create value. Olumayowa (2019) discovered an increased demand for innovative digital technologies and new ways of using financial services. It is a fact that any organisation that undertakes this process will be better positioned to meet the evolving needs of its customers. Above all, this study suggests that digitalisation is a fundamental factor in determining service quality and general customer satisfaction among today's digital customers. Sesar et al., (2021) recommended further studies that needed to be conducted on the nature and impact of digitalisation on customer loyalty and satisfaction. Irshad et al., (2022) identified that future studies might investigate the ease of use of food apps as an independent variable that may influence customers' satisfaction and brand image. Martínez de Miguel et al., (2022) asserted that there have been a limited number of studies dealing with customer satisfaction in the digital transformation of businesses.

2.2.1. Summary of Prior Research

A review of the existing literature indicates that while a significant amount of work has been carried out to understand customer satisfaction in the context of various industries (Sureshchandar et al., 2002; Farooqui & Alwi, 2019; Al Awadhi et al., 2021), there is still a gap in the extant literature regarding the exact role played by digital technologies in influencing customer satisfaction within the courier industry in Pakistan. Lee & Baker (2017) and Demirel (2022) support the notion that most existing literature has concentrated on the more significant service sectors, neglecting to consider the unique dynamics of digital technologies in courier and logistics. There is also limited research on the mediating roles of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in developing customer

satisfaction with digital technologies, as documented by Irshad et al., (2022) and Alasadee & Alfatlawi (2023). Addressing these gaps through comprehensive empirical research will advance academic knowledge and provide helpful tips for improving customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry.

2.3. Importance of Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a critical determinant of a company's success, influencing various aspects of business performance, including customer loyalty, retention, and profitability. Numerous scholars have emphasised that satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal, engage in repeat purchases, and recommend the company to others, thereby acting as brand ambassadors and contributing to a positive WOM (Singh, 2006; Hoyer & MacInnis, 2001; Tien et al., 2021). This long-term customer satisfaction relationship is the foundation for long-term business success.

The significance of customer satisfaction extends beyond immediate customer interactions; it has a direct impact on a company's financial performance and public image. Khadka and Maharjan (2017) argue that customer satisfaction is vital to maintaining company profitability, as it encourages continued patronage and can lead to increased revenue. Similarly, Drucker (1973) and later researchers pointed out that customer satisfaction provides the basis for business success. Therefore, extensive literature (Novikova, 2009; Angelova and Zekiri, 2011; Jashireh et al., 2016) has documented its influence on the profitability and survival of businesses. With increased customer satisfaction, the possibility of retention in the company increases, and such an outcome continues to bring profitability and a better competitive advantage in the market. This results in consistent profitability and a more robust market position.

In light of growing public expectations regarding service quality, customer satisfaction has become even more important. Gerson (1993) asserts that this trend has led quality professionals to prioritize customer satisfaction, as meeting and exceeding customer expectations can provide a competitive advantage. Fornell (1994) further supports this position, asserting that a higher level of customer satisfaction directly correlates with enhanced revenue growth and financial stability. This perspective emphasises the importance of treating customers as valuable assets to maintain the company's financial balance.

Traditionally conceptualised as one-dimensional, customer satisfaction has increasingly become multi-dimensional, enabling precise and specific measurements. The majority of early studies on satisfaction measured it using general assessments of overall experience or general feelings about customer experience (Aminuddin et al., 2020). The multidimensional nature of customer satisfaction has been depicted in studies, and different dimensions influence the overall evaluation (Chen and Tsai, 2008; El-Adly & Ismail, 2019). Giese and Cote (2000) identify three core components of customer satisfaction: a response to a specific focus occurring at a particular time and cognitive or emotional judgements based on evaluating performance against expectations.

The diversity in defining and measuring customer satisfaction also demonstrates its complexity as a construct. Fornell's (1992) perspective, which compares post-purchase perceptions with pre-purchase expectations, serves as the basis for measuring customer satisfaction in this study. This definition aligns with the study's focus on understanding how digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency influence customer satisfaction in the context of Pakistan's courier industry.

In conclusion, we cannot overstate the importance of customer satisfaction, as it directly influences customer loyalty, profitability, and a company's competitive standing. The evolution of customer satisfaction from a one-dimensional concept to a multifaceted construct suggests that there are more nuanced approaches in measurement and management, particularly in today's rapidly changing business environment.

2.3.1. Importance of Customer Satisfaction in Courier Industry

Customer satisfaction is crucial to the courier industry in that it assures the company of customer loyalty and retention, hence the survival of that company (Loo & Asrah, 2022; Wei, 2024; Ponnusamy & Ramasamy, 2024). A satisfied customer at a courier company is most likely to make repeated purchases and refer the company to other customers. Loyalty becomes a significant factor in maintaining business growth and sustaining competitive advantage in the marketplace (Hoyer & MacInnis, 2001). In the recent past, this has been increasingly so because the customers, through competitive markets, have been presented with different alternatives to get their service from several service providers (Yaacob & Yaacob, 2022).

The courier service's nature entails timely deliveries, accuracy, and proper communication. In such a case, when any flaw occurs, there is every tendency for dissatisfied customers, damaging the reputation and future business of the company concerned (Cvetić et al., 2024). Satisfied customers are better positioned to return for more and recommend the services to others, which helps with word-of-mouth publicity and ensures long-term business (Kidwai & Maqbool, 2023). Customers' satisfaction levels significantly influence an organisation's brand image and reputation. Satisfied customers are more likely to talk about the company's excellent services, increasing its reputation and market value (Zeithaml et al., 2009).

In addition, customer expectations are increasingly high with the development of digital technologies like real-time tracking and automated customer service tools (Rane, 2023). Therefore, exceeding these expectations will help companies be more competitive. In the courier industry, customer satisfaction is a measure of service performance and a key driver of brand loyalty, customer retention, and profitability (Noor-ul-Ain et al., 2022; Tijjang et al., 2023; Lisnawati et al., 2024). Improved customer satisfaction can generate a high ROI by creating customer loyalty and reducing the costs of attracting new customers. Consequently, product or service price fluctuations will not affect satisfied customers, and companies will be able to maintain or even increase their current pricing strategies (Fornell, 1992).

2.4. Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction has traditionally been one of the main areas of investigation, especially in the service industry, because it greatly relates to organisational change and overall performance. Many scholars have studied the multifaceted nature of customer satisfaction, which is shown through various ideas about how it is achieved and the factors that affect it. Much of this research consensus indicates that customer satisfaction is not just a positive outcome but, relatively, one of the critical drivers of customer loyalty, repeat business, and long-term profitability.

According to Potluri (2010), an organisation can only achieve customer satisfaction if it deliberately changes its attitudes and service delivery practices. From this perspective, we should treat customer satisfaction as a purposeful objective that requires strategic consideration and focused endeavours rather than as a fortunate consequence of excellent service alone. From a similar perspective, Rita et al., (2019) also suggest that customer satisfaction is vital for customer retention and encourages more consumption of services, hence essential for any venture's sustainability. Potluri (2010) identifies five critical factors that drive customer satisfaction: reliability, quality, accessibility, price, and availability, all of which require careful management to ensure customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Customer satisfaction may vary and change because it is a dynamic and subjective idea. According to Zeithaml et al., (2009), firms need to consider the various dimensions of customer satisfaction, such as the quality of the product or service, customer feelings and emotions, prices, brand image, and the total cost of the product or service. Each of these can tremendously affect a customer's perception of satisfaction. Quality is usually one of the foundational sources of satisfaction since customers expect to feel positive about the products or services they receive. Emotions are also important because positive emotional moments may enhance customer satisfaction, while negative emotions weaken satisfaction. Meanwhile, pricing is critical to customer satisfaction because it relates to the perceived value of the customer against the cost.

In addition, customer satisfaction influences buyers' behaviours. For example, satisfied customers are more likely to respond with positive behaviours, such as loyalty, reduced price sensitivity, and WOM promotion (Oliver, 1997). Understanding the factors that drive customer satisfaction is critical to effectively pursuing these positive outcomes.

Customer expectations are central to defining satisfaction. Satisfaction occurs when service delivery meets and exceeds these expectations, and dissatisfaction arises when it fails to meet those (Masorgo et al., 2022). Various factors influence these expectations, including previous experiences with the service, word-of-mouth recommendations from friends and family, and advertisements (Rane et al., 2023). In a study, Zeithaml et al., (2009) have quoted those customers always buy something with an anticipation level, and the satisfaction of customers is derived from how well the actual service they get fits the preconceived level. In the context of courier services, customers anticipate timely delivery of their packages, appropriate tracking, and professional handling (Kolasińska-Morawska et al., 2022). Customers will be satisfied and form a positive impression of the company if it meets or exceeds these expectations (Vrhovac et al., 2023). Customers' perceptions of the core service they receive inherently determine perceived value, another crucial factor (Paulose & Shakeel, 2021; Solakis et al., 2022).

Perceived value, a crucial factor, stems from customers' perceptions of the core service they receive (Paulose & Shakeel, 2021; Solakis et al., 2022). According to Zeithaml (1988), a customer perceives perceived value when they perceive the benefits from the service to be equal to or even greater than their costs. In the courier industry, perceived value refers to a guarantee of dependable and effective service for the cost of delivery (Jalagat & Aquino, 2021; Akram et al., 2022). If customers feel they are getting a high-quality service at a reasonable or competitive price, their satisfaction levels will increase. If it is too expensive for the quality provided, there is a likelihood that dissatisfaction will rise, probably leading to negative reviews or loss of business (Dlai et al., 2014; Ahmed et al., 2023). Another element that may contribute significantly to customer satisfaction is the emotional experience of the service (Carmo et al., 2022). Emotions are an essential touch between the process of satisfaction and experience, according to Bitner et al., (1992), because contentment, delight, or even annoyance created by an experience may influence customers' judgements about overall service. While unexpectedly excellent service may cause delight or pleasure, delays or service failures would elicit frustrated or annoyed feelings (Masorgo et al., 2023). In service industries, like courier services, the emotional experience resulting from such interactions plays a leading role in customer retention. Consider a courier company that consistently strives to ensure customer satisfaction. An issue with a late delivery, followed by either a prompt package delivery or excellent customer service, creates positive feelings that often offset a previous negative experience and lead to overall satisfaction (Riaz et al., 2022).

Price is another critical factor in determining customer satisfaction, reflecting sensitivity to changes in service

costs (Talapatra et al., 2021). Pricing has a direct impact on customers' behaviour, perceived value, and equity. According to Zeithaml (1988), price fairness, or the perceived appropriateness of the amount charged relative to the service received affects customer satisfaction. Customers are generally satisfied when they think the price they pay for a service is fair for the quality (Pei et al., 2020). Alternatively, high-quality service may not satisfy customers if they believe prices are too high or unjustified. Moreover, customers strongly correlate competitive pricing, meaning at least equal to or better than competitors, with high levels of satisfaction, as they are satisfied with the service and a satisfactory deal (Inderst & Obradovits, 2023). In industries that are very competitive in price, such as the courier industry, maintaining reasonable pricing strategies while offering excellent service will raise customer loyalty and satisfaction significantly (Heim & Sinha, 2001; Mohamad et al., 2022).

The key factors significantly contributing to customer satisfaction are particularly critical in service-orientated industries like courier services, where timely and reliable delivery is paramount to maintaining customer confidence and loyalty (Akhter et al., 2024). In these industries, service quality is the most important determinant of customer satisfaction (Akil & Ungan, 2022). High service quality meets but often exceeds customer expectations by making a big difference in the customers' perception of the service they receive. According to Parasuraman et al., (1988), service quality can be contextualised around five key dimensions: reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responsiveness. Reliability concerns the consistent and accurate performance of services, while assurance instills trust and confidence in customers. Tangibility refers to the physical dimensions of service that influence customers' perceptions, such as the condition of delivery vehicles and packaging. Empathy involves demonstrating care and individual attention to the clients, while responsiveness pertains to the prompt handling of customer queries and problems. When applied appropriately, these factors mean customers are more satisfied with the service. They will also provide positive comments, recommend the service to friends, and come back for more purchases.

Service quality is critical for understanding and improving customer satisfaction; this is especially true when industries have intangible products that customers may not own physically but can only experience. Regarding the non-physical nature of services, Lemon & Verhoef (2016) observe that the customer's perception of quality matters. Customers often assess satisfaction relative to the overall service experience and the quality of their contact with the service provider. Peeler (1996) claims that quality perception is a crucial competitive business force. Quality perception has an impact on customers' buying habits and is of utmost importance to a company that wants to maintain a competitive edge. According to Parasuraman et al., (1988), service quality is the deadliest competitive weapon, while Clow (1993) considers service quality a vital component of an organisation. Quality services attract and retain customers by meeting or exceeding their expectations. Throughout the 20th century, researchers and practitioners have consistently strived to improve service quality.

Improvements in service quality remain crucial, not only for enhancing levels of organisational performance but

also for increasing customer satisfaction while ensuring global competitiveness (Ali et al., 2016; Fotaki, 2015). By focussing their efforts on the delivery of higher-quality services, an organisation can significantly enhance its capability in not only sustaining customer satisfaction over time but also realising superior financial performance outcomes in developing a solid reputation in their markets (Nguyen & Leblanc, 1998). Meeting customer expectations is at the heart of service quality, which is the primary factor in loyalty and positive WOM (Khristianto et al., 2012).

Recent academic studies have focused more on identifying and understanding the direct relationship between the quality of the services offered and the level of satisfaction the customers enjoy. Uddin and Akhter (2012) argue that a company's success in efficiently satisfying its customers depends on the quality and excellence of the services offered. This is further reaffirmed by Ali et al., (2021), as they raise the vital aspect that the quality of the service directly impacts customer satisfaction. The specific relationship between these two variables of interest is well-annotated and highly researched, demonstrating that a higher degree of perceived service quality leads to an increase in customer satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Esmailpour et al., 2022).

Many authors have described service quality as a multidimensional and complex concept predominantly determined by customer expectations (Berry et al., 1988). The constructs involved in this concept are reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles—all very significant in providing a customer with an overall experience (Mosahab et al., 2010). When customers receive service at par or according to their expected level in these crucial dimensions, it enhances their overall satisfaction, making effective and comprehensive service management practices highly important.

The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction is direct and bidirectional. Sureshchandar et al., (2002) demonstrated in their study that when the quality of service is superior, it automatically contributes to a significant rise in customer satisfaction. Customers who are satisfied with the services offered prefer to imagine that the service quality is higher than expected. This self-reinforcing relationship highlights the importance of always providing superior services to maintain or improve customer satisfaction over time.

Furthermore, the relationship between customer satisfaction and expected service levels is a direct measurement that assesses the overall performance of any organisation. Customer satisfaction with the quality of service enables businesses to understand how effectively customer needs are met through crucial analysis and investigation of customer satisfaction with the quality of service provided (Gupta & Jain, 2004). The detailed study will not only enable them to identify gaps in the delivery of services but also point out those areas that need improvement for better results in customer satisfaction.

Although customer satisfaction and service quality are distinct concepts in their definition and application, they have an inseparable connection. There is considerable consensus among most researchers in this field,

purportedly establishing that these two variables are positively and highly correlated (Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Anderson & Sullivan, 1993; Kiran & Diljit, 2017). For instance, with an increase in service quality, not only is there a greater level of customer satisfaction, but there is also a subsequent development of loyalty, which will ultimately result in the long-term success of businesses.

Service quality in the constantly changing face of the digital era has expanded significantly to include both conventional and other forms of online interaction. Digital service quality has become a matter of prime importance, and the convenience of websites and super-efficient customer support mechanisms are crucial for the continuance and uptrend in customer satisfaction (Lin & Lee, 2006). As organisations gradually shift their services to the virtual world, ensuring that digital service quality matches or exceeds established standards for traditional service experiences has become essential.

Digital technologies have emerged as a vital and critical focus of service research due to their immense and transformative potential in improving customer experiences and overall satisfaction. Ostrom et al., (2015) make the persuasive case that technology is one of the three most significant areas for service research in today's increasingly digital environment. Digital technologies allow customisation, service recovery, and improvements to the customer experience, leading to greater satisfaction (Melián-González & Bulchand-Gidumal, 2016). Adopting digital technologies has considerable potential to substantially enhance organisations, resulting in notable improvements in customer satisfaction and retention rates. For example, Makarem et al., (2009) reported in a study that there is a positive relation between customer satisfaction levels and factors like service convenience, technological touchpoints, and the effectiveness of the results. Multiple researches work, such as Parida et al., 2019 and Sesar et al., 2021, further highlight this relationship by pointing out that digital transformation and the adoption of new technologies encouraged corporate innovation and simultaneously improved customer satisfaction metrics.

The significant rise of digital goods and services recently has provided companies with the opportunity to respond more flexibly and adaptively to the ever-changing demands of their customers, leading to notable alterations in their business models and operational procedures (Almeida et al., 2020; Reis et al., 2019). Furthermore, digitalisation has greatly reduced the physical barriers that used to make access difficult. This means that customers can now buy things online and use services from almost anywhere, which has changed their expectations and how they interact with businesses (Cobelli & Chiarini, 2020). Businesses must now focus on providing a positive digital experience, as customer expectations increasingly revolve around personalised and efficient service delivery (Kumar, 2014; Rauch, 2014).

The availability and ease of using many digital solutions in the market today greatly increased customer interaction and exposure to a wider range of products and services. Digital technology has then made it possible for higher transaction levels that don't require personal interaction or direct face-to-face contact with any service

representative (Meuter et al., 2000). Such a trend for change towards adopting self-service solutions, primarily felt through the pace and ease provided by state-of-the-art digital technologies, has dramatically reshaped and defined the face of customer service delivery in ways previously not thought possible (Vasya & Patrick, 2006). As a result, technology-driven customer satisfaction initiatives are becoming essential, particularly as emerging digital banks challenge traditional banking models by focussing on younger, tech-savvy customers (Geissinger et al., 2020).

The powerful combination of high service quality with substantial digital efficiency raises the general level of customer satisfaction and is vital in driving high business profitability. For instance, highly satisfied customers are likelier to become repeat buyers who return for more purchases and actively promote the company through positive WOM referrals to friends and family. They are also more likely to be loyal even when competitive markets offer them more lucrative options (McColl-Kennedy, 2003). Customer satisfaction plays a crucial role in retaining customers and achieving long-term profitability. A business that successfully combines high service quality with advanced digital technologies is uniquely positioned to achieve the ultimate goal of sustainable growth in today's dynamic market environment (Rita et al., 2019).

In summary, it has become clear that integrating high-service quality and sophisticated digital technologies is no longer a discretionary option for enterprises; it has become necessary for companies seeking to impact customer satisfaction positively in a competitive marketplace. Driving competencies, service quality's broader advantages, and technological strides have enabled businesses to create magic in memorable experiences and exceed the evolving needs and expectations of today's savvy customers.

Such a strategic drive ensures customer satisfaction; more importantly, it creates a sense of loyalty and commitment that may open prospects for sustainability in business over the long term (Ostrom et al., 2015). In any case, ensuring customer satisfaction in the future requires the seamless integration of high-quality service with the latest technological advancements in continuously changing digital technologies. Therefore, digital technologies and the quality of service provided are two major interrelated factors that substantially affect customer satisfaction levels. The study has thus outlined the two most important factors in determining customer satisfaction and, consequently, the success of businesses in today's changing environment.

2.5. Digital Technologies and Customer Satisfaction

In the modern world, digital technologies have gradually transformed into an influential force that has revolutionised entire industries and impacted how businesses conduct their activities. This transformation is particularly important because it enhances customer satisfaction levels by reshaping both businesses and their interactions with customers. As Westerman et al., (2014) indicated, this is a moment in history when the full potential of those advanced technologies is now being realised, allowing companies to do things that previously

were unimaginable or out of reach, pushing the boundaries of possibility in business. Business firms can enhance their customers' experiences by using digital technologies to manage and analyse data and facilitate informed decision-making in real time. Indeed, data analysis would be an indispensable part of decision-making for achieving and maintaining high levels of customer satisfaction, which would ensure overall success and organisation's reputation in the marketplace (Lanzolla & Anderson, 2008).

Within the B2C supply chain context, and especially for industries like courier services, digitalisation has moved beyond just a technological upgrade; it has become a strategic imperative necessary for businesses to survive. Digitalisation involves the comprehensive integration of various digital technologies into every aspect of business operation, fundamentally transforming how companies conduct their activities and generate value for customers in an increasingly competitive environment. This shift is critical for placing customers at the heart of business processes, enhancing service quality, streamlining operations, and delivering personalised experiences that directly boost customer satisfaction (Boulton, 2021; Beniff, 2022; and Google Cloud, 2022).

In today's rapidly technologically moulded environment, customers have mastered the realm of digital landscapes and have thus developed very high expectations in terms of efficiency, convenience, and various options when interacting with their businesses. Therefore, businesses have found it increasingly necessary to evolve through digital solutions that not only meet the growing expectations of these customers but also improve the process of value co-creation with them (Lee & Lee, 2020). Furthermore, innovative digital technologies create avenues for enterprises to offer services that are increasingly personalised and responsive, thus linking back to the core drivers of overall customer satisfaction (Rosete et al., 2020). The ability to promptly deliver information to customers, provide transaction services with convenience, and offer customer support services tailored to their needs via various channels significantly adds to and enhances the customer's overall experience when dealing with a company (Parviainen et al., 2017).

However, despite the substantial benefits digitalisation can offer in terms of customer satisfaction, there are several significant challenges, such as infrastructure limitations, high implementation costs, lack of skilled professionals, resistance to change, cybersecurity risks, regulatory and compliance issues, and interoperability and integration issues that must be overcome (Kallmuenzer, et al., 2024; Vărzaru & Bocean 2024). To align their digital efforts with the overall goal of creating customer value, many businesses require assistance. These specific challenges often arise from a lack of distinct focus on objectives, poor integration and cooperation between business groups and IT departments, and too few management approaches when it comes to dealing with changes in operational processes within an organisational context (Mahmoud et al., 2018; Boulton, 2021). Business leaders must be involved and deeply engaged in the entire process of digitalisation initiatives in order to have a positive and beneficial effect on overall customer satisfaction.

The engagement will include a critical aspect of the seamless integration of information technology systems into

the overall framework of the overarching business strategy (Seyedghorban et al., 2020). Moreover, businesses must emphasise achieving operational efficiency and effectiveness as a primary objective. The initiative would help them use and leverage all sorts of advantages that digital technology offers. This strategic focus will drastically improve customer satisfaction, enhance revenue, streams, and automate many processes. Such advancements contribute to greater cost-effectiveness, benefiting the organisation (Von Leipzig et al., 2017).

As they exist and function within the dynamic digital environment, businesses must identify ways to retain their customer base and ensure high satisfaction levels. Additionally, this requires both awareness and understanding of emerging digital trends that influence customer behaviour, as well as conducting market analyses to identify their current needs and future potential. Moreover, business enterprises will ensure they have the full capability for continuous product and service adaptation with precision to meet changing customer needs and expectations. When companies align their overall customer experience with ongoing digital transformation, they can enhance their ability to fulfil demands effectively. All these lead to increased customer satisfaction, which is crucial for ensuring the long-term success of an organisation in a contemporary competitive environment (IBM, 2022).

2.5.1. Digital Technologies Role in Courier Customer Satisfaction

Digital technologies have become indispensable and essential in significantly boosting customer satisfaction in the ever-evolving courier and logistics industries in the last couple of years (Nagy et al., 2023; Manjunadh & Manoj, 2024; Kraugusteeliana & Violin, 2024). These innovative technologies thus enable companies to substantially enhance their service delivery processes by bringing about more efficiency, accuracy, and responsiveness (Kafi et al., 2022). Such improvements are critical for meeting and exceeding customer expectations in today's fast-paced, highly competitive market environment, where customer demands constantly surge to change (Mathauer and Hofmann, 2019; Remondino & Zanin, 2022).

2.5.1.1. Real-Time Tracking and the Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things, commonly called IoT, “The Internet of Things describes devices with sensors, processing ability, software and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the Internet or other communication networks. IoT devices do not have to be connected directly to the public Internet; they simply need to be networked and individually address (Shafiq et al., 2022)”. IoT is undoubtedly one of the most critical developments in digital technologies, especially for the courier industry. The IoT allows tracking shipments in real-time, enabling customers to track the progress of their deliveries at every stage of the entire process (Mohamud et al., 2023; DHL, 2022; Forbes, 2020). Customers typically evaluate the overall effectiveness of a courier service primarily based on how quickly the goods arrive at their destination. When it comes to courier services, numerous tasks and stages necessitate meticulous attention before the package reaches its final destination.

While designed and implemented processes and systems ensure that products do not inadvertently end up at locations other than their intended destination, causing customer dissatisfaction and discontent, the sheer number of steps within these processes, unfortunately, results in delayed customer deliveries. In terms of logistics, this situation specifically emphasises customer satisfaction; companies must actively seek ways to enhance their overall efficiency to remain competitive in a rapidly changing market environment (Stratten, 2018). According to Greengard (2015), the ability to provide real-time updates directly to customers is strongly associated with increased customer satisfaction. This advantage is due to its ability to meet the urgent needs of today's customers, who require instant access to information.

Courier companies' advanced real-time tracking and monitoring systems allow them to provide customers with precise, very accurate delivery predictions. This considerable improvement in service will improve customer satisfaction overall and reduce the number of missed deliveries and returns that may occur (Rejeb et al., 2020). As technology becomes increasingly available, it is obvious that courier companies should seriously investigate IoT solutions if they want to remain competitive and satisfy customers' growing expectations (Allioui, 2023).

IoT is important for courier companies in terms of inventory management enhancement and route optimisation (Prapinit et al., 2024). This technology ensures much more efficient and effective delivery performance. Precise tracking minimises the risk of item loss or misplacement in the delivery chain, thereby increasing customers' confidence in the service they receive (Agu et al., 2018; Wang & Huo, 2018). Companies can also proactively predict and improve any issues likely to occur during the delivery process using IoT technologies. This proactive approach provides a much smoother and consistently reliable customer service experience (Jean, 2024).

2.5.1.2. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Automation

Artificial intelligence, popularly known as AI, has massively changed various aspects of the courier business recently. Package sorting, disposition route planning, and customer service overdraws are examples (Jucha, 2021). AI-powered systems can expedite the analysis and processing of large volumes of data (Rodriguez-Bustelo et al., 2020; Hemphill, 2019). Numerous factors, including but not limited to prevailing traffic and weather patterns, as well as specific delivery priorities that require attention, optimise real-time delivery routes. Using such advanced technologies results in faster and more precise deliveries. These characteristics are undoubtedly essential for maintaining customer sentiments in today's competitive markets (Clausen et al., 2015; Younis et al., 2022).

Advanced AI-powered automation significantly enhances the accuracy and efficiency of package sorting (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). Automation significantly reduces human errors, which frequently lead to package misrouting; as a result, it guarantees accurate routing and timely dispatch of every package within the anticipated timeframe. Furthermore, automation ensures that AI-powered chatbots, when integrated with customer service platforms, show more responsiveness to customers' queries by replying and providing assistance immediately

(Christopher, 2016). This advantage of modern technology bridges the gap between ensuring a wonderful customer experience and resolving issues with due speed and efficiency to satisfy the customer (Rodríguez et al., 2021).

2.5.1.3. Cloud Computing and Data Analytics

Cloud computing is a framework for online access to computing resources and services like software and storage on a pay-per-use basis. It allows organizations to elastically scale usage based on demand without hefty upfront investment in hardware (Armbrust et al., 2010; Mell & Grance, 2011). Cloud computing has revolutionised data management for courier firms, a big transition they are making. By harnessing cloud-based platforms, courier companies are now capable of storing, processing, and analysing bulk data volumes with the highest levels of efficiency (Moldagulova et al., 2021). This enhanced capability is crucial in ensuring that operations run smoothly without any interruptions. Managing customer information is crucial, as it involves carefully following orders and optimising various delivery processes for performance. Additionally, the cloud facilitates real-time data sharing across departments and locations. This function ensures that stakeholders have access to current and up-to-date information. Teams in the CI can enhance their coordination and efficiency (Papakostas et al., 2020).

Cloud computing acts as a strong facilitator for data analytics. The term Data analytics, on the other hand, Cao (2017) refers “to the theories, technologies, instruments, and processes that allow for an in-depth understanding and exploration of actionable data insight.” “Data analytics can optimize business performance by measuring and weighing raw data to gain information and draw conclusions from it (The Investopedia, 2025)”, enabling the company to gain far better insights into customer behaviour and preference. By carefully analysing data from various points of contact, including direct customer contacts, different delivery patterns, and valuable feedback, companies can monitor significant trends and identify opportunities for improvement (Jintana et al., 2021). This data-centric approach will help businesses and organisations personalise and serve their customers better by meeting all their needs and expectations, resulting in increased customer satisfaction.

2.6. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Quality service is the cornerstone of any business's success and customer satisfaction. Fida et al., (2020) elaborate on this concept by arguing that services are delivered to the customer in a way that exceeds what was expected; this exceptional performance is then transformed into customer satisfaction. As previously explained, establishing and maintaining a competitive advantage in the service industry requires excellent service quality. Ismail et al., (2006) contend that the two factors that significantly influence customer satisfaction include the level at which customers trust the services they are receiving and the level at which they trust the service provider.

According to Khan and Fasih (2014), satisfied customers will stick with the company and prefer to avoid going to other companies. Cronin and Taylor (1992) state that SQ drives customer satisfaction and loyalty. The studies also

show that service quality is one of the significant factors in determining customer retention or satisfaction. Mueeed (2012) highlighted that enhancing service quality is the only way to boost revenue and market share. The findings of Tax and Brown (2012) show that the company's performance and profitability depend on the service quality. Furthermore, Ladhari et al. (2011) pointed out that a high level of service quality is required to attract and retain customer attention effectively.

Most would agree that, though conceptually separate and distinct variables, both customer satisfaction and service quality can be measured independently; however, they are positively related to each other in such a way that they reinforce one another (Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Anderson and Sullivan, 1993; Kiran and Diljit, 2017). For example, on the other hand, Paquette et al., (2009) believe that what impeded the progress of empirical studies on this topic was that there has yet to be a clear distinction between the two concepts of service quality and customer satisfaction firmly and precisely defined.

The present empirical study has identified service quality as an essential variable positively related to customer satisfaction. While most experts agree that service quality significantly impacts customer satisfaction, there needs to be a general agreement regarding a standard approach that could have wide application in measuring this crucial variable. This project is an inclusive study that considers specific models for measuring service quality. We analyse and discuss the respective models in excellent detail to ensure they are appropriate for evaluating the level of satisfaction customers are experiencing with courier services operating in Pakistan. We carry out the analysis accurately.

2.6.1. The SERVQUAL Model Parameters

Shahin (2006) cites the SERVQUAL model, developed by the esteemed scholars Parasuraman, Zeithami, and Berry, as one of the most basic and widely accepted measures of service quality. This particular model is a derivative of the earlier model developed by Gronroos (1984). By far, the most widespread means of measuring service quality relies on a comparison between customers' expectations before their exposure to the service and their actual perceptions and feelings about the very same service that was rendered to them—a means that has been famously termed SERVQUAL, initially proposed by Parasuraman et al., (1985). Saleh and Ryan (1991) found that Zeithami, Berry, and Parasuraman initially identified ten different service quality variables. They further tested these variables. These tests reduced the initial variables into five key dimensions: responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy.

Responsiveness: According to Parasuraman et al., (1988), this criterion assesses responsiveness in terms of the ability to resolve different issues arising right on time and without much hassle. It entails promptly responding to customer complaints and meeting their needs and expectations. It shows an excellent willingness to help customers satisfy their needs and demands. It also demonstrates responsiveness to the customer's specific needs

and expectations, ensuring a positive interaction and experience. **Reliability:** As discussed by Parasuraman et al., (1985), reliability is an important dimension reflecting the ability of a service provider to perform the service accurately, on time, and dependably. **Tangibles:** According to Sureshchandar et al., (2001), tangibles refer to the fact that physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials have a profound effect on customers' perceptions and experiences.

Assurance: This crucial factor plays a vital role in ensuring that customers can have complete trust in the quality of services provided by this firm, thereby reinforcing the establishment of the highest level of reputation and, above all, the customers' complete trust. This firm establishes a solid foundation of earned trust by providing professional services that meet high standards, demonstrating excellent technical capabilities and competence within the industry. **Empathy:** Among such extensive care, consideration, and detailed planning for making the customer feel like an esteemed "guest" of the business and to make him/her feel warmly welcomed on every occasion, the following becomes one of the most significant forms. Adil et al., (2013) observed that in applying the SERVQUAL model, service quality is measured by the difference between expectations and perceptions; hence, the equation is service quality = P - E.

2.6.2. Critiques of the SERVQUAL Model

Buttle (1996) gave SERVQUAL a negative review, saying that it was based on the wrong model of expectation disconfirmation rather than a stricter model of service excellence based on behaviour, which could have provided more useful information. He added that SERVQUAL only contributes to the psychometric, statistical, and economic bodies of knowledge established in the disciplines that are critical to a full understanding of service quality. Similarly, Cronin and Taylor (1994) stated that SERVQUAL has several paradigmatic problems due to its poorly conceived use of the disconfirmation model, which reduces its usefulness.

In addition, Andersson (1992) pointed out that SERVQUAL does not involve any theoretical underpinnings from any economic, statistical, or psychological disciplines, which are all cumbersome toward understanding service quality in a much more nuanced manner. Various scholars in academia have also expressed serious concerns about many aspects of the SERVQUAL model, such as its dimensional stability, dependability, and overall validity over time (Carman, 1990; Asubonteng et al., 1996; Brady and Cronin, 2001). In addition to these concerns, scholars have proposed modifications to the SERVQUAL model to accommodate specific service types (Finn and Kayande, 2004; Paquette et al., 2009).

2.6.3. The SERVQUAL Model's Uses

Berry (1986) asserts unequivocally that in order for an enterprise to thrive in a fiercely competitive and hostile market, it must guarantee the quality of its products and services. The question of service quality becomes of paramount importance to all of these business enterprises because some businesses solely rely on providing

services. In conclusion, enterprises that solely depend on providing services, including but not limited to telecommunication companies, airline services, and so on, have relatively no value or importance to customers if the quality of what they deliver could be improved.

According to Parasuraman et al., (1988), the framework of SERVQUAL is straightforward, and this is possible because of the adequately outlined expectation's structure. Each of the five distinct quality characteristics depicted in the model makes a specific statement within the structure. Furthermore, another significant use of SERVQUAL is segmenting multiple categories of perceived quality within a company's customer base. We segment based on the analysis and consideration of each customer's service score.

2.6.4. The SERVPERF Model Parameters

Indeed, this paradigm effectively addresses the SERVQUAL model's shortcomings by discarding service expectations and focussing solely on service performance. Not only is the SERVPERF model a variation of the SERVQUAL framework, but Cronin and Taylor (1992) say it is also a smart response to the many academic criticisms of the SERVQUAL model. Experts assert that direct measurement of the service's actual performance best depicts customers' feelings and sentiments. The study by Adil et al., (2013) declares the SERVQUAL methodology ineffective because survey respondents are supposed to complete two questionnaires: one on expectations and the other on perceived service quality.

Numerous studies have explored the SERVQUAL and SERVPERF models in various service industries (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). One empirical study that focused specifically on the advertising industry, Quester & Romaniuk (1997), even reported that SERVPERF outperformed one of the adaptations of the SERVQUAL model. Moreover, Carrillat et al., (2007) conducted research showing that SERVQUAL and SERVPERF are equally effective and reliable tools in measuring the quality of services delivered. A comprehensive meta-analysis served as the fundamental foundation for the study. The main goal of this study was to look into the relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality in more detail. Note that the SERVPERF model performs better in this type of analysis (Moisescu and Gica, 2013). We specifically conducted this extensive study within the context of the tourism industry.

2.6.5. Models Tailored to Certain Industries

On the other side, Ghotbabadi et al., (2015) mentioned in their study that although the models referred to as SERVQUAL and SERVPERF had been developed specifically to assess and measure service quality for a wide array of service industries, many experts in the field strongly feel that these specific models cannot be utilised or applied to certain specialised sectors that differ from these general industries. In this regard, Dabholkar et al., (1996) presented a different view by proposing a hierarchical conceptualisation to quantify service quality for the retail sector. They demonstrated that the dimensions and subdimensions of service quality determine the overall

perception and contribute to customer service. Tsauro et al., (2002) modified the SERVQUAL model with various airline-specific qualities for the airline industry by applying fuzzy set theory and creating a unique model.

Mentzer et al., (2001) made a significant effort to develop an integrated logistics service quality (LSQ) scale comprising nine distinct dimensions: ordering procedures, timeliness, information quality, order accuracy, order condition, ordering release quantities, order discrepancy handling, personnel contact quality, and overall order quality. The developed scale for logistics service quality has gained widespread adoption and serves as a fundamental source for further research in the crucial field of logistics service quality. In a somewhat related study, Rafiq and Jaafar (2007) attempted to identify and explore the specific limitations of logistics service quality.

Despite careful dimension selection, the model for logistics service quality is not universally applicable due to factors such as geography and industry. The model clearly needs to be more broadly applicable in a variety of contexts as a direct result of these limitations. In 2015, Hua and Jing did a study that raised the concern that the logistics service quality model's nine-dimension scale might not be the best way to measure the quality of courier services in a business-to-consumer (B2C) setting. The model's original development aimed to evaluate logistics performance in a business-to-business (B2B) setting, making its limitations particularly noteworthy.

2.6.6. Evaluation of Courier Service Excellence

According to Yee & Daud (2011), the SERVQUAL model has been the most widely used framework in several studies that have attempted to measure and evaluate the level of courier services. In another related study, Zhu et al., (2011) also conducted research involving the Chinese courier industry, in which they seized the initiative to adapt the original SERVQUAL scale to suit their specific model for assessing the quality of courier services. They further enhanced their approach by including "security" as a new dimension in their evaluation framework. For their part, Meng and Zhou (2016) added a new dimension called "guarantee" to the existing SERVQUAL model, which led to the creation of this fuller and more accurate assessment model. The study's findings and conclusions suggest that the local courier business can improve its service provision by expediting the process of customer complaints and seeking solutions. Again, they are also considering implementing tailored and specialised services aimed at meeting the individual and unique needs of every different customer.

For instance, Liu & Liu (2014) studied the quality of express LS in Changdao, China. In their overall study, they critically examined the relevant aspects of this industry. In such an array study, they incorporated both the LSQ and SERVQUAL models to obtain an overall sound judgement about the quality of the courier service. In addition, Wei et al., (2016) undertook a significant task related to integrating the LSQ and SERVQUAL models. Still, using a seven-dimension scale, they systematically measured the service quality of the EMS system in China. Only a few researchers have used the LSQ model to measure the quality of courier service. Thus, the literature gap does exist. Ho et al., (2012) assessed customer satisfaction in Malaysia, and it is in contrast to Pholsuwanachai (2011), who

researched the service performance of courier firms in Thailand. He also concluded that only the dimensions of service quality, rather than the lot size of orders issued, have an impact on service performance.

Although the courier industry has experienced remarkable growth on an international scale, Gulc (2017) claims that only a few articles have directly addressed the issue of measuring service quality in this industry. Because this industry requires better evaluation methods, many researchers used existing scales and came forward with tailored scales to better assess the quality of courier service. Valaei et al., (2016) embarked on the critical task of designing the "CouQual" scale, a comprehensive tool intended suitably to probe into the various factors responsible for the quality of courier service.

It also aims to ascertain the influence of the perceived service level on the overall service quality appraisal. In this context, the "CouQual" scale meticulously measures five crucial dimensions that contribute to the comprehension of service quality: promptness, convenience, accuracy, safety, and tangibles. Through the study's conduct, the researchers found that the five dimensions—characteristics, promptness, safety, and convenience—were the most meaningful, combined to bestow the meaning of perceived service quality. They found that accuracy and tangibility did not have a positive relationship with the level of service quality. The finding suggests that these qualities may not be as important to customers.

Septian et al., (2022) utilised the courier service quality (CSQ) scale to extensively study and determine the relationship between the quality of courier services and the customer satisfaction levels realised. The results from their study indicate that courier service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, meaning that improvement in service quality may increase customer satisfaction levels. Based on their findings, the authors recommend adjusting the existing courier service quality scales to fit some countries' specific needs and conditions. More importantly, Burdi et al., (2023) developed a KPI model for courier services operating in Pakistan based on the fuzzy AHP methodology.

Drawing coherent and dependable conclusions from the sum of existing research currently available in the literature is challenging. This is mainly because the different authors have yet to define a common or standard set of parameters that would affect the overall quality of the courier service. Usually, the authors used specific rules to select the factors under examination. These rules may vary depending on the service provider's service, customers, location, and culture.

Latip et al., (2012) identified and highlighted that relatively few comprehensive studies have mainly focused on the SERVQUAL model in this domain of courier service, which is a significant area of service delivery (Johnson and Sirikit, 2002; Naik and Srinivasan, 2015). SERVQUAL is a successful, effective, and recommended method for assessing service quality in many industries. Professionals and researchers alike have thoroughly researched the model in numerous empirical studies, resulting in its widespread application across various service fields. We have

thoroughly tested this approach and found it exceptionally effective in evaluating and assessing service quality across various sectors and industries.

The SERVQUAL model is useful for comprehensively assessing and analyzing the quality of courier deliveries. This study has primarily borrowed from the SERVQUAL model's concepts because, in academic research and literature, it has gained sufficient recognition and acceptance. Recognizing that each industry has unique elements and peculiarities that frequently influence perceived service quality is important. Core factors identified in courier service research – A multi stakeholder study on courier service quality, which analyzed feedback from e shops, e customers and courier companies, found that timeliness of delivery, effectiveness of delivery, efficient and fast order processing and responsiveness to reported problems were the factors with the strongest direct impact on overall service quality (Gulc, 2021). These factors align with the SERVQUAL dimensions of responsiveness (timely response to customer issues), efficiency (fast and effective processing) and accuracy (compliance and completeness of orders) (Gulc, 2021). In the same analysis, tangibility and empathy related factors—such as branch appearance or courteous behavior—had far weaker relationships with other variables, suggesting they are less critical for courier (Gulc, 2021).

Support from logistics service literature – As for LSQ research in logistics literature, Mentzer et al. posited a model consisting of nine dimensions encompassing order accuracy, punctuality, and order mismatch handling (Lin et al., 2023). Subsequent research repeatedly places a strong focus on order accuracy (ensuring shipments are in line with customer orders) and punctuality (speed of delivery) as focal variables in determining customer satisfaction (Lin et al., 2023). These are congruent with accuracy and responsiveness/efficiency found in this study. Conversely, those such as aesthetics or empathy were revealed to contribute less towards intentions towards service reuse and overall satisfaction.

Relevance for Pakistan operations issues – Empirical literature reveals that in Pakistan, courier customers are very dissatisfied with delayed delivery, incorrect shipments, and delayed responses in answering queries ((Parasuraman et al., 1988; Gulc, 2021; Ahmed & Anwar, 2022). These are directly at issue with responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Focused improvement in such issues can result in dramatic customer satisfaction gains while fixes in tangibility or empathy do little in rectifying structural issues such as inefficient routing or delivery failure (Gulc, 2021). Focusing on these three dimensions is thereby in line with universal research results as well as certain operations-specific imperatives earmarking the courier sector in Pakistan. By grounding the choice of dimensions in published logistics and courier research—rather than relying solely on theoretical models—this research provides empirical support for

focus on responsiveness, accuracy and efficiency, thereby addressing the methodological gap identified in earlier versions of the thesis.

2.7. Critical Discussion of Existing Research and Identified Gaps

Despite the breadth of research concerning service quality, there exists a notable scarcity of studies dedicated to courier and logistics services, with existing investigations frequently addressing only fragments of the overarching issue. For instance, in a multi-stakeholder evaluation of the quality of courier services, Gulc (2021) synthesized various indicators into a limited set of essential factors—namely, delivery timeliness, delivery effectiveness, efficient order processing, and responsiveness to reported issues—thereby illustrating that operational speed and order accuracy serve as pivotal determinants of courier service quality. However, there was no investigation in this study on how digital technologies' role facilitates such aspects or impacts their effect on customer loyalty and satisfaction. Similarly, Mentzer et al.'s logistics service quality (LSQ) framework identifies nine dimensions such as order accuracy, timeliness and order discrepancy handling; while widely adopted, it predates recent digital transformations and thus offers little guidance on how technologies like real time tracking or automated sorting shape those dimensions. Lin et al., (2023) explored LSQ dimensions in China versus customer satisfaction but included logistics service quality and reuse intention as major constructs. These articles all attest to the saliency of responsiveness, accuracy and efficiency but entirely rule out digitalization as an antecedent and only sporadically test mediation effects involving such dimensions.

More recently, researchers have begun examining how technology affects service quality in e-commerce logistics, but important gaps remain. Akil and Ungan (2022) showed that timeliness, order condition, order accuracy and order discrepancy handling positively influence customer satisfaction, emphasizing that customers value fast and error-free deliveries. Nevertheless, that study focused on general logistics service quality and did not investigate specific digital technologies (e.g., real-time tracking, mobile apps) or their impact on responsiveness, accuracy and efficiency. Conversely, He et al., (2024) demonstrated that digital transformation improves supply chain efficiency in Chinese listed companies, yet their analysis operated at the corporate supply chain level and did not address B2C courier services or customer satisfaction. Taken together, these findings underscore a critical gap: while operational accuracy, timeliness and efficiency are recognized as central to courier service quality, there is little empirical work linking digital technologies to these dimensions or exploring how improvements in responsiveness, accuracy and efficiency mediate the relationship between technology adoption and customer satisfaction—particularly in emerging markets like Pakistan. It addresses this gap by investigating digital technologies as a driver for service quality improvement and gauging their indirect effects on customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry.

2.8. Integrated Rationale and Hypothesis Development

Research on service quality for couriers and logistics is continually centered around operations such as punctuality, order accuracy in delivering orders, and communication. For example, multi-stakeholder investigation determined that the promptness of delivery, the efficacy of the delivery process, swift order processing, and the responsiveness to reported issues represented the most significant determinants of overall service quality (Gulc, 2021). These elements correspond with the service quality dimensions of responsiveness (timely communication), accuracy (adherence to and thoroughness of orders), and efficiency (rapid and effective processing). Nevertheless, Gulc's research was descriptive in nature; it did not explore how digital technologies—such as real-time tracking, mobile applications, or automated sorting—might affect these dimensions or if enhancements in responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency lead to increased customer satisfaction. Similarly, the logistics service quality (LSQ) frameworks that emerged from Mentzer et al.'s research emphasize order accuracy, timeliness, and the management of order discrepancies but were formulated prior to the widespread integration of digital technologies, thereby offering minimal insights into technology-driven advancements. Studies on e-commerce logistics service quality again testify in favor of the fact that responsiveness, order condition, order accuracy, and order discrepancy handling are salient in determining customer satisfaction. However, such research does not take into consideration the effect of digital technologies or accommodate specific conditions prevailing in emerging markets. It is observed in this study as a substantial gap: while it is obvious how responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency are desirable attributes for customers, no empirical research is available about up until what level digital technologies improve such aspects and thereby increase customer satisfaction, especially in the setting of Pakistan's courier industry.

2.8.1 Effect of Digital Technologies on Responsiveness

We expect digital technologies to significantly enhance an organization's responsiveness to customer service, ensuring it is timely, qualitative, and flexible to meet various needs. Such responsiveness is of enormous significance in today's highly competitive global economy, as it enables an organisation to respond to customers' demands quickly, economise on its operations, and offer customised products that better suit customer tastes and preferences (Meehan & Dawson, 2002; Razalli, 2008; Zerenler, 2007; Theoharakis & Hooley, 2003; Liang et al., 2011).

In service delivery, the integration and application of digital technologies provide the key to increasing responsiveness. These technologies facilitate quicker and more precise responses to customer enquiries and demands, thereby ensuring their satisfaction. Such a high degree of responsiveness becomes critical in logistics, postal, and courier services, where timely and appropriate response to customers' needs becomes paramount (Bouranta et al., 2009; Stauss, 1995; Poria & Oppewal, 2003; Kritchanchai, 2004).

Digital technologies significantly enhance the way companies interact with their customers by providing highly responsive and controllable features. This not only serves to gain the customers' attention but also acts as an

essential factor for enhancing their overall engagement throughout the buying process. The ability to respond timely and appropriately to the needs and queries of the customers is, no doubt, one of the essential elements or factors that contribute to the success of digital technologies within the business context (Zhao & Lu, 2012; Wu, 2019; Grewal et al., 2018).

Companies that highly value the development and enhancement of their digital capabilities are significantly better prepared to generate and disseminate information and to react effectively to the market's demands. This strategic focus allows them to improve their overall ability to respond swiftly and demonstrates a remarkable level of agility within a constantly changing and dynamic market environment (Tams et al., 2014; Kohli, 2017). Therefore, the current study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: Digital technologies have a positive effect on responsiveness.

2.8.2. Effect of Digital Technologies on Accuracy

Mobile vehicle tracking devices integrate advanced technologies such as telematics, GPS, GPRS, and GIS to track the precise real-time location of various physical objects moving through the supply chain. Implementing such technology not only ensures an overall increase in cost efficiency but also significantly boosts customer satisfaction by providing users with precise and timely information about the shipment's current location, its delivery status, and the estimated arrival times of their parcels (Mondragon et al., 2009; Durr & Giannopoulos, 2003; Tsai, 2006; Malladi & Agrawal, 2002).

Real-time tracking systems have significantly assisted organisations by decreasing the volume of customer calls, as these systems provide immediate confirmation of proof of delivery. This confirmation procedure immediately clears all doubts in a customer's mind about their delivery status. Companies such as Amazon, DHL, and UPS have used these new technologies to improve the speed and accuracy of their deliveries. These companies have achieved higher levels of cost efficiency and increased customer service (Zhu & Liu, 2018).

Digital technologies increase visibility and traceability along the supply chain, turning an otherwise incomprehensible situation for all the parties concerned into one where information is more available and understandable. This level of transparency remained one of the critical benefits enjoyed by logistics companies, allowing them to optimally utilise their networks, reduce conflicts, and quickly locate any faults or issues. This process eventually improves the general accuracy of the supply chain operation (Wanganoo & Patil, 2020; Cano et al., 2021; Wijewickrama et al., 2021).

The integration and adoption of various newest innovations, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), and artificial intelligence (AI), in logistics systems provide a real-time monitoring process that is comprehensively developed and correlates with an increased level of sorting accuracy. The most

advanced innovation's integrated mechanism significantly reduces errors in this connection. It is essential for enhancing customer satisfaction and overall performance across the board. Consequently, AI has demonstrated remarkable potential in decreasing the sorting process errors by up to 50%, demonstrating the efficiency and reliability of AI-based innovations. Furthermore, an abundance of studies and expert reports (Chuang et al., 2017; Clausen et al., 2015; Younis et al., 2022; Hartley & Sawaya, 2019) have announced that AI-based innovations will soon become drastically essential to the logistic sphere of operations. In light of the aforementioned debate, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H2: Digital technologies have a positive effect on accuracy.

2.8.3. Effect of Digital Technologies on Efficiency

Operating within a well-structured digital ecosystem pays dividends in terms of business efficiency. Implementing and adopting various digital technologies has played a crucial role in streamlining processes effectively and using available resources more effectively for greater productivity and effectiveness in operation, improving efficiency across multiple industries (Gavalas et al., 2022; Sorbe et al., 2019).

The enablement and use of digital technologies on various platforms, such as social media, smartphones, drones, and extensive networks, have raised the general effectiveness of last-mile delivery systems to very high levels. Effective integration of retailers into last-mile delivery operations resolves a set of crucial issues related to reliability, economic viability, efficient use of resources, and accurate scheduling in one go. This integration, therefore, causes a significant improvement in operational efficiency in the delivery processes (Tiwapat et al., 2018; De Souza et al., 2014).

In this respect, the seamless amalgamation of digital technologies with information systems is crucial for optimum operational efficiency across a range of industries. This application influences accelerated service processes, thereby offering service-based industries an opportunity to improve the accessibility and overall efficiency of their respective operational outputs (Igor et al., 2019; Laudien & Pesch, 2018).

Blockchain, generally called distributed ledger technology, considerably enhances the efficiency of financial transactions. This is evident in bank transfers and international payments, which simplify these processes and make them faster and more reliable (Pan, 2024). Digital technologies have transformed the courier service industry, resulting in considerable increases in efficiency. The above examples support this hypothesis.

H3: Digital technologies have a positive effect on efficiency.

2.8.4. Effect of Digital Technologies, Responsiveness, Accuracy, and Efficiency on Customer Satisfaction

Successful digital transformation profoundly heralds the service-centric business revolution, influencing not only internal business processes but also external interactions and customer touchpoints. Businesses must fully prepare themselves to adapt to these constantly evolving digital transformation technologies in order to realise their full potential and strive for excellence in their service delivery (Demirel, 2022; Demirkan & Spohrer, 2018; Perkin & Abraham, 2017).

Digital technologies play a crucial role in enhancing the overall quality of services by significantly improving operational efficiency, effectively reducing the amount of human labour required, and expertly tailoring solutions to meet customers' varied needs precisely. When companies provide high-quality digital services, it leads to a notable boost in overall company performance, an increase in customer satisfaction, and a deeper emotional engagement with the brand itself, as evidenced by various studies (Demirel, 2022; Satpathy et al., 2020; Pansari & Kumar, 2017).

Digitalisation is a crucial determinant of service quality across many sectors. It has a strong influence on customer satisfaction. Quite a few studies conducted within this domain have shown that there is a strong positive relationship between the magnitude of customer satisfaction experienced by customers and the quality of the digital services offered, as particularly evident from the Tunisian Islamic banking case (Zouari & Abdelhedi, 2021).

With the advent of digital technologies, especially mobile phones and different online interfaces, the customer decision-making process has dramatically changed in today's world. Numerous studies on the subject have demonstrated a strong and noteworthy correlation between customer satisfaction levels and the overall quality of the digital services they receive, such as online shopping experiences and electronic services (Abdullah & Kassim, 2009; Wolfenbarger & Gilly, 2003; Wu, 2011). Drawing from the preceding discussion, we can formulate the fourth hypothesis as follows:

H4: Digital technologies have a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

The SERVQUAL model is useful in understanding the theoretical relationship between the concept of responsiveness and the resulting level of satisfaction. In simpler terms, it asserts that responsiveness, which refers to a firm's capacity to collaborate effectively with and provide service to the customer in a timely manner, can positively impact consumers' perceptions of satisfaction (Pitafi et al., 2019; Munusamy et al., 2010).

Employee responsiveness, maintained through a personal commitment to the roles and a genuine willingness to serve customers' needs and interests, contributed significantly to increasing customer satisfaction. Timely communication and prompt redress of customer grievances demonstrated their responsiveness, as both are

crucial elements that enhance customers' perceptions of overall service quality (Hasan, 2013; Siddiqi, 2011; Pitafi et al., 2019).

Extensive studies carried out across various industries, including the banking sector in countries like Jordan, Hong Kong, and Saudi Arabia, present responsiveness as one of the most important constituents of service quality. This responsiveness is critical for impacting and building customer satisfaction, as various studies have shown (Suliman, 2013; Lau et al., 2013; Albarq, 2013).

For customers, getting quick responses is highly important; many such swift responses may arguably be considered touchstones for supreme-quality service. A service provider's ability and willingness to efficiently satisfy customer needs and expectations significantly influence overall customer satisfaction (Voss et al., 2003; Nambisan et al., 2016). A service provider's capacity and desire to respond to customer demands influences customer perception, which can impact satisfaction. As a result, we expect:

H5: Responsiveness has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Reliability and accuracy often complement each other, making it a crucial factor in assessing the quality of services provided. It reflects a firm's ability to keep its promise or commitment in terms of providing correct and accurate information, accurately filling an order, or delivering merchandise on time without unnecessary delay. A company that produces outcomes with consistency in reliability automatically secures greater trust and satisfaction from customers, leading to enhanced relations and loyalty (Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Yang, 2001; Zeithaml et al., 2002).

Accurate transactions, detailed billing, and complete product descriptions can fully satisfy customers. For example, banks that can present correct and understandable account information or conduct transactions quickly and efficiently have a high probability of reaching advanced levels of customer satisfaction (Armstrong et al., 2000; Lau et al., 2013).

For instance, in service industries like banking, tangibility, responsiveness, and accuracy will primarily determine customers' satisfaction with the services. Providing reliable, accurate, and timely services is considered one of the significant ingredients of overall service quality (Lau et al., 2013). Consequently, we construct the sixth hypothesis, proposed below:

H6: Accuracy has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Efficiency is an integral component of overall service quality because it substantially reflects a firm's ability to meet customers' demands and expectations regarding promptness, convenience, and speed of service delivery. Services delivered efficiently provide timely and reliable results that, in turn, evoke feelings of being valued and cared for, thus increasing customer satisfaction to the fullest possible extent (Zeithaml et al., 2009; Parasuraman

et al., 1985; Andrejić, 2013).

Research has continued to demonstrate that the general efficiency of business operations, such as logistics, supply chain management, and service delivery, has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction. If these services can be performed well, customers are likely to consider what is being provided as higher quality and thus become more satisfied overall with their experience (Chang et al., 2017; Burity, 2021).

Efficient services play a vital role in boosting overall satisfaction levels and helping to strengthen customer loyalty on various occasions. Suppose companies continually offer premium-class and efficient services to their customers. In that case, customers are likelier to create and retain a sense of loyalty toward the respective company's specific products and services (Marquardt et al., 2017). Consequently, we proceed to the seventh hypothesis, outlined below:

H7: Efficiency has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

2.8.5. Mediation of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction

The information system success and technological acceptance models provide a framework for understanding how the adoption of chatbots influences the overall online customer experience and levels of customer satisfaction. The responsiveness exhibited by a chatbot plays a crucial role in significantly increasing the perceived value that customers assign to the quality of customer service they receive, thereby establishing it as an essential element contributing to customer satisfaction (Chen et al., 2021).

Responsiveness can be defined as delivering quick and timely services, which increases user convenience and fosters more effective interactions. Chatbots hold significant value in today's digital landscape due to their remarkable capability to provide immediate responses to enquiries and their continuous availability around the clock. This characteristic dramatically enhances the overall customer experience (Chung et al., 2020; Roy et al., 2018; Tiwana, 1998).

Consequently, companies increasingly view responsive chatbots as a revolutionary shopping tool that significantly enhances the overall quality of their customer service. When customers engage with a responsive and highly efficient chatbot, they are extremely likely to develop a positive perception of the company (Molla & Licker, 2001; Li et al., 2021). Therefore, we proceed to the eighth hypothesis, outlined below:

H8: Responsiveness mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

Digital technologies, such as real-time tracking systems, AI, and automation, improve the accuracy of service

delivery. The improvement entails the actual execution of orders, precise billing, and timely release of accurate information, thus cultivating customer trust and satisfaction (Yang, 2001; Zeithaml et al., 2002).

With the advancement of digital technologies, enhanced accuracy reduces errors and improves the reliability of the service experience. Customers prefer accurate service delivery. Therefore, they derive higher satisfaction and exercise trust in such businesses (Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Armstrong et al., 2000).

Accuracy plays a crucial mediating role in the process because it effectively leverages the intrinsic potential of digital technologies to realise substantial and tangible improvements in service quality. This level of precision serves to meet and exceed customer expectations while making sure the innovations of digitality are in a position to have a positive effect on overall customer satisfaction (Lau et al., 2013; Burity, 2021). Consequently, we proceed to the ninth hypothesis, presented below:

H9: Accuracy mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

Improvement in operational efficiency is greatly dependent on digital technologies like automation, real-time data processing, and AI-driven systems. These innovations simplify processes, reduce service delays, and optimise resources for the ultimate benefit of an expedited, more convenient service (Gavalas et al., 2022; Sorbe et al., 2019).

Efficient services meet customer expectations in terms of timeliness, ease, and rapidity. Using digital technologies to make things run more smoothly cuts down on delays and mistakes in service, making the customer experience smoother and more satisfying overall (Chang et al., 2017; Burity, 2021).

Efficiency serves as a mediating factor, transforming the numerous capabilities of digital technologies into tangible and practical enhancements in the quality of services provided. While businesses work to create an advantage by strategically leveraging technology to deliver their services much more efficiently than before, the value perceived for these services by customers can only increase, thereby fostering overall customer satisfaction (Zeithaml et al., 2009; Marquardt et al., 2017). Therefore, we proceed to the tenth hypothesis, presented below:

H10: Efficiency mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

2.9. Theoretical Underpinning

The given study undertakes an in-depth analysis of the important role digital technologies play in enhancing customer satisfaction within Pakistan's B2C supply chain in relation to courier services. This research, therefore, concentrates on establishing how responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency mediate the level of customer satisfaction. We develop the theoretical framework for this study based on the well-established SERVQUAL model.

We supplement this theoretical base with relevant and recent empirical evidence from 2020 to 2024, ensuring that the findings align with current market realities and trends.

The SERVQUAL model, which was founded by Parasuraman et al. (1988), has been mostly regarded as an innovative model to assess the service quality based on a gap analysis between customer expectations and perceived service performance. SERVQUAL typically comprises five dimensions of significance: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. However, the study critically applies SERVQUAL to measure responsiveness only, accuracy (on the basis of reliability), and efficiency because these most directly address the core concerns of courier operations in Pakistan's evolving market.

Responsiveness is highly significant in-service businesses, and it influences customer satisfaction. In the courier business, responsiveness refers to providing quick assistance and alerting customers about any issues. Research shows that technological solutions like real-time monitoring and automated notifications improve customer satisfaction through instant communication (Rane et al., 2023). Accuracy, linked to the reliability of SERVQUAL, has a major bearing on courier services for customer trust. Errors in delivery reduce the reliability of service, causing dissatisfaction and damage to reputation. Advances in technology like GPS navigation and IoT tracking reduce these errors, enhancing delivery accuracy (Lee & Baker, 2017). Efficiency brings power to SERVQUAL as it emphasizes the optimization of operations, which is essential for on-time delivery and cost control in profitability and competitiveness. Efficiency is not one of the essential SERVQUAL dimensions but emerges due to the model's emphasis on meeting customer expectations and eliminating waste. Cloud computing, analytics, and automation improve resource allocation and routing (Zhong et al., 2022).

Recent research has shown full support for the relevance and importance of the SERVQUAL model in determining the general impact of digital technologies on the quality of services delivered. Raja & Sivakumar (2022) conducted a comprehensive study that demonstrated the significant positive impact of using various digital tools in logistics to enhance the perceived reliability and responsiveness of services. Such an increase in service attributes leads to a higher level of customer satisfaction. Moreover, Ricardianto et al., (2023) also revealed important findings that usage of digital platforms by logistical and courier service industries improves the responsiveness of those services, which also increases the delivery accuracy. Customers' perceptions of the quality of the services they receive positively reflect this improvement. These studies, in turn, support the finding that digital technologies are essential in improving critical aspects of the SERVQUAL model for increased overall customer satisfaction.

This study justifies the use of SERVQUAL both theoretically and practically. A review indicates that tangibility and empathy are significant to service firms with interpersonal contact but less relevant to the logistics-focused courier company (Ahmed & Anwar, 2022). The success of the courier company relies less on work atmosphere or emotional care and more on operational precision and timely execution, with responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency being significant. Prior applications of SERVQUAL in logistics identify responsiveness and reliability gaps

as key drivers of dissatisfaction (Kidwai & Maqbool, 2023; Noor-ul-Ain et al., 2022). However, no effort has been made to examine the possibility of digital technology bridging these gaps in the framework of SERVQUAL. This study fills this gap by incorporating digital technology into the model, enhancing theoretical insight and practical guidance for the industry.

The SERVQUAL gap model measures perceived service quality and structures tools to enquire about gaps between customer expectations and performance that can be closed by digital tools. It helps in identifying variables, making surveys, and forming hypotheses connecting technology adoption with service quality and customer satisfaction. This makes the framework academically sound and reflective of Pakistan's courier industry's operating realities, where digitalisation is vital for improving the service and the need to remain competitive. This view refers to the need to extend classical service quality theory to technology-mediated environments. This research offers a sound basis for empirical testing, closing a significant gap in literature and practice.

2.10. Research Framework

This study primarily investigates the impact of digital technologies and responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency on customer satisfaction. Every organisation experiences a variety of effects of digital technologies, including responsiveness, service quality, accuracy, and efficiency. Thus, digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency are considered predictors in this study. Customer satisfaction is the outcome variable that is most crucial to every business. Consequently, we determined that digital technologies, along with responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, are essential for an organisation to outperform. For this study, we selected responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency as mediators in the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction, given their significant role in enhancing customer satisfaction. Figure 2.1 depicts the conceptual model so readers can better understand it.

Figure 2.1. Conceptual Framework of the Research

2.11. Summary of Chapter 2

The literature review examines the relationship between digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, as well as the multi-dimensional but critically important customer satisfaction within the Pakistan courier context. It underlines the vital contribution customer satisfaction as a multidimensional construct has to business success since a leading drive for customer loyalty comes from satisfaction, retention contributes to it, and overall profitability depends on retention. Previous studies on customer satisfaction illustrate the myriad dimensions that scholars have attempted to use in defining and measuring customer satisfaction. Many academics strongly emphasise the primordial role of service quality as an elementary influence on satisfaction outcomes. Recent research, however, has focused on real-time tracking automation and improving responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, which are critical factors driving customer satisfaction. This chapter mentions that satisfied customers positively contribute and engage in repeat business through word-of-mouth (WOM), thereby influencing a company's long-term success and profitability.

The chapter also discusses theoretical framework, including the SERVQUAL model. This framework offers a comprehensive foundation for understanding. Digital transformation enhances and improves customer experiences in various contexts. In addition, the chapter explains the massive influence of digital technologies on organizations' service delivery processes. Digital technologies, like IoT, cloud computing, and AI, play a crucial role in optimising processes, enhancing accuracy, and ultimately raising customers' expectations. We develop various hypotheses to explore the responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency that could potentially mediate the relationship

between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. The literature review has identified gaps in the existing research, particularly in the context of Pakistan's courier industry, providing a foundation for the current study.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

The present study investigates the relationship between digital technologies, customer satisfaction, and service quality. This chapter, therefore, describes the methods adopted in research to ascertain such a relationship. Firstly, this section delineates the research design, covering the definition of the target population, the process of selecting respondents, the target sample frame, the estimation of sample size, and the mode of administering the survey. The next section outlines the procedures followed in data analysis and the criteria for structural equation modelling, as adopted in the present study.

3.1. Research Design

The term "research design" refers to a framework or methodical approach to data collection and analysis of a research problem (Ranganathan & Aggarwal, 2018). Bryman (2007) explains that a plan for gathering and analysing data is known as a "research design." Research design encompasses strategy, sampling, data collection, and data analysis. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2011), research design involves collecting and analysing data to solve problems. De Vaus (2001) states that the primary goal of a research design is to ensure that the gathered data clearly and convincingly addresses the research objectives. In addition to the descriptive research design, Hair et al., (2003) also suggest three other study designs: the correlational, causal, and exploratory research designs. Sekaran (2003) also supports the statement and suggests casual and correlational research designs. Social science research employs several types of research designs, including exploratory, causal, correlational, and descriptive.

According to Ghauri et al., (1995), descriptive research identifies the population characteristics or phenomena mentioned in the problem statement. This approach prioritizes the "what" over the "why" of the research topic. Parasuraman et al., (1991) argue that descriptive research aims to describe a well-defined process. Hair et al., (2006) explain that descriptive research may use survey data or case studies or be based on observation. It also specifies relationships and their variations. One crucial aspect of descriptive research is that, although it may use multiple variables, a descriptive study only requires one variable. Descriptive studies serve three primary functions: describing, explaining, and validating study findings (Sekaran, 2003).

According to Hair et al., (2003), this research design has a few restrictions. Firstly, although

descriptive research is considered a very accurate research approach; its primary purpose is to help researchers better understand a specific topic. Therefore, it is challenging to identify a scenario's underlying causes or explain any "why" questions. Johnson (1953) also viewed secrecy as a flaw in this approach. When respondents know who the researcher is, they may either provide untruthful replies or answers they believe the researcher wants to hear. We resolved this problem by distributing the questionnaire to walk-in courier service customers, making them aware of the researcher's objectives for the current investigation.

According to Malhotra (2008), there are several approaches to research design, such as descriptive, causal, and exploratory. Parasuraman (1991) explains that exploratory research seeks to establish a framework and guide a constructive research study by first understanding a vague research problem. However, Ghauri et al., (1995) clarified that the purpose of an exploratory investigation is to comprehend a complex, unstructured problem. When relevant information is absent, understanding situations that require structuring becomes easier. According to Flick (1998), numerous researchers have recommended the focus group technique as a valuable tool for exploratory research and idea generation. We also need exploratory research to develop theories and hypotheses for further testing. This is because it helps us understand things better and provides a foundation for theories.

Churchill and Iacobucci (2006) suggest that the most effective way to ascertain cause-and-effect consequences is through experimentation, typically applying the causal study design. Sekaran (2003) also confirmed that causal studies identify cause-and-effect links because, similar to descriptive research, the subject of study is well-structured and well-known. Krause (2016) suggested that to determine causal explanations, it's essential to identify the consequences that require explanation before identifying the causes. According to Hair et al., (2006), the many redundant and complicating variables in social contexts make it challenging to conclude causal links. Furthermore, causal research makes sense when the investigation aims to identify the triggers for a specific phenomenon.

Esser & Vliegenthart (2017) highlighted the correlational design, which examines correlations between variables in a single group at multiple levels. This nonexperimental design examines the relationship between two or more variables. Wood et al., (2006) argued that researchers use correlation design to examine the impact of a possible cause they cannot control. This kind of research aims to characterize the relationship between the variables of interest rather than to

identify the causal relationship between the variables.

As explained above, selecting the best study design is critical to achieving the investigation's objectives. The primary aim of the research was to examine the correlation between digital technologies, service quality, and customer satisfaction. As a result, descriptive research was the most appropriate research design for establishing the study's framework. Hair et al., (2006) suggested that descriptive research is the better option when the study's objective is to identify the link between several factors. A descriptive research design is appropriate for this study because it strives to correctly and systematically explain a phenomenon.

There are two types of data collection methods: primary and secondary. Primary data refers to unpublished, first-hand information that no one can modify. "Secondary data" refers to information obtained from published sources, which indicates that the information has already been received for another purpose and may be utilised for other research goals. According to Kabir (2016), there are several ways to obtain primary data, including surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and experiments. Snyder (2019) recommended a survey as the most effective method for collecting primary data through interviews and questionnaires. To meet the study's objective, we collected data via a self-administered questionnaire. Self-administered questionnaires are ones that the respondent can complete on their own, whether on paper, online, or through a computer offline. They rely on the clarity of the written word rather than the interviewers' skill (Zikmund, 2003). We collected the data for this cross-sectional study all at once.

According to Saunders et al. (2009), quantitative research, commonly known as empirical research, extensively uses numerical data to enable generalisations. Quantitative research aims to gather data through surveys or carefully scripted interviews to examine the relationship between two or more variables (Baker and Foy, 2008). This research uses a quantitative method to test the hypothesis of the conceptual model.

Researchers have demonstrated the benefits of both qualitative and quantitative research designs over time. The researchers presented several reasons for the advantages and disadvantages of each method, and practitioners argued about how well they worked in different situations. To complete the study, a significant selection of methods is necessary. According to Eriksson and Kovalainen (2008), the two main methods for research are qualitative and

quantitative. The investigations can consider various research methods, including quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods (Attia & Edge, 2017).

Emerson (1995) argues that the qualitative approach is often more flexible, giving participants more influence over the information gathered. Another concern is the possibility that a particular issue will go unnoticed. Wolcott (1994) asserts that it generates data that lacks objective verification. The analytical procedure, including categorization and recording, is labour-intensive. Additionally, the initial data gathering requires competent interviewers. According to Yauch and Steudel (2003), using a quantitative survey approach has two main benefits. Firstly, it is quick to administer and assess. You can administer the survey quickly without visiting the organisation personally. This approach provides numerical data for comparing organisations or groups and determining the degree of agreement or disagreement among respondents. Neuman (2006) asserts that quantitative research significantly outperforms first-method research by producing results with broad applicability. Finally, advocates of mixed methods research believe that it serves much more comprehensive research objectives than qualitative or quantitative research alone.

3.2. Justification for Choosing a Quantitative Approach for This Research

The positivist research philosophy, which is based on the idea of objective reality, stresses using numbers and statistics to establish general rules and connections between causes. Interpretivism, on the other hand, differs from positivism. Interpretivism recognises the importance of subjectivity and focusses on understanding the meanings and interpretations that people give things. Ørngreen and Levinsen (2017) prefer qualitative methods like interviews and observations. According to Burton and Bartlett (2006), these are the two major philosophies that social scientists apply. Morcol and Ivanova (2010) argue that the long-standing argument about method selection and the best appropriate philosophical viewpoint continues. The current study used quantitative and statistical analytic methods to select positivist philosophy. The research did not include interpretivist, pragmatist, or other philosophies. According to the study's nature, positivist philosophy is appropriate for the investigation.

Social studies research can be inductive or deductive, depending on the researcher's expertise and interests. According to Haradhan (2018), the purpose of inductive research is to draw theoretical conclusions and patterns from the evidence of the observed data. In comparison,

deductive research uses fresh empirical evidence to test theories' established notions and patterns (Trochim, 2006). We also refer to it as theory-testing or deductive research. Theory testing entails not only evaluating theories but also refining, expanding, and improving them. Figure 3.1 highlights the complementary nature of inductive and deductive research methods.

Figure 3. 1 The Research Cycle

Even so, deductive and inductive investigations are equally vital to the progress of knowledge. Deductive research is more effective when multiple competing theories about the same phenomenon exist, and researchers want to determine which theory performs better and under what conditions. Based on the preceding discussion, it is clear that the quantitative method is better suited for this investigation. This is because the research's primary objective is to investigate the connections between digital technologies, customer satisfaction, and service quality in Pakistani courier services. Before the investigation, we use the specific factors to build a conceptual model and often report the findings quantitatively.

Cooper and Schindler (2003) proposed categorizing various research strategies into case study, action, experimental, survey, interview, and systematic literature reviews. The current study uses a survey approach. Sekaran & Bougie (2011) highlighted that when a researcher wants to acquire feedback from respondents on a particular scenario, they employ the survey method to obtain primary data. According to Zikmund et al., (2012), survey research offers a quick and precise evaluation and information about a specific study population. Furthermore, survey research with questionnaires is less expensive and more straightforward than secondary data collection, interviewing, and observation—especially when gathering information from a sizable sample.

As a result, a survey that confirms multiple things simultaneously, evaluates various variables,

and tests numerous hypotheses is appropriate for gathering responses from courier company customers in Pakistan. Also, the survey or quantitative method is the most common way to get information for similar or related studies on customer satisfaction (Oliva et al., 1992; Hanif et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2011; Luan-Thanh, 2024).

3.3. Population and Sample

The term "population" refers to the total group of individuals, events, or objects studied in the study (Cavana et al., 2001). Zikmund et al., (2012) also explained that the group to which the study's conclusions can be broadly applied is known as the target population. A comprehensive literature review found that most research in Pakistan's service industries focused on telecom and food delivery rather than courier services. Furthermore, only a few studies have examined consumer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. Therefore, the study focused on private businesses operating in Pakistan's courier industry. In Pakistan, four prominent local courier firms have parcel booking offices. These include TCS, LCS, M&P, and Call Courier. The study's target population consisted of walk-in customers of Pakistani courier companies.

Prior research has regarded customers as suitable respondents for measuring customer satisfaction, service quality, and the influence of digital technologies (Oliva et al., 1992; Willard, 2000; Irshad et al., 2022; Hanif et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2011; Luan-Thanh, 2024; Hilaluddin and Cheng, 2014; Farooqui and Alwi, 2019; Jain and Gupta, 2004; Al Awadhia et al., 2021; Mosahab et al., 2010; Alasadee and Alfatlawi, 2023). Furthermore, these individuals were the most suitable respondents for the investigated variables. Previous researchers selected customers as participants for the same scales used in this study (Hunter & Garnefeld, 2008; Zouari & Abdelhedi, 2021; Md. Ariff et al., 2012). Thus, this study received customers' feedback regarding the research variables. We asked respondents to participate in survey questions based on their experiences. The data collection for this research began after the second week of December 2022 and concluded within a month. There were 466 customers who filled out the questionnaire.

3.4. Sampling Method

For this investigation, the sampling method outlines the sample size calculation and procedure.

3.4.1. Strategies for Sampling

We can classify sampling designs as either probability or non-probability (Robson, 2002; Sekaran, 2003; Malhotra, 2008). Sekaran (2003) asserts that probability sampling guarantees the selection

of population elements through a recognisable random process. Non-probability sampling establishes that there is no known chance of selecting certain population members as study subjects. Additionally, a multistage sampling process can use a combination of probability and non-probability sampling procedures at various points along the sample plan. For the present study, simple random sampling was considered. The study provided equal opportunities for all respondents to participate in the collection process. The researcher visited the booking offices of the Lahore-based courier companies and distributed the questionnaire to their walk-in customers.

3.4.2. Sample Size

Lacan & Fink (2002) define the sample size as the number of units required to yield reliable results. People typically choose sampling because it is practical for gathering data from all members of the population. According to Gay and Diehl (1992), selecting the appropriate sample size is essential for generalisations. While researchers disagree on sample size, Pallant (2013) demonstrated that larger samples more accurately reflect the population. There are two primary criteria for calculating sample size. Mitchell (1993) proposed the first criterion, which depends on the statistical technique. Sekaran (2003) advocated that the second criterion for choosing a sample size be based on the overall population. Mitchell (1993) asserts that we still need to determine the ideal sample size for the structural equation modelling technique. There are two criteria that are most commonly used: in multivariate studies, a sample size of ten times the number of variables is usually needed (Curran-Everett et al., 1998), and structural equation modelling (SEM) requires at least 200 samples.

Therefore, we recommended a minimum sample size of 200 answers for the study to accurately detect the genuine effect among the participants. Small sample sizes can lead to incorrect correlation coefficients, defeating the study's objectives. Large sample sizes typically generate statistically meaningful results (Pallant, 2013). For sample size, Glenn (1992) provided two tables (1 and 2).

Table 3. 1 Glenn Table 1: Sample Size for $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ Precision Levels, where the confidence level is 95% and $P = 0.5$.

Size of Population	Sample Size (n) for precision (e)	
	$\pm 5\%$	$\pm 10\%$
500	222	83
1000	286	91
2000	333	95
3000	353	97
4000	364	98
5000	370	98
7000	378	99
9000	383	99
10000	385	99
15000	390	99
20000	392	100
25000	394	100
50000	397	100
100000	398	100
>100000	400	100

Table 3. 2 . Glenn Table 2 Sample Size for $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ Precision Levels, where the confidence level is 95% and $p = 0.5$.

Size of Population	Sample Size (n) for precision (e)	
	$\pm 5\%$	$\pm 10\%$
100	81	51
125	96	56
150	110	61
200	134	67
250	154	72
300	172	76
350	187	78
400	201	81
450	212	82

To obtain responses, the present study successfully sampled 467 out of 600 courier customers. Due to Lahore's high population, the researcher used Glenn's (1992) Table 1 criteria to select a sample size of 467 respondents. The degree of confidence is 90%, and the customer's response to the questionnaire is 77.83% out of 600 attempts at responding. This sample size also satisfied the first requirement previously mentioned. Secondly, the researcher focused on courier customers who visit the booking offices of courier companies to ship their parcels. There is no need to distribute a questionnaire to a large or diversified population in Lahore solely to gather responses from courier customers, as this would have been an expensive, time-consuming, and inaccurate method of selecting the sample size. For the respondents, the researcher used simple and understandable vocabulary in the questionnaire. The respondents provided answers in English.

For the current research, simple random sampling was deemed suitable to provide each walk-in customer of Lahore-based courier booking offices an equal opportunity to be chosen, thereby reducing sampling bias and increasing the sample's representativeness. This probability technique was suitable to collect varied customer opinions, considering the large footfall and mix of customer types at these offices. The study participants were customers who had experienced the use of courier services and engaged with digital interfaces, for instance, tracking apps, SMS alerts, or automated customer care software. The way samples were chosen made sure that the respondents had relevant experience in key areas—how quickly they got responses, how accurate the services were, and how effective the digital technologies were.

After completing their transactions at various courier booking offices, customers were randomly selected and asked to participate in the survey. Great care was taken to confirm that participation was purely voluntary, and this was done through open and clear explanation of the aim of the study, as well as assurance of the confidentiality of their answers. Further, the procedure involved seeking informed consent, all of which was conducted in strict adherence to set ethical guidelines to guarantee the respect and protection of the participants.

3.4.3. Data Collections

The study examined the correlation between digital technologies, customer satisfaction, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, as well as the mediating role of these factors. The investigation's nature necessitates the use of a survey instrument. Therefore, we specifically

designed a self-administered questionnaire for this research. There are diverse types of self-administered surveys, e.g., online, self-distributed, and through the mail. Data was gathered using a method that involved the utilization of a structured questionnaire, which was self-administered and specifically targeted for customer feedback. The questionnaire was administered personally to booking offices in Lahore, where the target was walk-in customers who were chosen randomly from among the population available. The respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire as soon as they had received their service on the premises, as this approach supported the gathering of accurate and timely feedback regarding the respondents' experiences. The design of the questionnaire was based on the dimensions of SERVQUAL—i.e., responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency—which consisted of validated items that had been utilized and that precisely targeted the area of courier services.

Sekaran & Bougie (2011) also clarified that a questionnaire individually provided by the researcher to the respondents aids in building greater trust with them during the survey introduction. The researcher rejected other self-administered questionnaire methods due to the lack of knowledge about the respondents' true identities, addresses, emails, or phone numbers. We chose this method to target a specific audience of courier customers. Other obvious benefits of self-administered surveys include their low distribution costs, as well as the accessibility and affordability of hardware and software. To ascertain that the instrument is efficient and reliable in its operations, a pilot survey was conducted. The pilot survey was conducted with 40 participants who provided valuable information and recommendations, playing a significant role in the testing and, therefore, the instrumentation development.

3.5. Questionnaire Design

Creswell (2013) asserts that measuring the variables can achieve an accurate description of the unique characteristics of the study's relevant variables. After agreeing on the sampling strategy and research design, the next step involved deciding theoretically and practically how to assess the critical variables in the study. We formulated questions for critical variables like digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction based on previous research studies that examined similar variables. A well-designed questionnaire leads to better data collection and precise conclusions. As such, the effectiveness of a research study depends critically on the questionnaire's design.

The first page of the instrument served as a cover letter, summarising the research purpose (Sudman & Bradburn, 1982) and providing the researcher's address and institution. The questionnaire design is based on Dillman's (1978) technique, which contains a cover letter, an instruction sheet, and the survey instrument. We divided the self-administered questionnaire into two separate sections. In the first section, the questionnaire gathered primary data from the respondents, e.g., gender and education. Furthermore, the survey investigated the use of courier services, the nature and frequency of shipments, and the reservation team's behaviour. The second section of the survey asked questions about digital technologies, customer satisfaction, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. This section consists of the five main questions, including subquestions regarding the constructs of the conceptual framework.

3.5.1. Scale of Research

Since 1932, users have debated the reliability and validity of the Likert scale and its number of points (Colman et al., 1997). Matell and Jacoby (1971) assert that each number has its advantages and disadvantages. According to Lee and Soutar (2010), the Likert scale is the most common tool for quantitative data collection. Marketing research primarily uses the Likert scale, particularly the 7-point scale, preferring it over the 5-point scale due to its ability to allow for greater discrimination and subtle variations among individuals. According to the constructs and item selection, a 7-point scale may outperform a 5-point scale regarding survey reliability (Chang, 1994). The 7-point scale offers a broader range of choices, which increases the likelihood of aligning with people's objective realities (Cox, 1980). We operationalised each component of this thesis using a 7-point Likert scale, which ranges from 1 (strongly disagreeing) to 7 (strongly agreeing). We chose the overall Likert scale based on the assumption that it is simple and quick to respond to.

3.6. Variable Measurement

The current study collected data using a previously tested, reliable, and validated self-administered questionnaire. To achieve research objectives, the researcher adapted scales from previous studies. Table 3.3 provides details about the research instrument. The data collection instrument used a 7-point Likert scale.

Table 3. 3 Summary of Variable Measures

Variables	Source	No. of Items
Customer Satisfaction	Adapted from Hunter & Garnefeld (2008)	(05)
Service Quality		(12)
Responsiveness	Adapted from Md. Ariff et al., (2012)	04
Accuracy	Adapted from Md. Ariff et al., (2012)	04
Efficiency	Adapted from Md. Ariff et al., (2012)	04
Digital Technologies	Adapted from (Zouari & Abdelhedi, 2021; Md. Ariff et al., (2012)	(05)

3.6.1. Scale for Customer Satisfaction

We adapted a five-item scale from Hunter & Garnefeld (2008) to measure customer satisfaction (Appendix 2). These items include service satisfaction, meeting expectations, a positive experience, trust in the company, and recommendations to friends and family. We measured them using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 signifies strongly disagree and 7 indicates strongly agree.

3.6.2. Scale for Service Quality Components

3.6.2.1. Responsiveness

We adapted a four-item scale from Md. Ariff et al. (2012) to measure responsiveness (Appendix 2). The items include service accessibility, representative availability, prompt response to queries, and solutions. We measured these items using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 signifies strongly disagree and 7 indicates strongly agree.

3.6.2.2. Accuracy

We adapted a six-item scale from Md. Ariff et al. (2012) and Zouari & Abdelhedi (2021) to measure the accuracy (Appendix 2). These items include parcel delivery on a specified schedule, delivery modification facilities, parcel delivery to the correct person, exact proof of delivery, parcel condition, and a satisfactory solution in case of any issue. We measured these items using

a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 signifies strongly disagree and 7 indicates strongly agree.

3.6.2.3. Efficiency

We adapted a four-item scale from Md. Ariff et al. (2012) to measure the efficiency (Appendix 2). These items encompass a user-friendly tracking interface, the efficiency of web interfaces in service delivery, the availability of tracking services, and the ability to quickly track shipment status through tracking user interfaces. We measured these items using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 signifies strongly disagree and 7 indicates strongly agree.

3.6.3. Scale for Digital Technologies

We adapted a five-item scale from Zouari & Abdelhedi (2021) and Md. Ariff et al. (2012) to measure digital technologies (Appendix 2). These items include an online parcel management service, a digital payment solution, a mobile parcel management app, a social media presence to respond to queries, and digital assistance. We measured these items using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 signifies strongly disagree and 7 indicates strongly agree.

3.7. Validation of the Instrument

Instrument validation is the process of ensuring an instrument accurately measures what it intends to measure. Pretest and pilot testing verified the instrument's validity before the study gathered large amounts of data.

3.7.1. Pretest

According to Churchill and Iacobucci (2006), pretesting is critical before undertaking pilot testing to ensure the development of a suitable questionnaire. Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) state that the instrument's pre-testing consists of three steps. Initially, a pretest aids in identifying difficult-to-understand questions. It also facilitates the comprehension and expression of the researcher's purpose. Finally, pre-testing helps spot ambiguous or inappropriate acronyms, double-barreled or deceptive questions, and questions that shouldn't be repeated. According to Rubio et al., (2003), determining proper content validity (CV) is an important initial step in developing measurement instruments. According to Thorndike and Thorndike-Christ (2014), content validity is the relationship between the test's content and the measured construct. Rubio et al. (2003) suggest that researchers conducting content validation should receive constructive input to develop measuring instruments. Once completed, the input serves as the foundation for

rewriting assessments or items for pilot research.

Initially, a study instrument was provided to specialists, including Ph.D.-qualified academicians from the associated subject, language experts, and courier industry managers, for recommendations on item wording to ensure face and content validity. Specialists' advice led to an update of the questionnaire. Experts in the relevant sector approved the questionnaire's contents because the characteristics examined in this research are associated with digital technologies, customer satisfaction, and service quality.

3.7.2. Pilot Test

Moser & Kalton (1992) say piloting is the 'dress rehearsal.' Creswell (2013) claims that a pilot study makes examining the instrument's items easier for biases, mistakes, omissions, and internal consistency. Trochim & Donnelly (2006) suggest that a pilot research study will help enhance the format and substance of the questionnaire. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2011), conducting pilot research might save time and money. Furthermore, assessing the questionnaire's reliability contributes to improving its items (Nor, 2005). Ghazali (2011) defined reliability as the degree of consistency of a scale used to measure hidden variables.

According to previous research, an effective research design is essential. According to Rahal et al., (2004), a pilot study should be conducted to verify that an effective instrument has been developed, as surveys and instruments with poor design are likely to produce little-valued data. We perform an analysis on the overall dynamics of the survey and arrange the questions in the anticipated order they will appear on the final questionnaire. Sekaran & Bougie (2011) recommend conducting a pilot research test to test the reliability of a measure before performing the final questionnaire.

In the present research, Cronbach's alpha (1951) was employed to determine the internal consistency reliability of the questionnaire items that capture responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. The reason for employing this Cronbach's alpha is that it has been universally accepted as a valid measure of the degree of relatedness of a group of items as a whole. The method ensures that the items included in each construct measure the same underlying phenomenon consistently. Since the research used multi-item scales designed for the SERVQUAL factors, it was important to confirm that the items were consistent with each other to ensure the scales were reliable for Pakistani courier services. According to Table 3.4, a value of Cronbach's alpha is

considered acceptable and perfectly correlated if it is closer to 1, unacceptable if it is less than 0.50, and no correlation if it is less than 0.50.

Table 3. 4 . Cronbach's Alpha values

Cronbach's alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.90$	Excellent
$0.90 > \alpha \geq 0.80$	Good
$0.80 > \alpha \geq 0.70$	Acceptable
$0.70 > \alpha \geq 0.60$	Questionable
$0.60 > \alpha \geq 0.50$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.50$	Unacceptable

Source: George (2003).

We first gave the pilot participants the same survey as the main one. The 40 customers in this study participated in a pilot survey to assess the instrument's reliability. Before distributing the completed questionnaire to the targeted respondents, we had to determine the size of the sampling frame, units, and elements. The pilot research results contributed a few improvements to the questionnaire. We compiled the pilot research data using SPSS. Table 3.5 indicates the reliability of the questionnaire items used in the pilot survey.

Table 3. 5 Current Research Pilot Survey Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Customer Satisfaction	0.951	05
Responsiveness	0.862	04
Accuracy	0.886	04
Efficiency	0.897	04
Digital Technologies	0.876	05

3.8. Data Analysis

The primary objective of this research is to investigate how digital technologies impact customer satisfaction via responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. We addressed the research questions and tested the hypothesis through statistical analysis of the data. This study used a quantitative technique. Therefore, we conducted the statistical analysis using SPSS 26 and SmartPLS 3.0. Social science researchers frequently employ these acceptable statistical tools. This study examined the link between independent, mediating, and dependent variables, focussing on

causal relations among variables. The data collection throughout a predetermined time frame makes the study cross-sectional. As suggested by Sekaran & Bougie (2011), this study examined the link based on causal relations; a cross-sectional study would be appropriate in this situation.

3.9. Data Screening

This is unavoidable because researchers may encounter data issues during the analysis, failing or producing biased results. According to Johnson and McClure (2004), conducting data analysis would be pointless if the results proposed unclear answers. Hair et al., (2010) also suggest that data screening is crucial for identifying violations of basic assumptions while using multivariate techniques. Data screening is a vital part of making sure that field survey data is reliable so that it can stand up to the tough tests and analyses that are needed to answer the research questions. We structure the stages of data screening as follows:

3.10. Missing Data Analysis

Researchers may encounter challenges while analysing the missing data. According to Little & Rubin (2014), this issue arises due to the respondents' indifference, lack of interest, and laziness. As a result, any missing data leads to two primary issues. Initially, it diminishes a statistical test's capacity to identify a correlation within a dataset. Biases may also surface at any point during the analytical process. There are various methods available for dealing with biases. According to statistical specialists, the listwise deletion technique is the most suitable approach for handling missing values. Henseler et al., (2014) state that when there are less than 5% missing values per item, the missing values should be switched using the mean. On the other hand, Hair et al., (2006) recommend that mean imputation can be used to impute missing data that is less than 10% missing. As a result, the current study used the median imputation method to impute missing values.

3.11. Multi-Collinearity Analysis

Strong links between the independent variables are known as multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2010; Tabachnik & Fidell, 2013; Pallant, 2013). According to Frank (2001), multicollinearity can make it difficult to determine which factors are best suited for predicting or understanding a statistical model's response variable. Such an approach can lead to skewed or false results. Furthermore, a high level of multi-collinearity ($r=0.9$ and above) amongst the independent variables tends to

raise the Standard Error (SE) (Pallant, 2007). Multicollinearity is one of the contradictions in structural equation modelling's assumptions. Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) are popular statistical tests for detecting multicollinearity. A high VIF value indicates that independent variables are more likely to be multicollinear. According to the general VIF criterion, a variable is considered extremely multicollinear if its VIF value is 10 or more. Pallant (2007) states that a VIF value greater than 5 indicates multicollinearity. On the other hand, when the tolerance approaches close to zero, it means that there is a lot of multicollinearity between the independent variables (Gujarati, 2009).

3.12. Structural Equation Modelling

Research data analysis and outcome interpretation can be complicated. Conventional statistical data analysis methods are relatively rigid, assume error-free measurement, and specify default models. Structural equation modelling, on the other hand, necessitates a model based on theory and research. This investigation employed a variance-based structural equation modelling and used SmartPLS software for data analysis.

According to Hoyle (1995), structural equation modelling is a thorough statistical method for examining theories regarding relationships between dependent and independent variables. Smart PLS is widely used in most social science investigations and offers many benefits. Structural equation modelling restricts the types of relations it can specify and lacks a default model. To establish a structural equation model, researchers must first identify the relationships and provide theory or research to support their hypotheses. Researchers can use structural equation modelling to determine the limitations of their measurements and solve multicollinearity issues. Additionally, as this study does, Smart PLS works better than other software, primarily when mediators are used to examine the variables' indirect effects (Hair et al., 2014). Furthermore, a literature review revealed that the most recent research on customer satisfaction (Irshad et al., 2022; Martinez de Miguel et al., 2022) used PLS-SEM for data analysis. As a result, the optimal application for this investigation was Smart PLS-SEM.

Jöreskog (1976) argues that structural equation modelling has long emerged as a primary statistical tool in social science research. According to Hershberger (2003), social scientists began to give it more thought and acceptance in the late 1990s. According to Hair et al., (2006), structural equation modelling is also significant in other fields, such as the behavioural and social

sciences, because it creates theories and can provide quantitative methods to address various research topics. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2001), structural equation modelling is a suitable method for analysing independent variables in combination with dependent ones. Structural equation modelling helps measure indirect and direct relationships between independent and dependent variables by utilising mediating variables. This research employed structural equation modelling because of the inclusion of independent, dependent, and mediating variables. According to Hair et al., (2006), structural equation modelling is especially significant for social science research because it offers an alternative viewpoint for identifying various models in the social sciences and complements various analytical and multivariate approaches such as factor analysis and regression analysis. Thus, the current study successfully used structural equation modelling to perform unidimensionality, validity, and reliability tests.

3.13. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) Stages

In structural equation modelling, measurement and structural models are two key components. The measurement model's purpose is to validate the measurement theory's construction. Furthermore, the first step involves evaluating the measurement model using the initial and end measurement models. The structure model is the second-most critical component of structural equation modelling. This method uses path diagrams to visualise causal relationships between variables with arrows representing hypothesised relationships. The second stage evaluates the structural model in preparation for testing the hypothesis.

3.13.1. Measurement Model

In the first phase of structural equation modelling, we analyse the measurement model. We use a measurement model to evaluate the factor loading of each construct. Moreover, it assesses the constructs' validity and reliability (Hair et al., 2014). The reliability and validity of measures are crucial in determining the relationship between constructs. The adequacy of the measurement model can be tested by considering convergent and discriminant validity (DV).

3.13.2. Convergent Validity

According to Henseler et al., (2009), convergent validity (CVL) occurs when two measures of the same construct that are theoretically connected are actually related. According to Hair et al., (2010), it indicates how well the measures of the same construct correlate. As Fornell and Lacker

(1981) and Henseler et al. (2009) say, convergent validity is linked to the average variance extracted (AVE), factor loadings (FL), and composite reliability (CR). Henseler et al. (2009) use average variance extraction with a standard of 0.50 or above to determine convergence in construct measures. Composite reliability has a standard value greater than 0.70. Examining whether every item significantly loads on a construct where the factor loading exceeds 0.60 is crucial (Hair et al., 2010).

3.13.3. Discriminant Validity

According to Hair et al., (2014), discriminant validity refers to how dissimilar one construct is from another. To put it another way, these are measurements of unconnected concepts. According to Rasli (2006), when it comes to discriminant validity, there are no cross-loadings of responses about latent constructs. In addition, when the correlation of independent constructs is greater than 0.85, discriminant validity is compromised (Cooper and Schindler, 2011). The discriminant validity should have an average variance extracted that is greater than the interconstruct correlation value. According to Hair et al., (2014), the most frequent approach to estimating discriminant validity is the Fornell-Larcker criteria. Furthermore, the cross-loading examination approach appears to be more straightforward. Other constructs in the study demonstrate some discriminant validity. As such, based on the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the diagonal values should be greater than the different values in their corresponding rows (Hair et al., 2013). The term "cross-loadings" refers to the requirement for a factor loading to exceed that of another construct FL.

3.14. Quality Criteria

Two criteria for the validity of the measurement model through SmartPLS are the coefficient of Determination (R^2) and Effect Size (f^2).

3.14.1. Coefficient of Determination

According to Henseler et al., (2014), the coefficient of determination is the most frequent method for measuring model evaluation. Table 3.6 demonstrates that a higher (R^2) value denotes a better model.

Table 3. 6 Threshold levels of Values for R2

	Range	Comments
R² Values	0.25	Weak
	0.50	Moderate
	0.75 and above	Good

Source: Hair et al., (2014)

3.14.2. Effect Size

The next criterion for analysing any model would be the effect of size. f^2 . After the mediator, we usually assess the effect of size based on the coefficient of determination (Henseler et al., 2014). Cohen (1988) proposed 0.02, 0.14, and 0.35 as the least, moderate, and maximum effects, respectively.

Table 3. 7 Threshold levels of values for f^2

	Range	Comments
f^2 Values	0.02 to 0.14	Least Effect
	0.15 to 0.34	Moderate Effect
	>0.35	Maximum Effect

Source: Cohen (1988)

3.15. Structural Model Assessment

SmartPLS uses three criteria to evaluate the structural model and test the hypothesis. Thus, the criteria would be the bootstrap confidence interval, T-statistics, and p-value “significance of the path”. Hair et al., (2013) state that once the requirements of the structural model are met, the path coefficient should be checked so that it will ensure whether there is indeed an influence of the exogenous construct on the endogenous construct or vice versa.

Table 3. 8 Path Analysis Significance Levels

Criteria	Significant	Non-Significant
P-value significance	Less than 0.05	More than 0.05
T-Statistics	More than 1.96	Less than 1.96
Bootstrapped Confidence Interval	No nonzero value in the range	A nonzero value in the range

Source: Cohen (1988)

Table 3.8 represents the threshold values. This will indicate a significant path if the p-value is less than 0.05, and vice versa, that there is a non-significant path if the p-value is greater than 0.05. Likewise, there will be a significant path if the T-statistics is greater than 1.96; vice versa, there is a non-significant path if the T-statistics is less than 1.96. Similarly, the bootstrapped courier industry should not contain any zero values within the range of 2.5% to 97.5%. It should be either all negative or all positive. Any path that includes a zero value is considered non-significant. We assess structural models to test research hypotheses, and this research follows the same approach. Chapter 4 explains the in-depth analysis.

3.16. Assessment of the Mediating Effect

The current study used the Preacher and Hayes (2008) technique for examining the mediation hypotheses and determining the mediation effect of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency that occurred in the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. This methodology therefore follows two recommendations: the bootstrapping method by Preacher and Hayes (2008) and the first product coefficient approach by MacKinnon et al., (2004).

According to Hoyle & Robinson (2004), the Causal Steps Strategy and the Serial Approach are two methods for evaluating mediation. There are different ways to do mediation analyses, such as the Sobel test (Sobel, 1982), the distribution of the product approach (MacKinnon et al., 2004), and the bootstrapping approach (Preacher and Hayes, 2008). Rucker et al., (2011) suggested a bootstrapping method for mediation analysis. It produces an empirical representation of the sample's indirect effect distribution. MacKinnon et al., (2004) suggested expanding the product of coefficients test to consider the importance of both the overall indirect effect and the differences between specific indirect effects.

We applied the bootstrap technique in this study to determine the confidence intervals and

calculate the indirect effect on customer satisfaction. Because bootstrap analysis is not parametric, it is not possible to draw any conclusions about the sampling distribution of variables or their indirect effects. The process of bootstrapping involves extracting direct samples from the original sample to create numerous distinct data sets, known as bootstrap samples. Next, we estimate the indirect effects in each of these sets. Several prior studies have highlighted the benefits and rationales for using the bootstrapping approach to test the mediation effect. Bootstrapping techniques, according to Shrout and Bolger (2002), can address flaws by enabling the real-world testing of an indirect relationship effect. According to Preacher and Hayes (2008), there are thus no distributional assumptions about the sample, its outcome, or the indirect impact of bootstrapping.

3.17. Summary of Chapter 3

The research established how digital technologies influence responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. According to Morse et al., (2002), nowadays, the primary role of this quantitative approach is in testing the collected data to present answers to the study questions. Additionally, the service industry is included as one of the primary focus areas contributing to a nation's economic development; hence, this study has focused on the courier service industry in Pakistan. We used simple random sampling in the present study to select 460 respondents for data collection. The present chapter goes into detail about the research design. This chapter follows with a discussion on scale construction and data analysis procedures. Using the structural equation modelling method, we tested the suggested connections in the framework, including both direct and mediated connections.

CHAPTER 4: DATA ANALYSIS and FINDINGS

The present study tries to establish how digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency have influenced customer satisfaction, mediated by responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. It tries to contribute valuable insights for the development of digital technologies, service quality, and customer satisfaction in Pakistan. This chapter outlines the statistical analysis methods used to answer research questions.

Chapter four presents the results of the data analyses and the statistical conclusions drawn from the present study. In addition, this chapter contains four sections. The first one is an overview of data screening. Some of the results provided in the research include missing value analysis and demographic analysis. The second section concerns the sample demographics of the research study. The third section covers criteria regarding structural equation modelling, including the initial and final measurement models. The final section introduces the research structural model and the process of hypothesis testing. We analysed the data using SPSS 26 and SmartPLS 3.0.

4.1. Data Screening

According to Hair et al. (2010), data screening is crucial for identifying violations of basic assumptions while using multivariate techniques. The primary data analysis helps the researcher gain sufficient knowledge about the collected data. Prior to data analysis, we conduct data screening as a pre-cleaning stage. We evaluate the responses we identify as defective or rejected. Table 4.1 presents the results of the data screening.

Table 4. 1 Tabulation of Returned Survey Responses

Method of Survey: Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage %
Number of Questionnaires Distributed	600	100
Filled Questionnaires	508	84.66
Incomplete and Rejected Questionnaires	41	6.83
Usable and Error-Free Questionnaires for Analysis	467	77.83

The summary tabulation of the returned responses provides an overall and detailed account of the entire data collection process, as well as the effectiveness of distributing the questionnaires to the respondents. We distributed 600 questionnaires to potential respondents, of which 508 were returned and completed, resulting in a solid response rate of 84.66%. This high response rate expresses the participants' positive level of engagement with respect to their view of the survey's relevance, interest, and acceptance level concerning participation in it. When response rates reach this high level, it indicates that the survey itself was clear and simple to understand, as well as that the topics under discussion were really intriguing and highly important to those participating in it.

However, 6.83% of the returned questionnaires were incomplete or rejected. While this constitutes a small percentage, it is always beneficial to seek to understand why such rejections would occur. As recommended by Hair et al., (2010), questionnaires with more than 10% of the questions not completed were excluded from further processing of data or excluded in the first instance. Some factors that might have necessitated such an occurrence include a lack of interest in participating in the survey. By focussing on these areas, future survey research studies can ensure the completion of as many questionnaires as possible, thereby increasing the number of usable responses.

We discovered that 77.83% of the returned questionnaires were usable and error-free. This gave us a solid and reliable foundation for further data processing by leaving out the incomplete and rejected responses. This means that the 467 distributed questionnaires are suitable for

generating meaningful and insightful conclusions. The high percentage of usable responses in the sample set ensures that the results are a true reflection of the target population's wide range of opinions and actions. This aspect is essential for ensuring that the results obtained from the survey are both reliable and generalisable.

The survey's response rate demonstrated a high level of participant engagement, and the collected data was sufficient for a thorough analysis. Despite the low number of refused or incomplete surveys compared to the total responses, it is crucial to explore ways to enhance the survey design and distribution for future studies. Overall, the survey's quality and quantity of usable data guarantee its ability to offer advantageous suggestions for future research or practical applications.

4.2. Multicollinearity

Multicollinear variables are those that have strong and significant links between different variables in a statistical model (Hair et al. 2010; Tabachnik & Fidell 2013; Pallant 2013). Frank (2001) found that when there is multicollinearity, it can be challenging to tell which variables are best at predicting or describing a response variable in a statistical model. The results may also be biased or wrong. Furthermore, the SE tends to go up when there is a lot of multicollinearity ($r = 0.9$ or more) between the independent variables (Pallant, 2007). Multicollinearity is one of the contradictions in structural equation modeling's assumptions. Tolerance and VIF are popular statistical tests for detecting multicollinearity. A high VIF value indicates that independent variables are more likely to be multicollinear. According to the general VIF criterion, a variable is considered extremely multicollinear if its VIF value is 10 or more. Pallant (2007) defined multicollinearity as a VIF value greater than 5. On the other hand, when tolerance approaches close to zero, it means that there is a lot of multicollinearity between the independent variables (Gujarati, 2009).

Table 4. 2 Multicollinearity of the Independent Variables Based on Tolerance and VIF Values

Constructs	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Digital Technologies (DT)	0.456	2.195
Responsiveness (SQR)	0.479	2.086
Accuracy (SQA)	0.408	2.453
Efficiency (SQE)	0.499	2.004

Table 4.2 shows the tolerance and VIF values for each variable. We use the tolerance and the VIF as two crucial measures to conduct a multicollinearity analysis of independent variables such as digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. These two measures are vital in showing how independent variables might have a high level of correlation with one another. If there is a high correlation, this can have a significant impact on the reliability and validity of the regression model, given the reality of misleading results and interpretations.

The minimum VIF recorded in this analysis is 2.004, while the highest VIF, on the other extreme, has been 2.453 for all the studied constructs. These values lie well below the generally accepted cut-off point of 10, which raises caution concerning potential multicollinearity issues. A high VIF value, normally more than 10, infers that high multicollinearity—a situation where independent variables are highly linked—might be present. This makes it rather difficult to ascertain their impacts within the model environment. However, VIF values range from 1 to 5 (in this case) and indicate mild collinearity, not at levels that would cause significant problems in the analysis.

The tolerance values, however, are the reverse of VIF and range between 0.408 and 0.499. Values closer to zero establish higher multicollinearity, and although this is on the low side, the range suggests independence between the constructs. Consequently, we will conclude that the model shows no issues with multicollinearity because none of the tolerance values are close to zero.

In other words, both VIF and tolerance results suggest no significant problem of multicollinearity among independent variables. That is, the regression model should function reliably without multicollinearity distorting the coefficients. Digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency were reliable and not affected by multicollinearity, which increased our confidence in their relationships. These results show that the model can accurately predict how these variables will affect your outcomes.

4.3. Demographic Analysis

This part of the experience with courier service, which was required from the respondents of this study, includes gender, education level, use of courier service, kind of shipments, use of courier company, and parcel booking procedure. The discussion that follows focuses on the respondents and their characteristics. The present survey sample consisted of 467 walk-in customers of courier companies in operation in Lahore.

Table 4. 3 Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Items		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	397	85	85
	Female	69	14.8	99.8
	Prefer not to mention	1	.2	100
	Total	467	100	
Education	Matric (O-Level)	5	1.1	1.1
	Intermediate (A-Level)	14	3	4.1
	Graduate	201	43	47.1
	Postgraduate	239	51.2	98.3
	Prefer not to mention	8	1.7	100
	Total	467	100	
	Use of Courier Company	Once a month	129	27.6
More than once a month	223	47.8	75.4	
Once every three months	38	8.1	83.5	
Once every six months	77	16.5	100	

	Total	467	100	
Shipments Type	Letter	120	25.8	25.8
	Parcel	180	38.4	64.2
	Heavy Shipment over 5 KG	44	9.4	73.6
	All types of shipments	123	26.4	100
	Total	467	100	
Courier Company	TCS	158	33.8	33.8
	LCS	61	13.1	46.9
	M&P	71	15.1	62
	Pakistan Post	37	7.9	69.9
	Call Courier	42	9.0	78.9
	DHL	47	10.1	89
	UPS	11	2.3	91.3
	Any Other Company	40	8.7	100

	Total	467	100	
Shipment Booking	Manual Booking	94	20.2	20.2
	Computer-Based Booking	257	55	75.2
	Digital Device-Based Booking	116	24.8	100
<hr/>				
	Total	467	100	
<hr/>				

The demographic data fully describe the sample population. The gender distribution was biased toward men—85% of the total sample; 14.8% were female, and 0.2% of participants preferred not to reveal their gender. Demographic features of the sample involved a tally of the male-female divide. Respondents overwhelmingly indicated they were male, which is representative of the customer profile that was witnessed at courier booking offices where data was collected. However, an effort was made to include female respondents based on their availability at these premises to ensure representation in the sampling environment. A significant disparity in survey responses between men and women could possibly alter the interpretation of the results, particularly if the topic involves gender-sensitive opinions or behaviours. Such differences may be a key factor when analysing data based on gender.

The sample's educational background is highly educated. Most respondents fall into either the graduate (43%) or the postgraduate (51.2%) category, whereas Intermediate-A-Level and Matric-O-Level are very low, standing at 3% and 1.1%, respectively. The percentage remains elevated. The education level of the respondents suggests that the survey offers observations about a population that is likely more knowledgeable or familiar with the topics under study. This factor may significantly influence how respondents answer the various questions, particularly the technical ones.

When analysing the frequency of people using courier companies, it is evident that nearly half of the respondents, or 47.8%, use courier services more than once monthly. In comparison, only 27.6% report using such companies once every month. A third category consists of those who use courier services once every six months; these represent a 16.5% portion. The group of people who use courier services once every three months is very small, comprising only 8.1% of all

respondents. Thus, the very high percentage of those who use these services frequently underlines that the respondents are, in fact and truly, regular and habitual customers of courier services. This suggests that the wealth of extensive and varied experiences they have had with these courier services over time could likely inform any feedback they give or their levels of satisfaction with them.

In terms of the types of shipments handled, parcel deliveries were the most common, as indicated by the fact that 38.4% of all respondents identified this as their primary shipment type. Consequently, 25.8% of the respondents primarily handled letters, a common shipment type in the industry. Another 26.4% claimed to manage all types of shipments, indicating no restriction on the type they were involved with. Finally, 9.4% explicitly reported dealing with heavy shipments weighing more than 5 kg. The different shipment types show that the respondents have different wants and needs. These differences could stem from varying expectations or levels of satisfaction with the services they seek from courier companies.

In terms of courier service preference, TCS holds the top spot, with 33.8% of respondents indicating their preference for this service. Furthermore, M&P trails TCS in popularity, attracting the attention and trust of 15.1% of the respondents, while 13.1% prefer LCS. Other courier services operating in the market include well-known names such as Pakistan Post, DHL, Call Courier, UPS, etc. These companies serve a smaller segment of the market. This information suggests that, despite the current competition, TCS continues to have a loyal customer base among the respondents in this sample.

The method of shipment booking follows an unmistakable trend toward complete digitalisation. The majority of respondents (55%) would prefer computer-based booking, followed by 24.8% who prefer digital device-based booking. Only 20.2% of the respondents still use the manual mode of booking. This shift toward digital booking methods is reflective of broader trends in technology adoption. It may indicate that respondents value convenience and speed. Furthermore, respondents who were engaged in manual booking processes (i.e., bookings made via personal contact without the use of online platforms) were asked to fill in the self-administered questionnaire. In these instances, the questionnaire contained detailed instructions and, where deemed necessary, brief explanations by the researcher on how to interpret questions related to digital technology. This goal was to ensure that all respondents, including manual bookers, could engage sensibly with the survey questions and produce relevant

responses.

The demographic data indicate that courier service users are male. High levels of education and frequent use of courier services define the group. They strongly prefer digital booking methods, demonstrating that they are comfortable with technology. TCS is their preferred courier service company. These defining characteristics provide a background and contextual setting for interpreting the survey results, particularly their engagement with technologies and their expectations for the services offered. A limitation in the present study is the omission of age from the demographic variables of the sample population. Though other demographic variables the omission of age in the data captured makes it impossible to examine whether variations in customer satisfaction perceptions exist among different age groups. The limitation denies generalizability of results to various ages and should be considered in future research to enhance overall knowledge of customer satisfaction dynamics.

4.4. Results Evaluation in the PLS-SEM Path Model

The acronym PLS-SEM stands for Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling. The most important analytical advantage of PLS-SEM is its capacity to consider many dependent and independent variables. A few other significant benefits include the management of multicollinearity among explanatory variables, screening, and missing data. The model can provide correct and accurate predictions regarding the direct relationships among independent latent variables and their corresponding dependent variable(s). The present study used a variance-based approach to structural equation modelling with SmartPLS 3.0. We can categorize these models into two groups: measuring and structural ones. The PLS algorithm underpins a measurement model that accounts for both convergent and discriminant validity. The structural model is all about testing the hypothesis, whether to accept or reject it. In this study, we analysed the direct and mediated effects using PLS-SEM.

4.5. Measurement Model

The author has elaborated on the measurement model in this section. The initial step in PLS-SEM analysis is to examine the measurement model. The measurement model demonstrates that the survey items accurately measure the constructs they aim to assess, thereby ensuring their reliability and validity. In other words, only the items whose confirmatory factor analysis has

been confirmed will be looked into further within the measurement model to see if all the confirmed items from all constructs make a big difference to the study's proposed model. Ramayah et al., (2011) recommend that because this study uses reflective measurement models, the model be examined for discriminant and convergent validity, as well as internal consistency and reliability. In fact, the reliability and validity of the measurements are the only factors that define the complex nature of the relationship between different constructs. Usually, "validity and reliability analysis," the most important and significant part of the PLS-SEM in question refers to the measurement model investigation phase. In this regard, we thoroughly review and elaborate on all examinations and analyses. Furthermore, Figure 4.1 provides a comprehensive illustration of the discussed measurement model.

Figure 4. 1 Measurement Model

4.5.1. Construct Validity

Cronbach and Meehl (1955) developed the idea of construct validity (CONV) sixty-nine years ago. The best way to summarise those opinions was probably Anastasi's (1950) assertion that "it is only as a measure of a specifically defined criterion that a test can be objectively validated at all." It is "pure speculation" to assert that a test measures anything beyond its criterion. Brown (1996) says that to objectively measure a test's supposed or intended criteria, it must show both discriminant and convergent validity, which are two different types of validity. Convergent validity refers to the strong correlation between measures of the same construct, while discriminant validity refers to the degree of differentiation between a construct and another construct (Hair et al., 2014). According to Brown (1996), construct validity determines whether the selected measurements explain the scenario.

4.5.1.1. Convergent Validity

According to Henseler et al., (2009), convergent validity is the degree to which two measures of the same conceptually connected constructs are related. It considers the construct loadings together with the average variance extracted. Hair et al., (2014) suggest that the higher outer loading on a construct indicates that the associated indicators have much in common in average variance extracted or that the items used to measure the same concept agree. Convergent validity demonstrates a strong correlation with other tests measuring similar constructs. However, if more than 0.50 is the value of the average variance extracted from the construct, it can retain items (Henseler et al., 2009). An average variance extracted score of 0.50 is considered satisfactory. There is excellent convergent validity because the latent construct explains half of the variation in its indicators (Hair et al., 2014). Generally, if the extracted average variance is less than 0.5, the measurement items are likely to contain more measurement errors. For outer loading, a score of 0.700 or higher signifies a significant loading of all items on a specific construct. If the value falls below 0.7, we should remove the outer loading.

The first measurement model showed the factor loadings, composite reliability, and variance extracted for several important constructs that were needed for the analysis. These pieces of information reflect an important and comprehensive judgement about a model's validity and reliability, which are necessary for an overall assessment of model performance. In structural equation modelling, these metrics are crucial because they show how well the observed variables

match and correlate with the underlying latent constructs. This, in turn, affects how reliable the model's conclusions are. Table 4.5 shows the results of the initial measurement model.

Table 4. 4 Initial Measurement Model

Construct	Item Code	Factor Loading	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Digital Technologies	DT1	0.805	0.910	0.669
	DT2	0.771		
	DT3	0.806		
	DT4	0.847		
	DT5	0.856		
Responsiveness	SQR1	0.774	0.907	0.709
	SQR2	0.839		
	SQR3	0.900		
	SQR4	0.851		
Accuracy	SQA1	0.776	0.913	0.637
	SQA2	0.800		
	SQA3	0.807		
	SQA4	0.799		
	SQA5	0.788		
	SQA6	0.817		
Efficiency	SQE1	0.857	0.929	0.765
	SQE2	0.855		
	SQE3	0.886		
	SQE4	0.899		
Customer Satisfaction	CS1	0.920	0.962	0.835
	CS2	0.915		
	CS3	0.919		
	CS4	0.920		
	CS5	0.896		

It's clear that when it comes to digital technologies (DT), the loading ranges from 0.771 to 0.856, which means that there is a strong link between the items labelled DT1 through DT5 and the overall construct. Additionally, the overall reliability score for digital technologies is 0.910, which is significantly higher than the suggested general measure value of 0.7. This evidence shows that the components are consistent with each other. The extracted average variance is 0.669, indicating that the indicators for this construct account for more than half of the variance inherent in it. These values confirm that the items represent the digital technologies in question consistently and reliably.

The responsiveness (SQR) construct has yielded excellent results, as evidenced by loadings

ranging from 0.774 to 0.900. This range indicates a robust and significant relationship between the measured items and the responsiveness construct. We have calculated the composite reliability for the responsiveness construct to be 0.907, indicating the internal reliability of the items in this measurement. The extracted average variance stands at 0.709, once again surpassing the critical threshold of 0.5. This surpassing value signifies that the indicators effectively and adequately explain the variance present in the construct.

The relevant literature says that the factor loadings for the accuracy construct as measured by SQA are between 0.776 and 0.817. This means that there is a strong and reliable link between the different items and how they represent the construct. Furthermore, as calculated, the composite reliability score is 0.913, reinforcing internal consistency in relation to this construct. The average extracted variance of 0.637 shows that the indicators capture the total variance well enough for this analysis. This strongly supports the model's convergent validity for this particular construct.

The Efficiency (SQE) construct's results look similarly impressive, with factor loadings ranging between 0.855 and 0.899. This range indicates a very high level of correlation between the individual items and the overarching construct itself. The composite reliability for this construct is commendable at 0.929, indicating a high level of internal consistency among the measurements. This conclusion is also supported by the fact that the average variance extracted for SQE is 0.765, which shows that the indicators that go with it quite well explain a large part of the total variance. This finding further seals the overall reliability of the model in question.

The last aspect is customer satisfaction (CS), where the factor loadings are considerably high, ranging between 0.896 and 0.920. This large range essentially means a profoundly positive relationship between the items that constitute the construct and the concept itself. Additionally, the composite reliability of 0.962 shows that the measurement model has extremely high internal consistency; the items hang together. More importantly, the average extracted variance value is 0.835, which is significantly higher than the threshold level. This essentially satisfies the requirement that the construct's indicators better capture the true variance.

Overall, the measurement model exhibits excellent psychometric properties. All of the constructs have factor loadings that exceed the threshold, indicating a close relationship between the observed variables and their respective constructs. The values for composite reliability were all

above 0.9, revealing that the constructs were internally consistent. The indicators also show enough variation in each construct, as shown by average variance extracted values greater than 0.5 (Henseler et al., 2009). This analysis's findings demonstrate that the evaluated model produces strong and useful results for further analysis in future research projects.

4.5.1.2. Discriminant Validity

In addition, discriminant validity was considered the extent to which one construction varies. According to Hair et al., (2014), discriminant validity referred to how much a given instrument contained a genuinely different construct from every other one. It suggests that each model construct has its own logic. The most commonly used method for testing discriminant validity is the Fornell-Larcker criteria (Hair et al., 2014). Furthermore, Heselers et al. (2009) suggest using the more permissive method of examining cross-loadings. The current study tested the discriminant validity of the constructs using both criteria. According to Henseler et al., (2009), a construct holds discriminant validity if the square root of the average variance extracted value is more significant than its highest correlation with any other latent construct.

Hair et al., (2014) say that a latent construct meets the Fornell-Larcker criterion when its square root of average variance extracted is higher than its latent inter-construct correlation with another latent variable in the model. Meanwhile, cross-loadings represent a situation where the loadings on the associated construct are larger than those on the indicators' outer construct. Table 4.6 explains the Fornell-Larcker criteria for discriminant validity and cross-loading for all constructs. Table 4.6 shows the Fornell-Larcker criterion. It says that the square root of the average variance is less than the hidden correlation between that factor and any other hidden factor for each hidden factor in the model. This guarantees the construct's discriminant validity.

Table 4. 5 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Constructs	CS	DT	SQA	SQE	SQR
CS	0.914				
DT	0.729	0.818			
SQA	0.773	0.691	0.798		
SQE	0.623	0.591	0.643	0.875	
SQR	0.672	0.622	0.646	0.620	0.842

In terms of customer satisfaction, we calculated that the square root of the extracted average variance is 0.914. This is a lot stronger than the correlations between the other constructs, which are digital technologies (0.729), accuracy (0.773), efficiency (0.623), and responsiveness (0.672). The results make it clear that the customer satisfaction construct is discriminantly valid by showing that it is sufficiently different from the other variables that were studied. Additionally, the extracted average variance value is relatively high, indicating that the indicators accurately represent the customer satisfaction construct. It makes a clear and effective distinction from the other variables included in the study.

The average square root of the extracted variance for digital technologies is 0.818, surpassing the correlations with speed (0.622), accuracy (0.691), and effectiveness (0.591). This particular result helps explain how this specific construct, digital technologies, differs from the rest of the constructs within this model. This finding demonstrates that the tests employed to assess this concept have successfully incorporated an independent factor that remains unaffected by the other factors under investigation.

The accuracy construct also exhibits strong evidence of discriminant validity, as indicated by the square root of the average variance of 0.798. This is significantly higher than the correlation coefficients with the efficiency construct, which is 0.643, and the responsiveness construct, which correlates at 0.646. These figures demonstrate the accuracy construct's strong differentiation from the other constructs in the overall model. This feature is beneficial, as it limits the accuracy-focused indicators to measuring only a specific portion of the studied data, in contrast to the efficiency- and responsiveness-focused indicators.

Efficiency's square root of 0.875 surpasses its correlations with the other constructs, particularly responsiveness, which stands at 0.6. This high level of average variance extraction demonstrates that the efficiency construct differs from the other constructs in the model and captures its unique variances. Such a high discriminant validity level strengthens overall reliability in the model for the efficiency construct.

We determined that the square root of the extracted average variance was 0.842. This value is much higher than the different correlations. Responding plays a key role in keeping this value separate from the other model constructs. This finding further suggests that the responsiveness

construct measures another distinct and separate dimension within the larger model. We have also determined that the respective indicators of this specific construct align with the goals and definitions of responsiveness.

In summary, the results of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion show that the constructs in this model possess forceful discriminant validity. It is always the case that the square root of the average variance taken from each construct is greater than the correlations with other constructs. This technique makes sure that each variable in the model represents a different idea. A high level of discriminant validity shows how different each construct is and how to measure it using its indicators, making the model strong and reliable.

The table of cross-loadings serves as a useful tool, offering important details about the measurement of a specific item relative to other constructs. In a typical and functioning measurement model, items should load more on their respective constructs than on the other ones. That particular distinction provides the critical indicator of discriminant validity, ensuring that something measures what it should. Table 4.7 demonstrates that all cross-loadings are smaller than loadings on the associated construct, thereby supporting that conclusion. Loads on the associated construct are more significant than on the other construct for the indicators. The results of these tests support the discriminant validity of each construct.

Table 4. 6 Cross Loadings of the Items

	CS	DT	SQA	SQE	SQR
CS1	0.920	0.684	0.730	0.627	0.631
CS2	0.915	0.678	0.705	0.587	0.619
CS3	0.919	0.650	0.700	0.572	0.621
CS4	0.920	0.677	0.721	0.538	0.621
CS5	0.896	0.644	0.676	0.520	0.575
DT1	0.665	0.805	0.657	0.636	0.548
DT2	0.534	0.771	0.483	0.405	0.429

DT3	0.547	0.806	0.504	0.421	0.482
DT4	0.594	0.847	0.546	0.480	0.503
DT5	0.620	0.856	0.603	0.437	0.563
SQA1	0.632	0.496	0.776	0.518	0.564
SQA2	0.602	0.554	0.800	0.499	0.515
SQA3	0.602	0.521	0.807	0.529	0.493
SQA4	0.555	0.539	0.799	0.455	0.438
SQA5	0.624	0.510	0.788	0.544	0.493
SQA6	0.677	0.666	0.817	0.532	0.576
SQE1	0.523	0.471	0.530	0.857	0.509
SQE2	0.602	0.561	0.611	0.855	0.603
SQE3	0.518	0.506	0.552	0.886	0.516
SQE4	0.527	0.521	0.548	0.899	0.529
SQR1	0.551	0.464	0.519	0.555	0.774
SQR2	0.502	0.530	0.479	0.481	0.839
SQR3	0.625	0.560	0.577	0.541	0.900
SQR4	0.577	0.538	0.595	0.514	0.851

For instance, the customer satisfaction context consistently shows higher loads for items labelled CS1 through CS5, particularly when compared to other existing constructs. CS1 has a very high loading of 0.920 on the customer satisfaction construct, which is much higher than its loadings on other constructs like digital technologies, which are 0.684 for accuracy, 0.730 for efficiency, 0.627 for responsiveness, and so on. It's important to note that the above trend holds true for all items related to customer satisfaction. This again shows that these indicators are valid and reliable for measuring the customer satisfaction construct without significantly affecting the

measures of other constructs.

The digital technology construct itself had the most substantial loadings on items from DT1 to DT5. For instance, DT1 had a loading of 0.805 on the digital technology construct, substantially higher compared to its loadings on other constructs, such as customer satisfaction at 0.665 and accuracy at 0.657. The evidence strongly shows that the items measuring the digital technology construct are distinct and specific, confirming that they are valid and different from other constructs. The same pattern holds for accuracy, with all six items loading more on the accuracy construct than others. For example, SQA1 loads at 0.776 on accuracy but very low on customer satisfaction and efficiency. This pattern reinforces that the accuracy items measure a unique aspect of the data, distinct from the other constructs.

In terms of efficiency, the four distinct items labelled SQE1–SQE4 have relatively high loadings for what they should measure. For instance, SQE1 has a particularly high load of 0.857 on the efficiency itself, while it has a relatively low load on other related constructs. This system makes efficiency even more reliable and valid because the indicators in this framework only affect efficiency and don't affect responsiveness or customer satisfaction, which are related concepts.

Finally, there are responsiveness items ranging from SQR1 to SQR4, which also reflect strong and significant loadings on their respective constructs. For instance, SQR3 demonstrated an impressive loading of 0.900 on SQR, significantly higher than its loading on competing constructs like accuracy (0.577) or efficiency (0.541). The clear and large difference in loadings indicates that only the set of indicators that represent the responsiveness construct can measure it. The cross-loadings table indicates satisfactory discriminant validity for all the constructs. Every item loads more strongly on its construct than on any other, thereby supporting the idea that the set of indicators measures distinctly different and separate constructs. This degree of distinctiveness supports the robustness and reliability of the measurement model. The items uniquely and exclusively represent constructs like customer satisfaction, digital technologies, accuracy, efficiency, and responsiveness.

4.6. Structural Model

After validating the measurement model, also known as the outer model, for validity and reliability, the next step involves assessing the structural model, also known as the inner model. Hair et al., (2014) state that multicollinearity among explaining variables should be checked

before conducting the structural model. The researcher concluded that multicollinearity between the explanatory variables was not an issue after completing the VIF and tolerance. The results of Table 4.2 suggest that there is no multicollinearity in the structural model's exogenous variables. However, this research requires further examinations.

According to Hair et al., (2014), the steps would include the determination of the model's predictability and the relationships among the various constructs. In other words, we compare the structural model to the hypothesised relationship in the inner model. Figure 4.1 illustrates the measurement model in this study, including all independent, dependent, and mediating latent variables. The hypothesised relationships between constructs in this research are determined by three parameters: Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of endogenous constructs, Effect Size (f^2) and Path Coefficients.

4.6.1. Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

According to the (R^2) value, the appropriate model accounts for a significant portion of the variance in the dependent variables. Henseler et al., (2014) highlighted that the conceptual models are usually tested through the use of (R^2), which is the endogenous latent variable coefficient of determination. The higher the (R^2) value, the more predictive the structural model is. The primary goal of PLS-SEM is to achieve a greater (R^2) since it aims to explain the endogenous latent variable. For instance, Cohen (1988) argues that (R^2) values of 0.27, 0.13, and 0.02 indicate fair, average, and weak values, respectively. According to Hair et al., (2014), (R^2) varies from 0 to 1; values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 demonstrate good, moderate, or weak predictive accuracy. Table 4.8 displays the (R^2) values for endogenous constructs.

Table 4. 7 Coefficient of Determination (R^2) for Endogenous Constructs

Construct	(R^2)	(R^2) Adjusted
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	0.696	0.693
Accuracy (SQA)	0.477	0.476
Efficiency (SQE)	0.349	0.348
Responsiveness (SQR)	0.387	0.386

The R^2 value in the variable customer satisfaction is 0.696, indicating that the model can explain a sizeable 69.6% of the variance exhibited by customer satisfaction. This fairly high R^2 value

strongly indicates that the predictors considered in this model are quite effective and well-suited to explaining the variations within customer satisfaction. Moreover, the adjusted R^2 , which also measures the same aspect, stands at 0.693 and is almost equal to the R^2 value; this confirms the strength and robustness of the model. The result further demonstrates that adding more predictors did not specifically change or influence the model's performance in any significant manner.

In accuracy, the R^2 result is 0.477, which indicates that the model can explain 47.7% of the variance observed in accuracy. This result shows a moderate amount of explanatory power, which means that the model eventually explains the majority of the variation in accuracy. However, it remains plausible that other factors could still exert an influence on this construct. It has been found that the adjusted R^2 value is 0.476, which is satisfactorily close to the R^2 value. This closeness indicates that the model is still stable and well-calibrated when the number of predictors added to the analysis is considered.

The value of R^2 for the variable efficiency is 0.349. That implies that the model explains 34.9% of data variation. Therefore, the relatively low R^2 suggests that other unexplained factors or variables may be affecting efficiency. The model under scrutiny does not adequately reflect or encapsulate these factors. Nonetheless, the model's closeness to the adjusted R^2 , with a value of 0.348, indicates that it does not exhibit overfitting issues, making it more reliable. This result holds up well, even when considering the relatively low level of explanation the model has captured.

The R^2 of responsiveness is 0.387, meaning that the model explains about 38.7% of the variation occurring in responsiveness. This moderate result indicates that the model captures many significant influences that drive responsiveness, but it may not encompass all influencers and variables. Additionally, the adjusted R^2 is 0.386, which is very close to the original R^2 ; this favourable outcome indicates that the model is stable and does not suffer from overfitting issues, thereby enhancing the credibility of the results.

In sum, R^2 and adjusted R^2 present different explanatory strengths for the various constructs under scrutiny. Customer satisfaction stands out with a very high R^2 value, indicating that almost 70% of the variance in this construct is explained by the model. This large percentage indicates that customer satisfaction is, in fact, one of the best-explained constructs within the boundaries

of the overall model. Furthermore, accuracy did fairly well in terms of explanatory power, which means that it may supply useful information but isn't quite satisfactory enough for customers to be satisfied with this criterion. In contrast, both efficiency and responsiveness have lower levels of variance explained, though these are still within the acceptable range for their respective purposes. The close relationship between R^2 and adjusted R^2 across various constructs indicate well-defined, stable models without significant overfitting effects that could compromise reliability.

4.6.2. The Effect Size f^2

The second criterion with respect to the evaluation of any given model is the effect size (f^2). This study used the second criterion to evaluate the model's fitness, which involved examining the effect size of a predictor latent construct at the structural level and reviewing the (R^2) values of each endogenous construct. According to Henseler et al., (2014), the size effect is usually checked after estimating the coefficients of the endogenous constructs. First, it uses effect size (f^2) to determine whether the excluded construct has any substantive influence on the endogenous constructs. Second, the effect size (f^2) can be measured by increasing (R^2) relative to the proportion of variance of the endogenous latent variable that remains unexplained. Cohen (1988) devised a formula to determine how significant the exogenous construct's effect is. The formula says that 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 are the smallest, medium, and largest effects, respectively. Table 4.9 below presents the (f^2) value for each path.

Table 4. 8 Results for the Effect Size (f^2)

Construct	Digital Technologies (DT)	Customer Satisfaction (CS)
Digital Technologies (DT)		0.127
Accuracy (SQA)	0.913	0.221
Efficiency (SQE)	0.537	0.010
Responsiveness (SQR)	0.632	0.051

These results indicate that digital technologies significantly influence three constructs: responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Among these three effects, digital technologies have a

relatively high impact on accuracy, with an f^2 value of 0.913. That is, digital technologies play an important role in achieving service delivery accuracy. The significant impact of digital technologies on accuracy highlights the fundamental nature of digital technology implementation, which every organisation strives to achieve for accurate, efficient, and reliable service delivery.

The responsiveness score is also quite high, with an f^2 value of 0.632. The introduction of digital technologies has significantly enhanced responsiveness, enabling organisations to respond timely to customers' needs and external demands. Its large effect size indicates that digital technologies are beneficial enablers for improving operational responsiveness, which makes any organisation's ability to adapt to constantly changing conditions easier. This means that the effect size for efficiency is 0.537, falling within the medium-to-large effects range. Although it may seem insignificant compared to the impacts on accuracy and responsiveness, it confirms the influence of digital technologies on efficiency. The medium nature of the effect size here shows that digital technologies streamline processes by cutting down on waste and improving overall productivity, with technology playing a greater role in enhancing the performance of organisations.

The magnitudes of effects vary when considering how digital technologies, accuracy, efficiency, and responsiveness influence customer satisfaction. The effect sizes of digital technologies, accuracy, and responsiveness are relatively small to medium, standing at 0.127, 0.221, and 0.051, respectively. These findings indicate that customer satisfaction influences the aforementioned constructs, albeit partially and with less pronounced effects. Efficiency is a low-variance explainer of customer satisfaction, with an f^2 value of 0.010, indicating that efficiency is not a substantial determinant of customer satisfaction. Evidence suggests that while efficiency improvements may benefit internal processes, they do not directly impact customer satisfaction.

In summary, the findings indicate that digital technologies strongly and significantly impact constructs such as responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. However, their respective impact on customer satisfaction is modest in nature. Similarly, other constructs like responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency have a partial impact on customer satisfaction, with efficiency having the least effect.

4.7. Path Coefficients

In PLS-SEM, the path coefficient tells us how strong and important the links between latent constructs are. Thus, the estimates for the structural model relationships range from -1 to $+1$ standardized values. A coefficient closer to $+1$ would indicate a highly positive relationship, while a coefficient closer to -1 indicates a strongly negative relationship. Figure 4.2 illustrates the model's path coefficients. As shown in Table 4.8, the path coefficient for digital technologies to accuracy was the highest (0.692). Efficiency and customer satisfaction yielded a minimal value of 0.080.

4.7.1. Hypothesis Testing

One alternative interpretation of these path coefficients is the standardized Ordinary Least Square beta coefficients. We looked at how important the relationship was by using the PLS-SEM bootstrapping procedure to determine the empirical t-value for the path coefficients. Using the PLS-SEM bootstrapping procedure, we calculated the empirical t-value of the path coefficients. This helped us figure out how important the relationship was. This conceptual model enables researchers to study the relationship between digital technologies, service quality, and customer satisfaction. Table 4.10 provides a synopsis of the hypothesis testing. Figure 4.2 displays the structural model's outcomes.

Figure 4. 2 Structural Model

We first examine the direct correlations between the independent and dependent variables to evaluate the inner model. The current study provides ten hypotheses to test the relationship between the variables. **H1:** The hypothesised statement says that digital technologies have a positive effect on responsiveness. According to reports, the path coefficient for DT→SQR was 0.622, with a t-value of 17.503. This score is greater than the threshold value of 1.96 with an associated p-value of 0.000, which is considered significant at any value less than 0.05. The study's empirical results validated hypothesis H1, demonstrating a positive impact of digital technologies on responsiveness. Consequently, the study supported the positive correlation between digital technologies and responsiveness.

H2: The hypothesised proposition states that digital technologies have a positive effect on accuracy. According to reports, the path coefficient for DT→SQA was 0.691, with a t-value of 19.659. This score is greater than the threshold value of 1.96 with an associated p-value of 0.000, which is considered significant at any value less than 0.05. The study's empirical results validated hypothesis H2, demonstrating a positive impact of digital technologies on accuracy. Consequently, it validated the positive correlation between digital technologies and accuracy.

H3: The hypothesised proposition states that digital technologies have a positive effect on efficiency. According to reports, the path coefficient for DT→SQE was 0.591, with a t-value of 12.322. This score is greater than the threshold value of 1.96 with an associated p-value of 0.000, which is considered significant at any value less than 0.05. The empirical results obtained in this study indicated that hypothesis H3 was accepted and that digital technologies have a positive effect on efficiency. Consequently, it validated the positive correlation between digital technologies and efficiency.

H4: The hypothesised proposition states that digital technologies have a positive effect on customer satisfaction. The path coefficient for DT→CS was reportedly 0.291, with a t-value of 4.126. This value is greater than the threshold of 1.96, and the associated p-value of 0.000 indicates significance at any level below 0.05. The empirical results obtained in this study indicated that hypothesis H4 was accepted and that digital technologies have a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This study supports the positive correlation between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

H5: The hypothesised proposition states that responsiveness positively affects customer satisfaction. The path coefficient for SQR→CS was reportedly 0.180 with a t-value of 3.696. This

finding is greater than the threshold value of 1.96 with an associated p-value of 0.000, which is considered significant at any value less than 0.05. The study's empirical results validated hypothesis H5, demonstrating a positive impact of responsiveness on customer satisfaction. This study supports responsiveness by showing a positive correlation with customer satisfaction.

H6: The hypothesised proposition states that accuracy positively affects customer satisfaction. The path coefficient for SQA→CS was reportedly 0.406 with a t-value of 6.674. The result is greater than the threshold value of 1.96 with an associated p-value of 0.000, which is considered significant at any value less than 0.05. This study's empirical results validated hypothesis H6, demonstrating a positive correlation between accuracy and customer satisfaction. This study supports accuracy by showing a positive correlation with customer satisfaction.

H7: The hypothesised proposition states that efficiency positively affects customer satisfaction. The path coefficient for SQE→CS was reported to be 0.079, with a t-value of 1.248. This is less than the threshold value of 1.96 with the associated p-value of 0.212, which is considered insignificant at any value higher than 0.05. The empirical results obtained in this study indicated that hypothesis H7 was rejected and that efficiency has no effect on customer satisfaction. Therefore, we could not establish a relationship between efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Table 4. 9 Table of Hypothesis Testing Direct Relationships

Path	Path Coefficient	SE	T-Test	P-Values	2.5%	97.5%	Results
DT -> CS	0.291	0.070	4.126	0.000	0.151	0.425	Accepted
DT -> SQA	0.691	0.035	19.659	0.000	0.618	0.755	Accepted
DT -> SQE	0.591	0.048	12.322	0.000	0.493	0.680	Accepted
DT -> SQR	0.622	0.036	17.503	0.000	0.550	0.690	Accepted
SQA -> CS	0.406	0.061	6.674	0.000	0.285	0.523	Accepted
SQE -> CS	0.079	0.063	1.248	0.212	-0.042	0.206	Rejected
SQR -> CS	0.180	0.049	3.696	0.000	0.090	0.279	Accepted

DT=Digital Technologies, SQR=Responsiveness, SQA=Accuracy, SQE=Efficiency, CS=Customer Satisfaction

However, the results of hypothesis testing pointed out that digital technologies have a significant effect on accuracy, efficiency, and responsiveness, which in turn affects the improvement of customer satisfaction. While accuracy and responsiveness have a positive effect on customer satisfaction, this model reveals that efficiency cannot significantly affect it. These are important findings because they show that digital technologies and accuracy must be the focus of effective customer satisfaction.

4.8. Mediation Analysis

In this section, the researcher tries to test all hypotheses related to mediation in the structural model. One of the purposes of this study is to determine whether responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency play a mediating role in the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. As suggested by Nitzl et al., (2016), this was supplemented by indirect impact analysis approaches that assisted in explaining the breakdown aspects of service quality variables. Finally, we must verify the lower and higher confidence limits. According to Preacher and Hayes (2008), the mediation hypothesis is acceptable if it contains no zeros, but it may be rejected otherwise. It follows a two-stage approach, in which the first stage estimates all the direct relationships in two ways: without and with mediators. Through bootstrapping, the second

stage calculates all the indirect effects and their significance. In the second analysis order, the mediators were considered to have a potential indirect impact on the study.

According to hypothesis H8, responsiveness mediates between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. To test this hypothesis, the researcher calculated the direct effects without incorporating the mediator into the model. Figure 4.2 includes the direct effects from the mediation analysis output without specifying a mediator in the model.

The second stage of this approach involved calculating indirect effects for the model. It was hypothesised that H8: "Responsiveness mediates between digital technologies and customer satisfaction." Figure 4.2 also illustrates the model's outcomes, which include the mediator. Table 4.11 displays the findings of the mediation analysis. The path DT→SQR→CS had an indirect path coefficient of 0.112. The indirect path was tested using a bootstrap statistical method at 5000 iterations. The results indicated an indirect path with a t-value of 3.453 and a P-value of 0.001. This indicator means the indirect path is significant. The study accepted hypothesis H8 and concluded that responsiveness was the link between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

It was hypothesised that H9: "accuracy mediates between digital technologies and customer satisfaction." Figure 4.2 also illustrates the model's outcomes, which include the mediator. Table 4.11 displays the findings of the mediation analysis. The path DT→SQA→CS had an indirect path coefficient of 0.280. The indirect path was tested using a bootstrap statistical method at 5000 iterations. The results indicated an indirect path with a t-value of 5.985 and a P-value of 0.000. This indicator means the indirect path is significant. As a result, hypothesis H9 was accepted, and the study concluded that there was a correlation between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

It was hypothesised that "efficiency mediates between digital technologies and customer satisfaction." Figure 4.2 also illustrates the model's outcomes, which include the mediator. Table 4.11 displays the findings of the mediation analysis. The path DT→SQE→CS had an indirect path coefficient of 0.047. The indirect path was tested using a bootstrap statistical method at 5000 iterations. The results indicated an indirect path, with a t-value of 1.240 and a P-value of 0.215. This means the indirect path is insignificant. In contrast, the confidence limits include zero in both the upper and lower bounds. This breaches the third requirement set by Preacher and Hayes

(2008). As such, hypothesis H10 was rejected, and the study could not establish the efficient mediation between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.

Table 4. 10 Mediation Effect

Path	Path Coefficient	SE	T-test	P-Values	Bootstrap Confidence Interval		Results
					LCL	UCL	
DT -> SQR -> CS	0.114	0.032	3.453	0.001	0.053	0.180	Accepted
DT -> SQA -> CS	0.282	0.047	5.985	0.000	0.185	0.368	Accepted
DT -> SQE -> CS	0.047	0.037	1.240	0.215	-0.027	0.120	Rejected

4.9. A Synopsis of the Results

Table 4:12 summarises the research findings. The study accepts 8 hypotheses while rejecting H7 and H10.

Table 4. 11 Synopsis of the Results

Hypothesis	Statement	Results
H1	Digital technologies have a positive effect on responsiveness.	Accepted
H2	Digital technologies have a positive effect on accuracy.	Accepted
H3	Digital technologies have a positive effect on efficiency.	Accepted
H4	Digital technologies have a positive effect on customer satisfaction.	Accepted
H5	Responsiveness has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.	Accepted
H6	Accuracy has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.	Accepted
H7	Efficiency has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.	Rejected
H8	Responsiveness mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.	Accepted
H9	Accuracy mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.	Accepted
H10	Efficiency mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction.	Rejected

4.10. Summary of Chapter 4

This chapter discusses the statistical analysis of data obtained from Pakistani courier companies' walk-in customers through a questionnaire. It provides the statistical techniques used for hypothesis testing on the collected research data. First, the data was screened before the statistical process started. The measurement model study on convergent and discriminant validity was conducted thereafter. The results obtained were sufficient to proceed with validating the measurement for the structural model. It has tested, through structural equation modelling, the hypothesised relationship of variables with the help of SMART PLS 3.0 software by Ringle et al., (2015). The results of the study indicate that ten hypotheses were tested; eight hypotheses were accepted and two were rejected.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSIONS and CONCLUSION

This chapter aims to synthesise the study's core findings and objectives, as stated at the start. This chapter takes a critical look at how the research adds to what is already known about how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction in the courier industry, especially when it comes to roles like speed, accuracy, and responsiveness. It also wraps up the chapter by highlighting theoretical and practical implications, actionable recommendations for industry practitioners, limitations of the study, and suggestions for future research avenues.

5.1. Summary of Principal Research Outcomes

The study aims to establish how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. The results indicated that digital technologies enhance responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. These results prove that the more courier services adopt digital technologies, the more they can meet and exceed customer expectations, increasing overall satisfaction (Greengard, 2015; Setiawati et al., 2022).

Another focus of this study is responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, which act as mediators between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. Applying the SERVQUAL model by Parasuraman et al., (1988), it has been proven that these dimensions have a quintessential role in transforming technological advancement into customer experience (Ricardianto et al., 2021; Akoğlu et al., 2022). Responsiveness, or the ability to quickly respond to customer enquiries and reports in real-time, became a key determinant of customer satisfaction, with digital solutions at the forefront, such as mobile apps and IoT systems (Erboz, 2017; Serafini et al., 2018; Rane et al., 2024; Chau et al., 2025). GPS tracking and automated systems have greatly enhanced accuracy, which is the ability of shipments to arrive at their destinations on time and without damage (Ivanov et al., 2019; Jean, 2024). Finally, efficiency, coupled with AI and automation, has facilitated delivery processes, reducing delays and operational errors and improving customer satisfaction (Matt et al., 2020; Riad et al., 2024).

The research depicted various challenges and opportunities in the thriving Pakistan courier industry. The sector is currently positioned on a digital adoption curve; however, it still encounters several significant challenges, including inconsistency in technology implementation, infrastructural deficiencies, and regulatory issues (Mordor Intelligence, 2024).

This development in the field of e-commerce growth carries immense potential for courier companies to welcome digital technologies, thus positioning them better for operation and service delivery. Companies in Pakistan's courier industry using digital technologies will significantly improve their ability to meet customer expectations and enhance customer satisfaction. (United Sol, 2023).

The current study used a quantitative research design to achieve its objectives. The study targeted walk-in customers in Pakistan's courier industry. The current study accessed respondents using a random sampling procedure. The researcher adapted a questionnaire using a 7-point Likert scale to collect data from the respondents. Before the final survey, the researcher pretested the questionnaire and conducted a pilot test to ensure its validity and reliability. According to the final survey, the respondents' response rate was 84.66%.

The present study's descriptive analysis shows that its customers perceive digital technologies in Pakistan's courier industry positively. Next, structural equation modelling was deployed using the SMART PLS 3.0 software to test both the measurement and structural models of the study. First, we tested all the constructs for their convergent and discriminant validity in the measurement model. The test results showed no issues with convergent and discriminant validity among the constructs. The next stage involved testing the hypotheses proposed by the current study using a structural model. The researcher outlined four research questions and ten hypotheses.

Hypothesis testing gave rich insights into the relationships between digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction in the Pakistani courier industry. All the hypotheses that concern the direct influence of digital technologies on responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction were supported, proving that digital technologies enhance responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, we discover that both responsiveness and accuracy have a positive impact on customer satisfaction, serving as crucial intermediaries between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. However, SQE hypotheses of direct and mediating effects between digital technologies and customer satisfaction were unsupported. It then follows that, though digital technologies improve SQE, the improvement does not actually trickle directly or indirectly into customer

satisfaction. These results indicate the central roles that responsiveness and accuracy play in connecting digital technology adoption to attain significant customer satisfaction in the courier industry. The following section gives a brief discussion of the findings of the current study.

5.2. Relationship of Digital Technologies with Responsiveness, Accuracy, Efficiency, and Customer Satisfaction

Nowadays, in the service-based economy, customer satisfaction remains one of the critical determinants for the success and competitiveness of all firms in every industry. Many studies indicate that customer satisfaction depends on several service quality components, such as reliability (accuracy), responsiveness, and efficiency. Additionally, integrating digital technologies has become important for enhancing customer satisfaction by improving various service quality components. Insights into the level of digitalisation in industries like banking, telecommunications, health, and logistics show that it has directly impacted the customer's perception and relationship with the service provider.

The banking industry can offer convenience, real-time transaction information, and personalised financial management thanks to mobile apps and online banking systems. At the same time, research shows that these technologies significantly improve customer satisfaction through better user friendliness, ease of answering user enquiries, and prompt response to service queries (Dootson et al., 2016). In the telecommunications industry, real-time support offers from digital platforms can facilitate customer satisfaction by providing service customisation and instantaneous responses to user enquiries, thus increasing customer satisfaction (Wang et al., 2018). Digital technologies, such as telemedicine and automated patient management systems, have significantly improved the healthcare industry. Electronic health records not only transmit information but also effectively support doctors and patients in choosing more suitable therapies; as a result, patients' experiences with accurate and efficient treatments can increase their satisfaction (Lee and Baker, 2017).

Digital technologies have fundamentally changed how the logistics and courier industry shapes customer satisfaction. Customers now anticipate real-time tracking of their shipments. They expect their parcels to arrive on time, as well as status updates on their orders. Technologies like automation, GPS tracking devices, and AI-supported customer service tools cater to customer

expectations and improve customer satisfaction (Rai et al., 2006). These operations have become more efficient and transparent, which inspires trust, an important factor from a relationship marketing perspective in this industry since retaining customers is crucial for this business.

On the other hand, digital technologies are relevant to SQC, which is a key driver of customer satisfaction. The ability to track the delivery will reduce customer uncertainty and anxiety while giving them a sense of control over the service and improving customer satisfaction (Greengard, 2015). Customers receive parcel mail outcomes (delivered parcels at destinations) through automated sorting systems, AI-based delivery routes, and technologies that reduce errors. According to Ivanov et al., (2019), these technologies concentrate on delivering the package punctually and at the correct location, which significantly influences the perception of service reliability and quality.

Mobile applications and self-service portals have also redefined customer contact by enabling instant access to services with minimal human interaction. Customers can independently schedule deliveries, track shipments, and resolve problems with the help of these technologies, resulting in increased convenience and customer satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 2005). The ability to seamlessly provide rapid, easy-to-use digital interfaces has recently become a key demand in shaping positive customer experiences in instances where speed and accuracy are important in-service industries.

Hypothesis 1: Digital technologies have a positive effect on responsiveness. The findings supported the hypothesis that adopting digital technologies, like real-time tracking and mobile apps, facilitates responsiveness in courier industry firms. With digital technologies, firms will be able to render timely updates on status, provide rapid responses to customer enquiries, and resolve issues efficiently. Literature available on the subject, such as Parasuraman et al., (1988), supports this finding that responsiveness is one of the critical factors in service quality to drive customer satisfaction. As a result, the study's findings significantly improved responsiveness, leading to the acceptance of H1. The evidence proves that digital technologies have a positive effect on responsiveness in Pakistan's courier industry, which was the study's main goal.

Hypothesis 2: Digital technologies have a positive effect on accuracy. The results confirm that GPS tracking and automated sorting systems enhance delivery accuracy, ensuring that packages arrive on time and at the correct destination. Such increased accuracy, reflected in reduced

delivery errors and enhanced reliability, later directly contributes to increased customer satisfaction. The result is consistent with findings in the literature review, for example, Ivanov et al., (2019), who indicated how digital technologies serve to enhance the level of logistics accuracy. Therefore, we have accepted hypothesis H2, demonstrating the positive impact of digital technologies on accuracy in Pakistan's courier industry. Consequently, we have fulfilled another aspect of objective 1.

Hypothesis 3: Digital technologies have a positive effect on efficiency. Thus, we have found strong evidence to support this hypothesis: digital technologies have enhanced the efficiency of courier operations. Digital technologies, such as automation and AI-driven systems, streamline operations by automating key processes such as routing, sorting, and customer service management, which in turn reduces delays and operational expenses. These findings align with the results of Cronin & Taylor (1992), who contended that service efficiency is a vital determinant of customer satisfaction for those industries where speed is important. Digital technologies positively impact the efficiency of the Pakistani courier industry, thereby fulfilling another requirement of Objective 1.

Hypothesis 4 (H4) tested the direct impact of digital technologies on customer satisfaction. To support this, the study's findings revealed that digital technologies had a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Real-time tracking, process automation, and self-service platforms improved customer experiences in terms of increased transparency, fewer delivery errors, and better delivery control. Customers were more satisfied with services that used digital technologies. This conclusion is in line with Greengard (2015), who has argued that using digital tools makes the services more reliable, eventually building trust among customers. Therefore, we can agree with H4, which says that digital technologies directly and positively improve customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. This satisfies Objective 1's last requirement.

The primary aim of Objective 1 was to investigate the impact of digital technologies on the main service quality components—responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction—within Pakistan's courier industry. We tested Hypothesis 1, Hypothesis 2, Hypothesis 3, and Hypothesis 4 to determine if we met this objective. We met Objective 1 by investigating the impact of digital technologies on the courier industry in Pakistan, specifically in terms of speed, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. We evaluated the four hypotheses. These findings have confirmed that digital technologies significantly improve responsiveness, accuracy,

efficiency, and customer satisfaction. Real-time tracking and mobile applications enhanced responsiveness by facilitating timely communication and resolving issues promptly. Digital tools, in turn, supported accuracy, ensuring accurate and reliable delivery. Automation and AI technologies have increased efficiency, resulting in improved operational efficiency and delivery speed. Digital technologies improved the quality of all service components. Digital technologies have a positive and significant effect on both service quality components and customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry, thus accomplishing Objective 1.

Conclusion: Digital technologies have implications not only for service quality components but also positively affect customer satisfaction. The Pakistani courier industry is still vigorously struggling to implement digital technologies fully to improve service quality and customer satisfaction. Therefore, adopting more digital technologies can help them overcome this hurdle and improve customer satisfaction. Soon, it will be crucial to provide each customer with a rapid and easy-to-use digital interface that ensures outstanding efficiency and speed, especially in service industries where speed and accuracy significantly shape positive customer experiences.

5.3. Relationship of Responsiveness, Accuracy, and Efficiency with Customer Satisfaction

Service industries, particularly logistics and courier services, closely link responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. Research has shown that responding promptly to customers' needs significantly influences their satisfaction, as timely communication fosters customer trust and loyalty (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Kassim & Abdullah, 2010). Customers expect error-free services, so accuracy is just as important for service delivery. Not being able to provide error-free services, like deliveries being late or lost, leads to much lower customer satisfaction ratings than other services (Rai et al., 2006). Efficiency therefore helps streamline and minimise costs. However, responsiveness and accuracy have less of a direct impact on customer satisfaction because customers do not necessarily view operational speed but timely updates and precision in delivery (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). The three dimensions contributing to service quality, responsiveness, and accuracy are associated with high degrees of customer satisfaction in the courier industry, based on the literature (Oliver, 1999; Greengard, 2015).

In this regard, objective 2 of the study is to explore the impacts of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency on customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. In time-sensitive and reliable

service industries, these three SQCs are critical to customers' perceptions of service delivery and satisfaction. We tested the proposed hypotheses 5, 6, and 7 to achieve this objective.

Hypothesis 5: Responsiveness has a positive influence on customer satisfaction. Responsiveness refers to the firm's capability to deliver its services as fast as possible, react swiftly to enquiries forwarded by customers, and settle problems without delay. In the courier industry, responsiveness becomes all the more essential because customers expect information related to the movement of their shipments in real time and answers to their queries to be similarly prompt. The study results supported H5, which indicated a significant positive relationship between responsiveness and customer satisfaction. This finding corresponds to the earlier research of Parasuraman et al. (1988), where responsiveness was identified as one of the key dimensions of service quality influencing customer satisfaction. The support for H5 reveals that responsiveness is one of the major determinants of customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry, and the greater the improvement in responsiveness using digital technologies, the higher the contribution to customer satisfaction. As a result, H5 partially achieves Objective 2.

The goal of Hypothesis 6 (H6) was to ascertain whether accuracy positively affects customer satisfaction. In the courier industry, accuracy is defined as the timely and error-free delivery of packages to the correct location. Any instance of inaccuracy in deliveries, or even delays, may lead to customer dissatisfaction. This aspect will, therefore, be one of the most critical determinants in assessing service quality. The study's results validate H6, indicating a significant and positive relationship between accuracy and customer satisfaction. This again is supported by Ivanov et al., (2019), who proposed that the delivery process needs proper improvement in its accuracy to build trust among customers and develop satisfaction. Customers become satisfied with the services provided when the delivery is error-free and made on time. Thus, accuracy is one of the key components in the overall customer experience. Accepting H6 implies that accuracy plays a significant role in influencing customer satisfaction, thereby contributing to Objective 2.

H7, therefore, hypothesised that efficiency positively affects customer satisfaction. For efficiency, smooth processes and automated systems enable faster and more cost-effective delivery. Therefore, we anticipated that fewer delays in providing prompt service would boost customer satisfaction levels. Nevertheless, the findings of this study led to the rejection of H7, which means that digital technologies enhance firms' operational efficiencies but have a

negligible effect on customer satisfaction. This finding contradicts previous studies such as Cronin & Taylor, 1992, which identified efficiency as a critical driver of satisfaction within the service industries. In the courier industry, customers will be more concerned about timely updates, responsiveness, proper deliveries, and accuracy than with internal operational efficiencies. As a result, while efficiency is important to the company's performance, its impact on customer satisfaction is less direct in this context. As a result, we rejected H7, suggesting that efficiency has a limited impact on customer satisfaction and a partial achievement of Objective 2. In other words, Objective 2 was to study the impact of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency on customer satisfaction within Pakistan's courier industry. We tested the research hypotheses, revealing a significant and positive influence of responsiveness and accuracy on customer satisfaction. The acceptance of H5 and H6, respectively, confirms this. These findings again emphasise the necessity of timely responses and providing correct orders to ensure high customer satisfaction.

However, the rejection of H7 indicates that efficiency had no significant impact on customer satisfaction. This implies that, although efficiency is a more critical determinant in the internal processes of the courier industry, it does not affect how customers assess its service quality. The level of responsiveness and accuracy resonates more significantly with customers when evaluating their overall satisfaction with courier services. Therefore, we partially achieved objective 2 by demonstrating that responsiveness and accuracy are significant factors that contribute to customer satisfaction. On the other hand, efficiency had a small effect on customer happiness.

5.4. Mediating Role of Service Quality Response, Service Quality Accuracy, and Service Quality Efficiency

The literature well documents the mediation relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction through responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Digital technologies, such as real-time tracking and automation, make businesses more responsive by improving communication. This, in turn, cuts down on delays and increases customer satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Greengard, 2015). At the same time, accuracy plays a vital mediating role since accurate and timely deliveries through digital tools like GPS tracking create trust in customers and enhance satisfaction, according to Rai et al. (2006). Efficiency, however, is less pronounced as a mediating role since customers are more concerned with the responsiveness

and accuracy of operations than operational efficiency when evaluating satisfaction with service (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). As a result, the effect of digital technologies on customer satisfaction is responsiveness and accuracy, with efficiency playing a less significant role in shaping customer perceptions of service quality.

We designed Objective 3 to investigate whether responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency serve as mediating variables between digital technologies and customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. The important part that service quality components play in this process is essential for understanding how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction, both directly and by making service quality better. Hypothesis 8, Hypothesis 9, and Hypothesis 10 tested this mediation relationship.

Hypothesis 8 (H8) posited that responsiveness mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. The results confirmed this hypothesis, showing that improving responsiveness through digital technologies is an important mediator in enhancing customer satisfaction. In this study, digital technologies improved responsiveness, resulting in higher levels of customer satisfaction, which confirms responsiveness's mediating effect. As a result, we accept H8, which states that responsiveness is the link between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. This discovery will help us reach Objective 3.

Hypothesis 9 (H9) focused on whether accuracy acts as a mediator between digital technologies and customer satisfaction relationships. We have fulfilled the hypothesis, confirming accuracy's significant role as a mediating factor in the DT-CS relationship. In this study, digital technologies have improved accuracy, resulting in an increase in customer satisfaction. Therefore, we have accepted Hypothesis 9. Because accuracy mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction, we have achieved Objective 3.

Hypothesis 10 (H10) states that efficiency mediates the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. This hypothesis proved ineffective in this study because it revealed that efficiency's mediating effect on the DT-CS relationship was insignificant. While digital technologies such as automation and AI-driven systems improved operational efficiency, these improvements did not significantly impact customer satisfaction. This finding contrasts with earlier work by Cronin and Taylor (1992), which estimated that efficiency could be critical in determining customer satisfaction within specific industries. Customers in the courier industry

are more concerned about timely responses and correct deliveries than internal operational efficiency. As a result, H10 was not supported, and efficiency did not mediate the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. Therefore, achieving this aspect of Objective 3 was not possible.

Objective 3 investigated the mediating effects of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. Subsequently, the study proved that responsiveness and accuracy are important factors in the connection between the two concepts, which supports Hypotheses 8 and 9. The result implies that digital technologies boost customer satisfaction by enhancing responsiveness and accuracy, crucial aspects of the courier industry that customers highly value.

However, the fact that Hypothesis 10 was not supported suggests that while digital technologies improve efficiency, this factor does not significantly influence the relationship between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. In terms of perceived courier service satisfaction, customers seem to place a higher value on responsiveness and accuracy, suggesting that efficiency alone may not be as transparent or directly influential in shaping customer perceptions of service quality. In the end, we partially met Objective 3 by showing that responsiveness and accuracy were the main factors that led to customer satisfaction with digital technologies, while efficiency played a less important role.

The findings of this study therefore conclude that digital technologies significantly enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, all of which are key SQC in Pakistan's courier industry. This research also established that digital technologies directly enhance customer satisfaction through improved responsiveness and accuracy, which would be critical to delivering seamless and reliable service. While automation and AI-driven systems improve overall efficiency, their impact on customer satisfaction is less direct compared to responsiveness and accuracy, which customers value most in assessing service quality. The study also shows that responsiveness and accuracy play a supporting role in the connection between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. The result highlights how important it is to communicate and provide services on time to increase customer satisfaction. Because of this, the study makes it clear that courier companies need to invest in digital technologies that guarantee speed and accuracy to keep their competitive edge in today's constantly changing digital world.

5.5. Implications of the Current Research

The current study makes several important contributions to the existing literature on service quality, digital technologies, and customer satisfaction, especially in the setting of the courier industry. These findings provide an extension of the theoretical insights from the SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman et al., (1988), which includes responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency as mediators in the causal linkage of digital technologies with customer satisfaction. These small pieces of information add a whole new dimension of complexity to conventional service quality frameworks, as well as nuanced views on how digital technologies affect customer satisfaction in service sectors.

5.5.1. Theoretical Implications

This study makes one of the key theoretical contributions by integrating digital technologies into the widely accepted SERVQUAL model. The generally applied SERVQUAL has focused on five basic dimensions of service quality: reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responsiveness. We still need to address how digital technology shapes these dimensions. The current study has filled the gap by illustrating how digital technologies specifically enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency to improve customer satisfaction in the courier industry. These results show how digital technologies like real-time tracking, automation, and mobile apps have changed how responsiveness and accuracy are managed, especially in industries that value on-time and accurate delivery. According to what we learnt from these results, future theories of service quality should take into account digital technologies as clear ways to improve service quality. This is especially true for service industries that depend on technology to do their jobs.

The study confirms that responsiveness and accuracy are the main mediators between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. The results reinforce previous research by demonstrating that digital technologies, specifically responsiveness and accuracy, have a greater impact on customer satisfaction than efficiency. The study revealed an unexpected finding: although adopting digital technologies improves efficiency, it does not serve as a significant mediator between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. The efficiency variable also would run in contrast with traditional assumptions of the role of efficiency in service quality and

customer satisfaction, especially in industries where timely service delivery is critical. Nevertheless, the results of this study show that, for customers, responsiveness and accuracy are more important than efficiency in their general satisfaction judgement about the service. So, one area that could be useful for future research is finding out when efficiency has a bigger effect on customer satisfaction, depending on things like the type of service, what the customer expects, or other factors that are unique to the industry.

In light of this research, the implications of SERVQUAL underscore how significantly digital technologies have played a role in enhancing service quality and customer satisfaction. The results assert that customers must perceive mobile apps, such as those that track shipments, locate facilities, or provide time estimates, as useful and user-friendly. This is because how people see technology has a big impact on how they accept and use it. In this way, SERVQUAL creates a basis for understanding how to use digital technologies to improve important aspects of service quality, such as responsiveness and accuracy. These are crucial for enhancing customer perceptions about service reliability and satisfaction. According to the expectancy disconfirmation paradigm, these improvements in service quality lead to positive disconfirmation, which means that when service performance goes above and beyond what the customer expected, they are happier. This theory implies that businesses should focus on adopting digital technologies, ensuring they meet customer expectations, and improving the tangible aspects of service quality, particularly responsiveness and accuracy, for maximum customer satisfaction.

Finally, it helps extend the theoretical understanding of service quality and customer satisfaction in an emerging market like Pakistan's courier industry. It also underlines that digital technologies could help mitigate traditional challenges in service delivery, such as poor infrastructure and slow communication systems, by increasing responsiveness and accuracy. These findings have broad theoretical implications, especially for service providers in emerging economies, where adopting digital technologies is likely to enhance service quality and customer satisfaction. This study paves the way for further investigation into the impact of digital technologies on service quality and customer satisfaction in various emerging markets, each of which may present distinct challenges or opportunities that could facilitate or hinder the adoption of digital technologies.

In sum, this research makes several key theoretical contributions: It integrates digital

technologies into the SERVQUAL model, and it emphasises the mediating functions of responsiveness and accuracy, and it nuances the role of efficiency in customer satisfaction. It expands the role of digital technologies within the framework of service quality theory. The theoretical discussion of digital technologies and service quality is enhanced by these findings. This is especially true in fields where providing accurate and on-time services is essential for customer satisfaction.

5.5.2. Practical Implications

Therefore, this study underlines the importance for practitioners, especially in the courier industry, to invest in digital technologies and further develop responsiveness and accuracy to drive customer satisfaction. Customers place a high value on real-time communication and correct service delivery, as shown by the findings; therefore, tools such as GPS tracking, automated sorting, and mobile apps are crucial for enhancing the level of service quality. Companies operating in Pakistan, along with other emerging markets, should be more focused on adopting technologies that ensure increased operational transparency and reduced delivery errors since these drivers ensure high customer satisfaction.

Second, while some efficiencies, such as automation and route optimisation, contribute to courier companies' overall success, the research suggests they are less immediately apparent to customers. To achieve high customer satisfaction, firms should invest in customer-facing digital technologies that improve communication and delivery precision. Thus, a practical implication for managers is very clear: investment in customer-centric technologies that enhance visibility and service reliability should be a core strategy for maintaining competitive advantage.

The managerial contribution of this study is to offer specific strategies for leveraging digital technologies to improve customer satisfaction. Managers in the courier industry should focus on integrating solutions that are responsive to customer needs and enhance service accuracy. Employees' training in the effective use of digital tools will also be crucial for maximising the benefits of technology adoption. The findings also indicate that although operational efficiency is necessary for cost management and scalability, customer satisfaction is responsive to accuracy; therefore, managers should focus on enhancing service quality to achieve customer loyalty and positive brand perception.

The study in Pakistan is imperative for policymakers and regulators to provide an enabling environment for digital technology adoption, especially in the logistics and courier industries. It is of foremost importance that the industry has the infrastructural and technological wherewithal to install GPS tracking, automation, and real-time communication systems to improve service quality. Policymakers must consider regulations that will enable digital innovation and remove the obstacles to technology adoption to enable local courier companies to compete effectively in the global digital economy.

5.6. Limitations of the Research

Although this study has garnered valuable insights into how digital technologies affect responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction within Pakistan's courier industry, a number of limitations must be recognised. These limitations highlight areas that necessitate additional research to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the subject.

The study's exclusive focus on Pakistan's courier industry poses a significant limitation. The study's findings provide deep insights into how digital technologies drive service quality and customer satisfaction in the country under investigation; however, they cannot be fully generalised to any other sector or region. The expectations about service quality, extent of digital technology adoption, and drivers of customer satisfaction can be radically different in other countries or industries, such as retail, health care, and financial services. Additionally, the wide variation in infrastructure, technological capabilities, and market dynamics across different regions of Pakistan can result in a change in the use of digital technologies and how customers perceive them. Such variation implies that the findings of the current study may not be directly applied to other industries or countries due to varying levels of digital maturity or service expectations. Therefore, future research could focus on comparing different industries, countries, or cities to understand the impact of digital technologies on service quality and customer satisfaction in different settings.

It has primarily focused on the overall use of digital technologies, although they are critical to improving responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Further, there was no examination of other emerging technologies increasingly influencing service industries, including AI, machine learning, blockchain, or predictive analytics. Beyond what this research can capture, these high-level technologies can further transform service delivery, improving operational efficiency and

boosting customer satisfaction. It does not consider how integrated digital platforms, such as end-to-end customer relationship management systems, can further facilitate a seamless and integrated customer experience. Future research can broaden this scope by better understanding the role of these emerging technologies in the service industry.

The research has adopted a cross-sectional design, which provides a snapshot of the relationship between digital technologies, service quality components, and customer satisfaction at any time. While the method is important for highlighting associations, it does not allow for an analysis of how those associations change over time. The implementation of digital technologies and their effect on service quality and customer satisfaction may be gradual. For instance, customers may perceive new technologies to change because they habituate with increased usage or because companies refine their processes to meet customer needs better. The cross-sectional nature of this study prevents the observation of long-term trends, such as how continuous improvement in digital technologies affects customer satisfaction over time. Therefore, future research must adopt a longitudinal study approach to capture the dynamic effect of digital technologies on both service quality and customer satisfaction.

Customers self-report through questionnaires, which may project various types of biases. Depending on their recent experience with the courier service, the respondents may provide socially desirable responses. There could also be a possibility of recall bias, such as customers not remembering some of the important details of their experience when asked about certain service quality components like responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Such bias could affect the data's reliability and, in turn, lead to an overestimation or underestimation of digital technologies' impact on customer satisfaction. Despite taking some measures during the design stage to reduce biases, it is crucial to always consider the inherent limitations of self-reported measures when interpreting results. Future studies may use objective performance data, such as real-time tracking logs and customer service response times, to supplement self-reported data for more robust analysis.

Although this research focused on how digital technologies may influence service quality and customer satisfaction, it did not consider the external contingencies that may affect these relationships. The economy, competitors' actions, government and regulatory rules, and Pakistan's technology infrastructure's limitations could all influence the use of digital

technologies and customers' perceptions of service quality. For instance, an unstable internet network or logistical barriers in rural areas could lead to digital technology issues such as unreliable real-time tracking, thereby affecting customer satisfaction. On the other hand, competitors' service innovation or government policy related to digital transformation may shape customer expectations and satisfaction. Future studies should examine how these external factors interact with digital technologies to influence service quality and customer satisfaction outcomes.

This study looked at the direct and indirect effects of digital technologies on service quality components and customer satisfaction. It did not consider the potential effects of moderating variables. Variables such as customer demographics, including age, income, digital literacy, customer expectations, frequency of service use, or complexity of deliveries, could moderate the effect of digital technologies on service quality and customer satisfaction. For example, we expect tech-savvy customers to have different expectations about using digital technologies compared to those who are less familiar with technology. Those deliveries are very frequent or valuable; the accuracy of digital technologies may be more critical than other service quality components. Investigating such moderating variables in future research will provide a fine-grained view of how different segments of customers perceive and derive value from digital technologies.

This study conceptualises customer satisfaction as a unidimensional construct, focussing on the impact of digital technologies and service quality components on overall satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is, however, a multi-dimensional construct that may include emotional satisfaction, loyalty intentions, and service recovery satisfaction. For example, a customer may express satisfaction with the promptness of delivery and responsiveness yet simultaneously experience dissatisfaction with the resolution of a service issue. This nuance of understanding customer satisfaction was not fully captured in the study, limiting the depth of analysis that could be achieved. Future research may investigate different customer satisfaction dimensions and understand how digital technologies affect various aspects of the customer experience.

While this study contributes to the understanding of how digital technologies influence service quality and customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry, it also has some limitations. Future research should look into these issues by using the results in different industries and

areas, adding new digital technologies, using longitudinal designs, and contemplating exogenous factors and moderator variables. Addressing such limitations will provide a deeper understanding of the long-term consequences of digital technologies on service quality and customer satisfaction.

5.7. Future Recommendations

The study's results yield the following recommendations: They are useful for effectively using digital technologies to further improve courier service in Pakistan. These recommendations aim to enhance responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, all of which significantly contribute to a positive customer experience.

The study identifies responsiveness as the most significant mediator between digital technologies and customer satisfaction. Therefore, to enable instant communication with customers, any courier company must invest in real-time tracking systems, mobile applications, and automated customer service platforms. Customers are becoming more accustomed to receiving real-time updates about their delivery status, as delays can significantly reduce their satisfaction ratings. On the other hand, courier companies can improve responsiveness—or, otherwise, customer satisfaction—by letting customers constantly access shipment updates and giving them the opportunity to interact with the company through various digital channels like mobile apps, websites, and SMS alerts. Furthermore, investments in AI-powered chatbots or virtual assistants will help solve customer queries faster, improving service responsiveness.

Accuracy was the prime driver of customer satisfaction, which means that courier companies have to focus their resources on how they can increase precision in delivery. Companies should capitalise on GPS-enabled tracking systems, automated sorting technologies, and route optimisation algorithms to minimise errors at each point of the delivery process. Ensuring correct delivery to the right addresses at the right time will help companies maintain customer confidence. It is desirable that courier companies invest in some predictive analytics tools that can estimate the possibility of disruption in deliveries due to traffic and weather conditions on that particular route and, therefore, plan to reroute the same for timely arrivals. Furthermore, the companies should implement quality control measures that reduce the likelihood of human error while sorting and delivering. Ensuring the accuracy of deliveries will improve customer perceptions of service reliability and overall satisfaction.

Although efficiency is a crucial aspect of operational performance, the study revealed that it has a less direct correlation with customer satisfaction than responsiveness and accuracy. This means that courier companies must make any efficiency enhancements from digital technologies visible to customers. To achieve this, digital technologies can communicate service improvements to customers, such as reduced delivery or processing time. For example, firms can quote delivery times when ordering and advise customers of reduced delivery windows where operational efficiencies allow. Providing dynamic delivery options, such as flexible delivery slots or same-day delivery, also increases the value of efficient operations for customers. When possible, companies should look to increase efficiency, particularly for customers, through loyalty programs or discounts based on speed and service efficiency.

While digital technologies are vital in enhancing service quality, they are only as effective as the personnel who can use such tools effectively. As a result, courier organisations should invest in training programs to help their employees fully utilise digital technology, such as real-time tracking systems, automated customer service tools, and route optimisation software. Employees who are proficient in using these technologies will be better equipped to handle customer enquiries, resolve issues promptly, and optimise delivery processes. Companies should provide regular training sessions to keep staff updated on new digital tools and emerging trends in the logistics industry. Furthermore, a customer-centric approach among employees using these technologies can significantly improve the customer experience. This will equip employees to promptly address customers' needs.

As digital technologies continue to evolve, customers are increasingly expecting to take control of their service experience. Thus, courier companies should provide self-service platforms that take full responsibility for customer delivery. Mobile apps and web portals should provide enough convenience for the customer to track the shipment, reschedule the delivery, or choose an alternative delivery location. The experience of customers provided with self-service options will also minimise burdens related to operations for the customer service team. Companies should integrate AI-driven customer service chatbots that can handle routine enquiries, freeing human agents to put more effort and attention into complex customer problems. Such initiatives will increase operational efficiency while also improving the overall customer experience by providing better service access and convenience.

In this context, the courier companies will have to continuously seek the customer feedback and act on it to maintain high levels of customer satisfaction. The post-delivery survey or feedback obtained by customers from mobile apps or websites will facilitate a deeper review of areas that need attention. Companies need to study customer complaints or suggestions and identify recurring issues like delays, wrong delivery, or failure of communication and devise ways to solve them. By using customer feedback and optimising service delivery, courier companies can refine their digital technologies to be competitive and meet customers' evolving expectations. Personalised responses to feedback or individual concerns demonstrate dedication to customer satisfaction and can foster enhanced customer loyalty.

While digital technologies are crucial to boosting the capacity of service quality, the companies must also consider Pakistan's local market and infrastructural limitations. In this regard, certain challenges concerning inconsistent internet connectivity, road conditions, and delivery in rural areas may affect the effectiveness of the digital tool. As a result, courier companies must develop localised strategies to address these issues, such as using mobile applications that operate offline or offering delivery options in remote areas. Working with local partners or government agencies to address infrastructure constraints would also improve service quality across the country.

Therefore, companies should adopt digital technology methods offering more responsiveness and accuracy, as these two drive customer satisfaction in Pakistan's courier industry. Self-service options and training in the use of better technology must accompany investment in customer-facing digital technologies to fully reap the benefits of digital transformation. Other ways to optimise gains involve making such efficiency gains more visible to customers and using feedback for continuous improvement. Courier companies should address these recommendations to improve customer satisfaction and provide a more reliable customer service experience.

Figure 5.1 Revised Framework

5.8. Revised Structural Model and Interpretation

The final structural model is an outcome derived by hypothesis testing. Hypotheses H1–H4 and H5–H6 were verified: digital technologies had a significant positive effect on responsiveness (H1), accuracy (H2) and efficiency (H3), and directly had a positive effect on customer satisfaction (H4). Responsiveness (H5) and accuracy (H6) were significant predictors for customer satisfaction, while there is no significance in the direct effect for efficiency (H7). Mediation test results showed responsiveness and accuracy intervened between digital technologies and customer satisfaction (H8 and H9), while in no instance does efficiency do so (H10).

The results led to an adjustment in the structural model depicted here. The diagram highlights the retained links with solid arrows and matching labels, whereas the eliminated efficiency→customer satisfaction link (H7) is shown with a dashed grey arrow. Note that the direct link between digital technologies and customer satisfaction (H4) remains in the final model since it is statistically significant and can explain a considerable amount of variance in customer satisfaction.

5.9. Evolution of the Framework

Within the first conceptual model outlined in Chapter 2, it was posited that digital technologies had an indirect effect upon customer satisfaction by improving responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency. Although literature supported this mediation hypothesis, behavioural evidence revealed a direct effect

upon customer satisfaction for digital technologies. Such a finding implies that customers perceive technology adoption—the epitomization within such features as real-time tracking information, automatic updates, and simple applications—with a direct contribution upon their satisfaction in addition to service quality dimensions improvement. Consequently, the refined model retains the DT→CS linkage (H4) and depicts the digitalisation impacts as direct and indirect with the interceding variables being responsiveness and accuracy.

The results further revealed that while digital technologies boosted efficiency, there was not a significant rise in customer satisfaction. That finding suggests customers value speediness and operational smoothness up to a point; yet, responsiveness defined by prompt communication and proper trouble-solving and accuracy defined by proper and complete shipments matter more to them. As such, the ultimate model numerically de-emphasizes the direct link between efficiency and customer satisfaction (H7) by depicting it as a dashed grey line.

As a result of including such empirical results, now the end concludes in a clearer, evidence-based model. The concluding story sketches out what it did with the basic model—highlighting what were supported or rejected hypotheses—and highlights the managerial importance behind investing in digital technologies, an investment which carries direct and indirect impacts on customer satisfaction in terms of enhanced responsiveness and accuracy.

5.10. Conclusion

The current study focused on exploring the effect of digital technologies on customer satisfaction through the B2C courier industry of Pakistan with specific interest for the mediating roles of responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency.

Using a quantitative design and analysing data through PLS-SEM, the study confirmed that digital technologies have a significant positive effect on responsiveness and accuracy, which in turn strongly enhance customer satisfaction. Efficiency, while operationally valuable, did not exert a significant direct effect on satisfaction. These findings provide empirical evidence that customers value reliable information updates and delivery accuracy more than speed alone.

The study contributes to theory by applying the SERVQUAL framework in a digitally supported courier setting and by providing an empirical test of responsiveness and accuracy's mediation. Through this, it fills an important gap within the extant literature for technology-fomented service quality for emerging markets. In practical terms, the findings highlight the need for strategic investment in such technologies as real-time tracking, IoT, data analytics, and automated interaction platforms for customer satisfaction improvements that can be measured.

One of the main contributions of the current study is the development of the Revised Structural Model (Figure 5.1), presented in the detail of Section 5.8 and elaborated further through the Evolution of the Framework presented in Section 5.9. This improved model integrates the validated relationships among digital technologies, responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, and customer satisfaction. It depicts the iterative refinement and empirical validating of the originally developed conceptual framework and therefore offers a definitive handbook for both academicians and industry leaders. Through the emphasis on the empirically validated mediation roles of responsiveness and accuracy, the model offers unambiguous guidance for courier operators who want their technological investment priorities focused on dimensions that directly affect the customer experience.

Overall, our study reveals that the digital evolution of the courier market needs to focus on those technologies that enable higher responsiveness and accuracy, since these factors impact customer satisfaction the most. The transformed structural model serves as both an empirical and conceptual guide for prospective studies and for managers who want to align digital strategies with strategies focused on service quality for the customer. Additional studies on

different geographical locations and service markets are recommended to refine and validate such a framework, thereby ensuring that the ever-evolving digital world is properly exploited for the delivery of greater customer value.

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APPENDIX.1: QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Sir/Madam

This questionnaire is to assist me in understanding the courier service user experience. It contains questions about the courier service experience concerning digital technologies and customer satisfaction. It is part of a PhD project at the University of the West of Scotland, Paisley. It aims to evaluate digital technologies for customer satisfaction in Pakistan's B2C supply chain of courier services.

Your response is needed to complete the questionnaire. Please feel reassured that there is no right or wrong answer. Some questions are about demographic information, responsiveness, accuracy, efficiency, the impact of digital technologies, and measuring customer satisfaction. I appreciate your contribution and time.

Section A: Demographic Information

Instructions: Please select the suitable

option. Please specify the gender.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to mention

Please select the education level.

- Matric (O-Level)
- Intermediate (A-Level)
- Graduate
- Postgraduate
- Prefer not to mention

How often do you use the courier service?

- Once a month
- More than once a month
- Once every three months
- Once every six months

What kind of shipments do you send out?

- Letter
- Parcel
- Heavy Shipment (Over 5 KG)
- All types of shipments

Which courier company do you mostly use?

- TCS
- LCS
- M&P
- Pakistan Post
- Call courier
- DHL
- UPS
- Any other company

How does the staff book the parcel?

- Manual Booking
- Computer-Based Booking
- Digital Device-Based Booking

To what extent do you agree or disagree with responsiveness? Please tick (✓) one box for each item. (Please rate where 1= Strongly disagree and 7= Strongly Agree)

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Somewhat Disagree 3	Neutral 4	Somewhat Agree 5	Agree 6	Strongly Agree 7
The courier company's customer services are easily accessible.							
The courier company's website has customer service representatives available online.							
The customer service representative gives a prompt response to customer queries.							
The customer service representative quickly resolves shipment-related queries.							

To what extent do you agree or disagree with Efficiency? Please tick (✓) one box for each item. (Please rate where 1 = Strongly Disagree and 7=Strongly Agree)

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Somewhat Disagree 3	Neutral 4	Somewhat Agree 5	Agree 6	Strongly Agree 7
The shipment tracking interface is user-friendly.							
The service delivery via all interfaces of the courier company's website is efficient.							
The online tracking part of the "web or app" is always available for customers.							
The ability to check shipment status is quick through the tracking interface.							

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the Accuracy? Please tick (✓) one box for each statement (Please rate where 1 = Strongly Disagree and 7=Strongly Agree)

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Somewhat Disagree 3	Neutral 4	Somewhat Agree 5	Agree 6	Strongly Agree 7
The parcel was delivered as per the communicated delivery date and time.							
In case a modification was made (either to the delivery address or time), delivery was completed as per updated information correctly.							
Riders ensured parcel delivery to the right person at the given address.							
Proof of delivery (image) always matches the delivery details.							
The package arrived in good condition.							
In case of an issue, a satisfactory solution was provided.							

To what extent do you agree or disagree with using Digital Technologies? Please tick (✓) one box for each item. (Please rate where 1= Strongly Disagree and 7=Strongly

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Somewhat Disagree 3	Neutral 4	Somewhat Agree 5	Agree 6	Strongly Agree 7
The courier company provides user-friendly online parcel management services (booking, drop-off, tracking, and delivery).							
The courier company offers digital payment solutions.*							
The courier company provides a user-friendly mobile app for parcel management services.							
The courier company is active on social platforms to share the latest updates and quickly respond to queries.							
The courier company provides digital assistance whenever required. **							

Agree)

To what extent do you agree or disagree with Customer Satisfaction? Please tick (✓) one box for each item. (Please rate where 1= Strongly Disagree and 7=Strongly Agree)

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Somewhat Disagree 3	Neutral 4	Somewhat Agree 5	Agree 6	Strongly Agree 7
I'm satisfied with the services of this company.							
This company meets my expectations.							
I've had especially good experiences with this company.							
I have trust in this company.							
I recommend this company to friends and family members.							

APPENDIX.2: MEASUREMENT ITEMS

Items for Measuring Customer Satisfaction

Sr. No.	Items	Source
1	I'm satisfied with the services of this company.	Hunter & Garnefeld (2008)
2	This company totally meets my expectations.	
3	I've had especially good experiences with this company.	
4	I have trust in this company.	
5	I recommend this company to friends and family members.	

Items for Measuring Responsiveness

Sr. No.	Items	Source
1	The courier company's customer services are easily accessible.	Md. Ariff et al., (2012)
2	The courier company's website has customer service representatives available online.	
3	The customer service representative gives a prompt response to customer queries.	
4	The customer service representative quickly resolves shipment-related queries.	

Items for Measuring Accuracy

Sr. No.	Items	Source
1	The parcel was delivered as per the communicated delivery date and time.	(Md. Ariff et al., 2012; Zouari & Abdelhedi, 2021)
2	In case a modification was made (either to the delivery address or time), delivery was completed as per the updated information correctly.	
3	Riders ensured parcel delivery to the right person at the given address.	
4	Proof of delivery (image) always matches the delivery details.	
5	The package arrived in good condition.	
6	In case of an issue, a satisfactory solution was provided	

Items for Measuring Efficiency

Sr. No.	Items	Source
1	The shipment tracking interface is user-friendly.	Md. Ariff et al., (2012)
2	The service delivery via all interfaces of the courier company's website is efficient.	
3	The online tracking part of the "web or app" is always available for customers.	
4	The ability to check	

	shipment status is quick through the tracking interface.	
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Items for Measuring Digital Technologies

Sr. No.	Items	Source
1	The courier company provides user-friendly online parcel management services (booking, drop off, tracking, and delivery).	(Zouari & Abdelhedi, 2021; Md. Ariff et al., 2012)
2	The courier company offers digital payment solutions.	
3	The courier company provides a user-friendly mobile app for parcel management services.	
4	The courier company is active on social platforms to share the latest updates and respond to queries in a timely manner.	
5	The courier company provides digital assistance whenever required.	

APPENDIX.3: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Participant Information Sheet

Thesis Topic: Digital Technology: A Tool of Customer Satisfaction in the B2C Supply Chain of Courier Services in Pakistan

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, you need to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. I will also read the essential parts of this information to you before participating. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Covid-19 Safety Guidelines

Please note that this survey will be conducted under the Pakistan government's COVID-19 safety guidelines to ensure the safety of both the researcher and the participant. This entails that throughout the survey, a 2-meter social distance will be observed, and a face mask is worn except where the survey is conducted in an open space or where the participant is exempted from wearing a mask on a health basis.

What is the purpose of this study?

I am a PhD research student at the University of the West of Scotland, researching the digital technologies in the courier supply chain. This research focuses on critically evaluating digital technologies as a tool for customer satisfaction in Pakistan's supply chain of courier services.

Why have I been chosen?

You have chosen to participate in this research because of your direct (or indirect) experience with the courier supply chain. In general, participants in this study are selected based on their experience and knowledge of the research topic and not on educational qualification, political, religious, or ethnic affiliations.

Do I have to take part?

There will be no consequences if you choose not to participate, answer any question, or even discontinue the survey at any given time, as participation in this research is not mandatory for any participant.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you agree to participate in this research, you will be asked to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire will last for a minimum of 10 and 15 minutes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There is no risk because the information you share remains confidential.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your participation in this questionnaire will immensely contribute to understanding the impact of digital technologies on courier service customers' satisfaction.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) is the institution in charge of handling the data for this research. All activities that involve handling personal data are under the supervision of the UWS Data Protection office and can be reached via this email address: dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

The provision of your consent will serve as the legal basis for handling your data. You can give verbal permission for your data to be used in this research before and after the researcher has fully briefed you verbally and provided you with an information sheet.

Participation in this study will be kept confidential to ensure that the data and the use of all the given information are restricted only for this research. Also, each participant will be given a code name, and should they request anonymity of either themselves or the individuals they talk about, their identity will be kept confidential. Participants who wish to withdraw from participating have the right to do so within 28 days after collecting the data. You can do that through my contact details at the end of this form.

If you have any concerns regarding handling your data, you should please inform UWS through dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you still have reservations, contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) at [www.https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights](https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights).

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The study is strictly for academic purposes only, and it is non-profit or commercial. The findings of this study will mainly form part of my final thesis for the award of a doctorate in Business Studies. The results may also be published as journal articles, conference papers, and book chapters during and after my studies.

Who has reviewed the study?

The body that will review this study shall be the School of Business and Creative Industries Ethics Committee at UWS.

Contact for further information.

If you require any further information, please contact:

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Thank you for taking part in this study.

APPENDIX.4: UWS LETTER-ETHICS APPLICATION APPROVAL

21/07/2022

Dear Ather Hafeez,

Your application 18348: Digital Technology: A Tool of Customer Satisfaction in the Supply Chain of Courier Services in Pakistan, submission reference 15521, has been approved, with conditions, by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below.**

Please add details of how the data will be held securely and confidentially.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. Good luck with your research.

Dr. John Quinn

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AVE	Average Variance Extracted
B2C	Business to Consumer
BDA	Big Data Analytics
CC	Courier Companies
CI	Courier Industry
CEP	Courier, Express, Parcel
COD	Cash on Delivery
CONV	Construct Validity
CouQual	Courier Quality
CR	Composite Reliability
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CS	Customer satisfaction
CSV	Courier Services
CV	Content Validity
CVAL	Convergent Validity
DHL	Deutsche Post DHL Group
DT	Digital Technologies
DV	Discriminant Validity
Factor Loadings	FL
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GPS	Global Positioning System
IoT	Internet of Things
LCS	Leopard Courier Service
LS	Logistics Services
LSQ	Logistics Service Quality

M&P	M&P Courier
ML	Machine Learning
PLS	Partial Least Square
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
ROI	Return on Investment
SBP	State Bank of Pakistan
SE	Standard Error
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SQ	Service Quality
SQA	Service Quality Accuracy
SQC	SERVQUAL components
SQE	Service Quality Efficiency
SQR	Service Quality Responsiveness
TCS	Tranzum Courier Service
UAE	United Arab Emirates
UPS	Universal Parcel Services
VIF	Variance Inflation Factors
WOM	Word-of-Mouth